

PreMETS

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training

D2.5 Train-the-trainers toolkit

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Module TN1: Learner happiness, motivation, engagement
and performance strategies
[Booklet]

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A. Introduction

The digital transformation of higher education was heavily accelerated by the COVID-19 crisis which posed the need for high quality and inclusive digital education. Such a challenge cannot be tackled in an isolated manner as it requires a true systemic and holistic approach to provide a suitable solution. There is a strong link between boosting the digital skills of three main actors (university lecturers, university administrators and students) and the improvement of EU's digital readiness towards inclusive and high-quality online education delivery (HBR, 2020, EC, 2020). Whether isolated efforts of digitalization of higher education have been done recently, the outcomes of this approach have deemed to be inefficient leading to: frustrated academic staff unable to cope with technology, ineffectiveness of the taught content and delivery mode, limited engagement of students (lack of focus/attention/interest, limited connectionism and constructivism), lack of inclusiveness and personalized online teaching, rigidity of university administrators towards online teaching, and overall confusion and concern over the value of university services in such online format (EACEA, 2020).

Students (trainees) are meeting substantial skill-gaps such as: Inability to interact with lecturers in an online environment and foster connectionism and constructivism; absence of online learning skills such as being well organized, self-motivated, and possess a high degree of time management skills in order to keep up with the pace of the course (i.e., text-based interaction takes more time); lack of skills to fight the sense of isolation and psychological well-being; lack of active learning skills; lack of ability to understand responsible/ethical digital education utilisation.

B. Motivating Learners

Higher education institutions are expected to produce skillful, problem solvers, and competent graduates. This becomes possible when the instructors are using the appropriate teaching methodology and the learners are active and empowered in the teaching-learning process.

Of the factors that influence student learning, motivation is surely one of the most potent (Svinicki, 1999). An instructor can improve a student's intrinsic motivation through external stimuli, by setting realistic incremental task-based goals, and by allowing students to work autonomously through them.

There are hundreds of studies which show evidence to support the notion that goal setting increases success rates (e.g. Turkay, 2014).

“Task-based goals had large and robust positive effects on the level of task completion, and [...] also increased course performance” (Clark et al. 2016).

According to Clark et al. (2016) “goal setting is a low-cost, scalable and feasible intervention that could improve college outcomes and could be built into the technology used to deliver these course components”.

Engagement is fostered by allowing students to study on their own terms; anytime, anywhere. Studies into workforce productivity have shown that allowing people to work from anywhere led to as much as a 50% increase in productivity (Koulopoulos and Keldsen, 2016).

WHY DO WE PERCEIVE THAT PRODUCTIVITY IN THE WORKPLACE SHOULD DIFFER FROM PRODUCTIVITY IN EDUCATION?

People who are actively engaged, no matter the situation, are more productive. Nearly 50% of the connected generation prefer working non-traditional hours and over 60% use mobile devices to manage their lives (Aruba, 2014), this should be used to educators' advantage. On average people spend around five and a half hours daily, actively engaged on some form of Internet-connected device, these figures are massively augmented, up to thirteen hours a day, for younger generations (Koulopoulos and Keldsen, 2016).

Educators need to harness this mobile potential and, if only utilising a fraction of this time, can massively enhance learning outcomes. However, even though technology can aid motivation and engagement it does not automatically lead to better learning, it is only when this engagement can be harnessed for learning that there will be any academic benefit (Higgins, 2012), again stressing the need for pedagogically sound implementation. Empowerment is improved through increased student agency and autonomy, as well as interdependency, these are all supported by student-centred methodologies which aim to improve the “students’

capacity to act or exert themselves into their learning” (Sheninger and Murray, 2017).

An example is differentiated instruction, this is a pedagogical strategy that allows students to work collaboratively on meaningful tasks at their own level and pace (Prensky, 2001) through activities such as task-based learning. Meta-analysis studies have consistently shown that collaborative learning has wide-spread positive influence on academic achievement, self-esteem, quality of interpersonal interactions as well as student attitudes (Prince, 2004).

The number of collaborative tasks implemented also has an effect on the results. Springer et al. (1999) investigated this further and found that the best results, in terms of positive effect size, were to be obtained through medium amounts of group work. However, it has also been said that self-directed learning may have a negative effect (Colliver,2000).

According to Pitler et al. (2007), it is, therefore, critical to correctly implement technology into instructional scenarios to increase learner agency and facilitate “analytical and critical thinking and the collaboration championed in the constructivist approach to education”.

C. From constructivism to connectivism

The constructivism learning theory has evolved to be in today's era of social media, a connectivism learning theory that considers that learning occurs through connections learners make with each other as well as with the learning content. Learning through connections is an important piece of putting the learner at the center of the learning process; a process that empowers the learner to be fully engaged in the learning process and to be the builder of her own knowledge using her curiosity and imagination. Constructivism has been and continues to be a hot topic in learning theories.

In online learning environments, cognitive learning theories provide a framework for a learner centered approach to instructional design.

These theories emphasize constructivist orientations to learning, such as generative learning (Jonassen, 1988), situated learning (Chiou, 1992), and problem-based learning (Savery, J. R., & Duffy, T. M., 1995).

Constructivist orientations aim to assist the learner in selecting appropriate information pertaining to the learning content, organizing information into internally consistent concepts, and integrating new knowledge, making it personally relevant and meaningful (Lawson, 2011).

The constructivist model of education provides a significant environment for authentic learning, active learning, and reflective learning.

The six main characteristics of constructivist learning environments as noted by (Jonassen, 1994) are:

1. Constructivist learning environments provide multiple and complex representations of reality, avoiding simplifications.
2. Constructivist learning environments emphasize knowledge construction in relation to its content instead of knowledge reproduction.
3. Constructivist learning environments emphasize authentic tasks in a meaningful context rather than abstract instruction out of context.
4. Constructivist learning environments provide learning environments such as real- world setting or case-based learning instead of predetermined sequences of instruction.
5. Constructivist learning environments encourage practices based on thoughtful reflection.
6. Constructivist learning environments support collaborative learning through social negotiation, instead of competition among learners.

As an extension of constructivism, connectivism emerged recently in the digital age of a networked era as an educational pedagogy, in which learning is the

process of building networks of information, contacts, and resources that are applied to real problems (Downes, 2007) (Siemens, 2007).

“Connectivist learning focuses on building and maintaining networked connections that are current and flexible enough to be applied to existing and emergent problems. Connectivism also assumes that information is plentiful and that the learner’s role is not to memorize or even understand everything, but to have the capacity to find and apply knowledge when and where it is needed.” (Anderson and Dron, 2011).

Siemens (2005), who is considered as the father of connectivist learning theory, states the following as 8 principles of connectivism:

- Learning through Learning and knowledge rest in a diversity of opinions.
- Learning is a process of connecting specialized nodes or information sources. Learning may reside in non-human appliances.
- Capacity to know more is more critical than what is currently known.
- Nurturing and maintaining connections is needed to facilitate continual learning.
- Ability to see connections between fields, ideas, and concepts is a core skill.
- Currency (accurate, up-to-date knowledge) is the intent of all connectivist learning activities.
- Decision making is itself a learning process. Choosing what to learn and the meaning of incoming information is seen through the lens of a shifting reality. While there is a right answer now, it may be wrong tomorrow due to alterations in the information climate affecting the decision.

D.Improving the soft skills

According to a Canadian funded study (Lai and Viering, 2012) essential 21st century skills are soft skills such as critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, metacognition, and motivation. Other studies have shown that the demand for skilled workers has declined, and those skilled workers have “moved down the corporate ladder” forcing lower-skilled workers out (Frey and Osborne, 2012).

Frey and Osborne (2013) go on to question whether human labour can even succeed in “the race against technology by means of education” while others estimate up to 140 million job losses worldwide to machines by 2025 (Manyika et al., 2013).

These studies emphasize that, not only should we be teaching the hard skills, but also that students will ultimately succeed when interpersonal, communication and problem-solving skills (soft skills) are also taught.

They highlight that we, as humans, must learn to harness our perception skills and even biases, and to use these to our advantage.

THE ROLE OF EDUCATION SYSTEM

The education system must, in an age of information overload, teach learners how to source relevant information, whereby the sifting and evaluation of these, combined with competent communication of the results of their investigation, will make the foundation of the problem-solving and critical thinking skills that future employees will need.

Learners will need to be shown how to use the theory that they are taught in real-world situations, how to apply the knowledge not just to remember in rote fashion. According to the Foundation for Young Australians (2017), such transferable skills will allow young people to “capitalise on [...] opportunities and navigate the challenges brought by these changes”. Finally, we need a system “to foster a learning culture that encourages creativity that will ultimately drive us on towards a future that we currently cannot even start to comprehend” (Robinson and Aronica, 2015).

TECHNOLOGY IN LEARNING: ADVANTAGE OR DISADVANTAGES?

A review of 45 meta-analyses on the effects of technology on learning, showed that over the past 40 years digital technologies have shown consistent positive benefits on learning but the benefit is only advantageous to learning if the activity is effectively aligned with what is to be learned (Higgins et al., 2012).

It is, therefore, the methodology behind the application of the new technology in the classroom which is ultimately crucial in making teaching more effective.

Methodologies must be selected in which students are empowered and engaged, whereby their agency and motivation are supported, where web-based learning complements, not replaces, face-to face lessons.

According to Mat Docherty (2018), by implementing tried and tested pedagogical methods, all of these goals can be met relatively easily.

So, by implementing constructivist learning approaches to support higher-order thinking skills (Bloom 1956), the learning experience can greatly enhance student performance and enable them to work competitively throughout their future careers. By including mobile-based learning that unused potentials can be drawn upon and by setting incremental task-based goals that students can be encouraged to reach their full potentials.

E. Active Learning

In the teaching-learning process, when the learners are empowered using the appropriate teaching methodology, they feel a sense of confidence, capability, competence, and self-esteem, enabling them to meet life's challenges more effectively.

Therefore, a shift in theory (education theory) to a more student-centred approach using active learning is recommended because this approach has its own role to make the students creative and competent in their study (Mickelson2009).

The teaching-learning process in higher learning institutions should be implemented properly and use the right teaching methodology in relation to the nature and content of the course or subject. In different countries of the world, education is now moving toward new practices in teaching and learning to make the learners creative and competent, which is active learning (student-centred method), because the traditional teaching method (lecture) is not adequately preparing students for the real world of work. (Sewagegn and Boitumelo, 2019). The new practices of teaching that active learning is focused on are creativity and problem solving if it is properly implemented (Litchfield and Dempsey, 2015).

In higher education institutions and other education levels (i.e., primary, and secondary schools), student-centred methodology, specifically active learning is (Brown, 2003; Harris, 2008) to make the learners creative and proficient in their learning.

Active learning is an innovative model for the provision of high-quality, collaborative, engaging, and motivating education (Misseyanni et al., 2018). It engages learners in the process of learning through activities and/or discussion, and it increases learners' higher order thinking as compared to passively listening to a lecturer (Freeman et al., 2014).

The assessment and feedback which are implemented in the active learning classroom have also its own contribution for the empowerment of students.

If the instructors are using authentic assessment methods and provide effective feedback and if the students participated in the assessment and feedback process, it is possible to increase their performance and confidence in their learning.

So, for learning to be active, students do more than listening; they have to read, write, discuss, or be involved in problem-solving activities (Chan et al., 2016).

The fundamental concept of active learning is to advance the learning experience of learners and the teaching experience of instructors. When learners are active in

the classroom, they are engaged in higher-order thinking (analysis, synthesis, evaluation) and in a variety of activities such as reading, discussing, writing, and problem solving (Bonwell and Eison, 1991).

Such classroom activities put the student at the center of the learning process enabling them to improve their critical thinking skills (Chan et al., 2016). Active learning can be realised by any method of teaching which actively involves students in the real learning process of (Prince, 2004).

Studies indicated that active learning has a greater impact on student mastery of higher and lower-level cognitive skills.

It increases students' performance across the different disciplines. On average, students who learn in conventional lecture courses are 1.5 times more likely to fail than students who learn in courses with only active learning (Freeman et al., 2014). Mickelson et al. (2009) also indicated that active learning shows that student involvement in the learning process leads to deep learning.

The active learning approach aims to actively involve students in the learning process. Bonwell and Eison define it as meaningful activities that require students to think about what they are doing (Bonwell and Eison, 1991) and include elements of student activity and engagement in the learning process (Prince, 2004).

It uses Bloom's taxonomy model to progress from lower order thinking tasks to higher level cognitive work (Bloom et al., 1956) by employing taxonomies such as Application and Assimilation (Daggett, 2014).

Some studies indicate that this approach, compared to traditional lectures, is preferred by students (Chickering and Gamson, 1956) and that it is comparable in efficiency yet superior in promoting the development of students' skills in thinking and writing.

Additionally, a meta-study of student performance in undergraduate science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) courses "indicate that average examination scores improved by about 6% in active learning sections, and that students in classes with traditional lecturing were 1.5 times more likely to fail than were students in classes with active learning" (Freeman, 2014).

In the teaching-learning process, instructors in higher institutions are required to use different active learning techniques or strategies to empower students in their learning.

The selection of the techniques depends on the nature and content of the subject they are teaching. The active learning strategies comprise different activities that share the common elements of involving learners in doing things and thinking

about the things they are doing (Bonwell and Eison, 1991). The use of different active learning strategies can significantly improve the teaching-learning process. Different authors, Mocinic (2018) and Oliveira et al. (2006), proposed the following list of active learning methods to be used by instructors in higher learning institutions to make the students creative and proficient in their learning:

1. Collaborative learning
2. Discussion methods: discussion, case study, and brainstorming
3. Role play
4. Problem-based teaching
5. Projects (individual or group)
6. Peer teaching
7. Debates
8. Short demonstrations followed by class discussion, etc.

Integrating the above-listed active learning methods in the instructional process based on the nature and contents of the course will make the student's learning successful and competent. For example, collaborative learning is one of the best methods of active learning which can facilitate learner's critical thinking. Peer interactions during collaborative learning can be helpful for the learner's development of critical thinking (Kim et al., 2013).

Therefore, as Eison (2018) stated, the above-listed active learning strategies increase students:

- Creativity
- Critical thinking
- Discussion or speaking with other students, in a small group, or with the whole class
- Exploring personal attitudes and values
- Providing and receiving feedback

Hence, using different active learning strategies properly inside and outside the classroom is very important specifically for the learners. Eison (2018) suggested that instructors have used a larger proportion of time in helping students to develop their understanding and skills and a lesser proportion of time in transmitting information when they use active learning strategies appropriately. In this strategy (active learning), instructors provide opportunities for learners to apply and demonstrate what they are learning. In addition, they provide opportunities for learners to receive feedback from peers and/or the instructors themselves. In general, the active learning strategies have the following characteristics in promoting students' learning in the classroom (Bonwell and Eison, 1991):

- Students are actively involved in the instructional process more than just listening.
- More emphasis is given on advancing students' skills, and less is given on

- transmitting information.
- Students are involved to develop their higher order thinking skills.
- Students are actively involved in different activities (e.g., writing, discussing, and reading)
- Emphasis is placed on the learners' investigation of their attitudes and values.

PSYCHOLOGICAL THEORIES OF ACTIVE LEARNING

The traditional way (lecture method) of teaching assumes that all students learn the same, and they cognitively process information the same way at the same rate (Litchfield and Dempsey, 2015). Currently, there is a shift in education theory to a more student-centred approach, specifically active learning methodology (Mickelson et al., 2009), because this approach has its own contribution for the learners' better understanding of the issue/lesson presented to them.

Student-centred teaching method emerged from constructivist learning theory (Moate RM, Cox, 2015). This theory was frequently described as a student-centered teaching method because it emphasised on student's active role in the teaching-learning process (Baeten et al., 2013).

According to the constructivism theory, the learner is active rather than passive. Constructivists believe that knowledge is experience-based activities rather than directed by instructors (Roblyer, 2006) and it is not received from the outside environment; rather, the student interprets and processes what is received through the senses to create knowledge.

According to Hativa (2000), the theory of constructivism entails that students learn well only when they are active in the teaching-learning process rather than passive, when they use what they are taught to alter their prior knowledge, and when they construct their own understanding.

In addition, learners develop their own interpretation of the issue presented to create a theory that makes sense to them. They then connect the new knowledge with the personal knowledge structure that they construct.

Hativa (2000) added that in the constructivist learning theory, "meaningful learning takes place only when students actively process the new information, interpret it, and link it to their present knowledge." This theory has an implication for effective classroom teaching in a way that instructors should encourage students' active involvement in the learning process and learners gain valuable information for their creativity and competency.

In active learning, learners construct and formulate knowledge based on previously acquired beliefs and experiences. This theory has a huge contribution in empowering learners using active learning methodology. The process followed to empower learners using active learning requires a dynamic interaction between the learners and their experience. The theoretical foundation of critical thinking and higher-order thinking skills is the constructivist principle of learning through experience (Mickelson et al., 2009). Mickelson et al. (2009) added that, during active learning as to constructivist theory, the students take control of their learning.

F. Learner Empowerment

Empowerment in the academic setting is the approach and practice of supporting learners to become able to shape their learning and study for a sustainable future. So, learner empowerment is giving more autonomy and ownership for the learners in their learning in the instructional process and ultimately produces an intrinsic desire to learn (Schrodt et al., 2008).

Learners become effective in their learning when they are empowered.

Learners should be empowered for every activity in the instructional process. When learners are empowered, they become motivated, work harder, and strive for a better performance (Angela, 1997). For this to happen, the role of the instructors involves guiding and facilitating rather than transmitting information to the learners. This means the instructor must make the teaching-learning process more active to empower the learners.

Furthermore, as to Schrodt et al. (2008), empowered learners should:

- Be more likely to see the meaningfulness of the course content and activities.
- Feel a greater sense of self-efficacy in performing classroom tasks.
- Be more likely to perceive that learning course content can have an impact.

In relation to this, Kirk et al. (2016) found out “that highly empowered students reported better grades, fewer behavioral incidents, increased extracurricular participation and higher educational aspirations than students who were less empowered.” Therefore, empowerment is a process enabling the learner to think, believe, and carry out an activity and criticize his/her own work and make decisions autonomously.

Thomas and Velthos as cited in Frymier and Houser (1996), empowerment consists of four dimensions:

1. Meaningfulness—considers the value of tasks in relation to one's own beliefs, ideas, and standards. If the work is not meaningful, the students will not be motivated to generate high-quality work (Glasser)
2. Competence—means that the person feels qualified and capable to perform the necessary activities to achieve the goal. The feelings of empowerment are decreased when the individual lack self confidence in their skills and feel intimidated by the task or goal.
3. Impact—means that the accomplishment of a task is perceived to make a difference in the scheme of things. The more impact individuals believe they have, the more internal motivation they should feel.
4. Choice—refers to the degree to which persons self-determine their task goals or methods for accomplishing them. This model predicted that great choice contributes to feelings of increased empowerment (Thomas and Velthouse as cited in Frymier and Houser, 1996).

Therefore, empowerment can be seen as a goal aimed at cooperation, based on mutual respect, discovery of perspectives, development of vision, and provision of options for reaching creative solutions (Rood, 1997).

Angela (1997) mentions that learner empowerment is both a means and an end. As a means, it helps learners to attain and enjoy quality learning. In the end, student empowerment is a desirable goal that all teachers should pursue because, when students feel that they can do something and do not feel powerless in their learning environment, the quality of learning begins. Angela (1997) further explains the important components of student empowerment: empowerment through involvement and empowerment through partnership.

Firstly, student empowerment is possible only through active involvement in their learning, and the best ways to empower students are to allow them to be prearranged and to let them make their own decisions. Secondly, student empowerment is not a one-party activity. It requires genuine understanding and acceptance on the part of the school authority, including teachers and the school administration. Without partnership, student empowerment in the school setting is impossible. To this effect, empowering students is essential, and the students should have confidence in the knowledge and skill they possess.

This happens when they are empowered through a range of assessment methods. Secondly, student empowerment is not a one-party activity. It requires genuine understanding and acceptance on the part of the school authority, including teachers and the school administration.

Without partnership, student empowerment in the school setting is impossible.

To this effect, empowering students is essential, and the students should have confidence in the knowledge and skill they possess. This happens when they are empowered through a range of assessment methods. As to Bonwell and Eison

(1991), students' involvement in their learning can be further improved by the instructor's use of different active learning strategies. If the students are actively involved in an active learning process using different strategies, they develop higher order thinking tasks as analysis, synthesis, and evaluation. Therefore, these higher order thinking tasks increase the learner's creativity and make them empowered in their learning.

In the instructional process, the instructors should give chances for learners to cooperate with each other using different strategies. The learner's cooperation in the learning process helps them to share their experiences and improve their learning. Active learning contributes to the active participation of students in class discussions and to improve their understanding of class contents.

In general, if active learning is properly implemented in the instructional process in higher learning institutions and other education levels, it develops student's skills for critical thinking and increases their competency. Critical thinking is one of the skills in which student-centred learning promotes and this learning approach shifts the focus of power, in terms of what is learnt and how it is learnt, from the instructor to the student (Clarke, 2010).

Therefore, the development of higher order thinking skills, critical thinking skills, creativity, and competency is the result of proper implementation of active learning, and this empowers student's learning and study.

G. Community Building

The requirements and needs of learners are common in the training sessions about Predictive Maintenance and in practice, these sessions appear similar challenges and problems that trainers should deal with. Therefore, community building is essential for trainers as fostering a common basis among them and they could share their experiences and challenges. It could support them and allow them to easily share their experiences, discuss about potential challenges and challenges they faced, and to learn from each other's experiences (Cuddy, 2002).

In addition, a community of trainers could enable each other to give and receive advice by expressing their insights based on their experiences. Using an online tool for community building, trainers will have the opportunity to develop further their courses and exploit their expertise. They could use this tool to share relevant information and material as well as to organise online workshops and webinars. Regarding training courses, instructors could enrich them incorporating experience of different trainers and their knowledge (Darling-Hammond et al., 2019). More effective training methodologies could be developed capable of following industry standards and current trends (Hargreaves and Fullan, 2015).

Community building could also motivate trainers and enhance their euphoria feeling as they could share their success stories and celebrate their achievements. Trainers also could maintain their enthusiasm and acknowledge their impact in the sector of predictive maintenance (Pink, 2011). This allows other trainers to evolve their courses establishing a continuous learning environment. Best practices could also be derived from trainers' interaction, and these could be used in updated courses to teach learners how to address key problems and current challenges in the sector of predictive maintenance.

An online tool for community sharing also develops knowledge sharing among a geographically distributed population (Reddi et al., 2021) that work in different cultural environments. Solutions and approaches, that are successfully be implemented in several areas, could be characterized as adaptable and robust. On the other hand, culturally sensitive approaches could be also studied and promote a deeper understanding of how to be globally applied. Trainers could exploit useful insights and through direct communication among them could create global learning networks.

Finally, ongoing collaboration could be achieved among trainers in an online tool or using an asynchronous mode such as forums (Yoon et al., 2020) and other relevant networking actions (i.e., live Q/As, live streaming, webinars, etc.). This online tool could motive trainers to deliver presentations, conduct workshops, or lead discussions, etc. allowing collaboration among trainers to be more dynamic and interactive. Overall, community building not only improves the quality of

trainers' work but also brightens trainers' feelings and boosts their level of euphoria.

H. Assessment and Feedback

Assessment and feedback are the fundamental tools in active learning and a base to the empowerment of learners if they are properly implemented. The assessment methods which are developed in relation to any teaching mode should be aligned with the learning outcomes which will be measured. As to Sluijsmans et al. (1998), assessment as a tool for learning has a great impact on the students' learning and development into reflective practitioners.

Empowering learners in the assessment process encourages or engages them in real life situations. Empowering learners with different assessment methods has a major impact on their results, and learners should be empowered for every activity in the teaching and learning process (Sewagegn, 2016). Angela as cited in (Sewagegn, 2016) noted that learner empowerment is possible only through active involvement in their learning.

In active learning, the two forms of assessment, that is, formative and summative assessments, can be used and play a valuable role. According to Gibson and Shaw (2010), formative assessment can be achieved through the observation of classroom activities such as discussions, student presentations, self and peer assessments, and group work. Formative assessment does not often occur in lecture-based teaching where communication is one way, with little or no input from the learners. Active learning techniques, however, provide more opportunities for formative assessment to take place as the instructor observes student performance and modifies the learning experience accordingly. However, unlike formative assessment, summative assessments are not used to adjust instruction during learning; instead, they are more likely to be used to determine student scores and grades.

Amo and Jareno (2011) noted that self and peer assessments are being increasingly used in higher education to help students learn more efficiently. Assessment can provide feedback to the instructor themselves to improve their instructional process and to check how the learning is going on.

Peer assessment refers to the assessment of students by other students, and it is a mode of assessment associated with the use of active learning (Baker, 2008). It encourages learners to be more responsible in their learning and performance (Pantiwati and Husamah, 2017).

Peer assessments are based on the behaviors of others and use some type of recording tool like a checklist, rating scale, or rubric developed from the learning objectives to guide the assessment (Gibson, 2010).

Self-assessment is an assessment which allows students to assess their own performance (Sewagegn, 2016), and it is a main tool to empower students in the assessment process (Tan, 2004).

It encourages students' self-regulation of their learning and setting of goals for self-improvement. It is most effective when it is embedded into the learning in the unit, and students are provided with the opportunity to learn from their mistakes.

Observation is the main tool to gather ongoing information about students' performance. It can take place in a variety of settings, across many activities, and employ a number of different tools to record information including checklists, anecdotal records, frequency count tables, and rubrics (Gibson and Shaw, 2018). Observational assessments empower measurement of students' behaviour, skills, and abilities in ways not possible via traditional assessment (quiz, test, or exam). When planning to observe students, instructors should consider whom they want to observe, what to observe, and how to evaluate and document what they see.

Presentations and demonstrations are both authentic assessment techniques that are important in active learning classrooms (Gibson and Shaw, 2018). When learners are required to present and demonstrate their work to an audience inside and outside the classroom, there is a chance to get feedback from the audiences and learn from it to improve their performance. These two assessment methods provide students with the opportunity to make the connection between their learning and real-world learning environments.

In relation to each of the above-mentioned assessment methods, there should be appropriate and timely feedback.

Feedback is information provided by an agent (e.g., teacher, peer, self, book, experience) regarding aspects of one's performance or understanding (Hattie and Timperley, 2007).

Sadler (2010) noted that giving detailed feedback for students to their work, with suggestions for improvement, should become a common practice in higher education. Hattie and Timperley (2007) also added that effective feedback is characterized by its clarity, purposefulness, meaningfulness, and compatibility with students' prior knowledge. Therefore, if the assessment is supported by the provision of effective and appropriate feedback in the active learning process, it enhances the students' learning and makes them competent in their field of study.

I. Conclusion

This unit provides an overview covering key competences that would help students/trainees to develop digital skills in online education.

From different studies and literature, it is indicated that empowering learners using active learning in higher education institutions and other education levels has its own contribution to make the learners creative and competent in their learning and study area. Instructors in the classrooms and outside (laboratory and practical sites) of higher learning institutions are advised to use different active learning strategies based on the nature of the course with the support of appropriate assessment methods and feedback.

J. References

- Brown KL. From teacher-centered to learner-centered curriculum: Improving learning in diverse classrooms. *Education*. 2003; 124:49-54
- Mickelson JJ, Kaplan WE, MacNeily AE. Active learning: A resident's reflection on the impact of a student centered curriculum. *Canadian Urological Association Journal*. 2009; 3(5):399-402
- Harris M, Cullen R. Learner-centered leadership: An agenda for action. *Innovation in Higher Education*. 2008; 33:21-28
- Misseyanni A, Papadopoulou P, Marouli C, Lytras MD. Active learning stories in higher education: Lessons learned and good practices in STEM education. In: Misseyanni A, Lytras MD, Papadopoulou P, Marouli C, editors. *Active Learning Strategies in Higher Education: Teaching for Leadership, Innovation, and Creativity*. Emerald Publishing Limited; 2018. pp. 75-105
- Freeman S, Eddy SL, McDonough M, Smith MK, Okoroafor N, Jordt H, et al. Active learning increases student performance in science, engineering, and mathematics. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*. 2014;111(23): 8410-8415
- Chan YF, Sidhu GK, Suthagar N, Lee LF, Yap BW. Relationship of inquiry-based instruction on active learning in higher education. *Pertanika Journal of Social Science and Humanities*. 2016;24(S):55-72
- Hativa N. *Teaching for Effective Learning in Higher Education*. Tel Aviv: Springer; 2000
- Bonwell CC, Eison JA. Active learning: Creating excitement in the classroom. In: ASH#- ERIC Higher Education Report No. 1. Washington, D.C.: The George Washington University; 1991
- Prince M. Does active learning work? A review of research. *Journal of Engineering Education*. 2004;93(3):223-231
- Mickelson JJ, Kaplan WE, MacNeily AE. Active learning: A resident's reflection on the impact of a student centered curriculum. *Canadian Urological Association Journal*. 2009; 3(5):399-402
- Mocinic SN. Teaching strategies in Higher Education [Internet] 2010. Retrieved from: <https://hrcak.srce.hr/file/124604> [Accessed: 2018-06-13]

Oliveira PC, Oliveira CG, de Souza N, Costa N. Teaching strategies to promote active learning in higher education. *Current Developments in Technology-Assisted Education*. 2006; 1:636640

Kim K, Sharma P, Land SM, Furlong KP. Effects of active learning on enhancing student critical thinking in an undergraduate general science course. *Innovative Higher Education*. 2013; 38:223-235. DOI: 10.1007/s10755-012-9236-x
Moate RM, Cox JA. Learner-centered pedagogy: Considerations for application in a didactic course. *The Professional Counselor*. 2015;5(3):379-389. DOI: 10.15241/rmm.5.3.379

Cuddy, C. (2002). Cultivating communities of practice: A guide to managing knowledge. *The Bottom Line*, 15(2).

Reddi, V. J., Plancher, B., Kennedy, S., Moroney, L., Warden, P., Agarwal, A., ... & Tingley, D. (2021). Widening access to applied machine learning with tinyml. arXiv preprint arXiv:2106.04008.

Darling-Hammond, L., Wei, R. C., Andree, A., Richardson, N., & Orphanos, S. (2009). *Professional learning in the learning profession*. Washington, DC: National Staff Development Council, 12.

Hargreaves, A., & Fullan, M. (2015). *Professional capital: Transforming teaching in every school*. Teachers College Press.

Pink, D. H. (2011). *Drive: The surprising truth about what motivates us*. Penguin.

PreMETS

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training

**Module TN2: Reducing the percentage of drop-outs from
online education**
[Booklet]

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the European Union**

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A. Introduction

Dropout can be broadly defined as a student's failure to enroll for a definite number of successive semesters. There are still many different definitions of dropout found in literature, none of which are being accepted as a standard definition. Several related concepts are often employed, some as synonymous – **attrition, withdrawal, non-completion** – and others as antonymous - **retention, persistence, continuance, completion, and success**.

The term **dropout** is usually about students who do not complete a course or program of study, but it can also mean several other things, such as moving on to another course or institution.

The term **persistence** can refer both to course and degree program: “remaining, and engaged, in the course of study to completion of the enrollment period”. A more student-focused definition states persistence as *continuous or intermittent program attendance until students reach their educational goals (usually completion of course or program)*. **Retention** means “continued enrollment in an online program from admission through program completion”. Finally, **withdrawal** can thus be temporary (stop-out) or more or less definitive (dropout).

Dropout rates within higher education (HE) have emerged as a significant concern, given their pivotal role in assessing the quality of higher education and determining government funding allocations. The associated costs, which impact institutions, students, and society at large, are substantial. Universities often face financial setbacks due to attrition, viewing non-completion as a misuse of both time and resources, often funded publicly, allocated to students' education, which fails to contribute to human and social capital. Furthermore, dropout rates can tarnish an institution's reputation, signaling poor or inadequate performance. For students, dropping out entails wasted time, resources, and the potential loss of motivation to pursue further education, creating feelings of frustration and demoralization.

The issue of dropout rates is not exclusive to HE but also affects online courses. Online learning often requires a high level of self-discipline and motivation in order for students to keep up with coursework. The absence of traditional classroom structures, face-to-face interactions with teachers and peers can pose challenges resulting in some learners struggling to remain engaged throughout the course. Additionally, unlike conventional classes that offer group discussions, collaborative projects, networking opportunities which foster social interaction; their virtual counterparts may lack such aspects leading to feelings such as isolation or disconnection contributing towards significant dropout rates. Furthermore, technical difficulties including poor internet connectivity issues impede participants from navigating various platforms effectively thereby reducing participation levels inhibiting effective absorption lessons being taught by the

instructors. Technical problems could lead to discouragements among students further compounding drop out-rates problems .

Successfully balancing online coursework with other responsibilities, such as work obligations and personal commitments, can prove to be a challenging feat for many students. Inadequate time management skills may consequently lead learners to fall behind in their studies ultimately resulting in dropout rates increasing. Furthermore, certain online courses may not offer adequate support services that one would commonly find accessible within traditional educational settings - specifically counseling/tutoring/academic advising thus impacting student retention rates adversely. Students' perception of the value or credibility of pursuing an education through virtual means versus more conventional classroom-based methods is yet another factor that could affect course completion motivation levels greatly- particularly when they do not view course content relatable to their intended academic/career objectives. Lastly but equally important are external factors like health issues, financial difficulties/unexpected life events which will most likely negatively impact dedicating enough necessary resources (time & energy) towards completing assignments/coursework leading up potential rise on dropout statistics amidst participants involved .

The significance of comprehending and tackling dropout rates in HE and online courses cannot be overstated. Dropout rates serve as a crucial indicator of the educational quality provided by institutions. Elevated levels of dropout may indicate shortcomings in course design, teaching methodologies, student support services or institutional policies that necessitate attention to ensure an effective delivery method for engaging education. Dropout rates often influence resource allocation decisions made by funding agencies and educational authorities who may provide lesser financial backing to establishments with high dropout numbers as they are frequently utilized when evaluating program effectiveness whilst allocating resources accordingly.

High dropouts have significant fiscal implications not only on students but also academic organizations; i.e., individuals waste tuition fees while losing out on potential learning benefits from dropping out resulting in diminished revenue returns particularly concerning online classes where students usually pay per class/credit hour. High attrition can impact negatively upon both successful outcomes attained by learners alongside their contentment levels encompassing emotions such as frustration demotivational leaving them less inclined to pursue further knowledge offerings towards accomplishing personal career goals etcetera thus reducing job prospects socio-economic inequality engendered economic growth therefore acting detrimentally across all aspects involved therein. Scrutinizing non-completion rate data yields valuable insights regarding opportunities available at improving training initiatives aid programs providing directed interventions intended enhancing successor retention and success metrics evidenced through promoting equity inclusivity within tertiary academia

thereby ensuring equal access equating student accomplishments regardless origins circumstance preserving equality working environments paving avenues aimed fostering diversity helping amplify active participation among constituents disinclined due disparate societal circumstances benefiting industry achieved more exceptional performances having supervisors/subordinates representing varying perspectives originating divergent backgrounds ultimately essential uplifting overall productivity achievements elevating society's living standard uniformly dispersed amidst its people encouraging widespread prosperity so imperative addressed reaching agreement amongst stakeholders expecting maximal feasible amplification firstly testing prospective resolutions beforehand launching plans advantageous impacting positively significantly affecting how users appreciate interfaces concomitantly exert strength reversing demonstrable drawbacks prevailing current approaches seeing critical potential offering such changes.

The rise of online learning is evident as social and educational technologies mature. In the era of COVID-19, it has emerged as a prevalent method for pursuing academic goals. Despite the convenience and advantages associated with online classes, their completion rates are unexpectedly low. Online courses are gaining traction in higher education, as indicated by research at (Johnson, 2019). This shift is primarily driven by learner demands and budgetary constraints (Limperos, 2015). For example, the prevalence of online courses in the United States has notably risen over the past two decades. By Fall 2016, the total number of distance learners reached 6,359,121 (Seaman, 2018). Online courses are recognized for their effectiveness, comparable to traditional face-to-face classes (Kumar, 2019). Students opt for online enrollment to achieve their personal and professional objectives. The widespread popularity of online course enrollment can be attributed to the appealing features of greater flexibility and unrestricted digital access to extensive information (Zimmerman, 2012). Access to online courses enables learners to organize their classes around family and work commitments, a flexibility that may not be feasible through other means.

Additionally, the global impact of the COVID-19 pandemic has significantly affected students, instructors, and educational institutions worldwide (Shaikh, 2022). In response to social distancing measures, instructors transitioned their courses to online platforms, and students continued their studies from home (Toquero, 2020). During this period, online learning emerged as the predominant method for continuing academic activities globally, leading experts to consider it a viable alternative to traditional face-to-face education. Higher education institutions swiftly embraced online education, integrating media and technology into their delivery methods (Rahmat, 2022). Recognizing the necessity to adapt and enhance their capabilities, they aimed to achieve the desired educational outcomes (Maqsood et al., 2021).

Despite the substantial expansion, the persistence rates for online courses are notably low in comparison to traditional in-person offerings (Xavier, 2020). Online learners often face challenges in completing their courses and attrition, or dropout, emerges as a prominent issue in numerous colleges (Friðriksdóttir, 2018). This poses a significant challenge for administrators and instructors in the field of online education. The problem remains complex and demanding. Only approximately 15% of students from Open Universities graduate with degrees or qualifications, underscoring the limited persistence rate among those taking online courses (Mishra, 2017). Experiences of online dropout lead to frustration and undermine learners' confidence, deterring future enrollments. This implies inadequacy, questionable quality, and financial losses for institutions (Gomez, 2013).

Recognizing the importance of reducing dropout rates among online learners for the benefit of students, educational institutions, and businesses, numerous researchers have highlighted this necessity over time (Murphy, 2017). The increased reliance on technology in the learning process, accentuated by the pandemic, has underscored the critical nature of this aspect of online learning. Consequently, there is a growing need for further exploration into the quality of online learning from a fresh and enhanced perspective.

The choice to discontinue participation in a course is not solely tied to knowledge but can often be attributed to a lack of persistence. Persistence in online courses is acknowledged as a multifaceted phenomenon shaped by various factors (Choi, 2018). No single factor can reliably predict student attrition from online courses (Gaytan, 2015). It is crucial to conduct extensive studies on persistence to gain a deeper understanding of the factors influencing the completion of online courses or the decision of online learners to withdraw (Choi, 2018).

Here, we will analyze what factors are positively or negatively linked with persistence in post-secondary online education settings. When we say persistence, in this analysis we mean on intention to persist in the currently enrolled online course, which is considered as the most referenced indicator of persistence (Roland, 2018).

According to (Shaikh, 2022), we can categorize factors related to learner dropout in online learning programs into several categories:

- Persistence factors related to online learners
- Persistence factors related to online courses and course providers
- Persistence factors related to online instructors

Below will be described briefly in each of these categories with all the factors related to the category itself.

B. Persistence factors related to online learners

Here, we will focus exclusively on factors associated with online learners. Examining these factors offers a glimpse into the common understanding among scholars, their divergent perspectives, and occasionally, discrepancies in empirical findings.

1. Demographic attributes:

- Age: Many researches focus on how age and gender influence persistence or dropout decisions in online courses. Age-related findings vary, with some studies suggesting older students are more prone to dropout, while others argue for better performance and persistence in older students.
- Gender: Gender differences show mixed correlations with retention, with some studies suggesting a likelihood of male students dropping out, and older females being influenced by domestic responsibilities.

2. Academic experience:

- Distance/online learning experience: Positive impacts on awareness and confidence are associated with experience in distance or online learning.
- Academic standing: Higher academic standing correlates with increased persistence, while the academic year's significance in predicting retention varies.
- Field experiences: Previous experiences in programming or data handling may enhance persistence, but findings are inconsistent.
- Grades: GPA and grades are considered influential, but findings on their significance in predicting retention vary.

3. Relevant technical and management skills:

- Technological skills: Proficiency, confidence, college readiness, and clear goals impact course completion. Lack of technical skills serves as a dropout indicator.
- Time management: Effective time management positively influences persistence, while challenges in time management are associated with early dropouts.
- Workload management: Active organization and planning increase persistence, while an unexpected change in workload can lead to dropout.

4. Behavioral and psychological attributes:

- Locus of control: Internal locus of control is linked to persistence, where individuals believe outcomes depend on their decisions and efforts.
- Motivation: Motivation, intrinsic motivation, and self-determination positively influence persistence.

- Self-efficacy: Higher self-efficacy is associated with increased resilience and course completion.
- Self-regulation: Successfully self-regulating learners exhibit metacognitive, motivational, and behavioral processes, impacting persistence.
- Resilience: Effectively handling challenges distinguishes persistent students from dropouts.
- Active participation: Actively engaging with course content correlates with increased persistence.
- Satisfaction: Satisfaction with faculty and courses is linked to course completion.
- Attitudes: Learners' attitudes toward the course and interactions influence completion.

5. Personal variables:

- Multiple responsibilities: Family and employment responsibilities, especially for part-time learners, pose challenges to persistence.
- Financial issues: Financial concerns may lead to dropout, with conflicting findings regarding the impact of loans/financial assistance.
- Family and friends support: Supportive family and home environments positively impact persistence.
- Health issues: Disability and health challenges may contribute to the withdrawal of online learners.

C. Persistence factors related to online courses and course providers

Here we will outline factors associated with the design of online courses and the support provided by institutions. It encompasses aspects such as the structure of the course or program, the complexity of the curriculum, the manner in which learners engage with the content, and the perceived importance of support services.

1. Course design:

Definition and structure of courses, interactivity, and fulfillment of learner needs are predictors of persistence and dropout.

- Course organization: Poor course organization and design affect learner satisfaction and contribute to dropout decisions.
- Course content: Well-structured courses with rigorous, relevant content and clear instructions facilitate persistence. Boring and unrelated course elements promote dropout decisions.

- Course relevancy: Course relevancy to learning styles and career objectives shapes decisions to persist or withdraw
- Team-building activities: Courses promoting team-building activities foster increased interaction, contributing to increased retention.
- Scaffolding: Scaffolding elements in course design enhance motivation and related learning, supporting persistence.

2. Institutional support:

Institutional support services are crucial for completion, though learners may not perceive them equally. Absence negatively impacts academic success.

- Student support services: These services can help learners to overcome barriers that can result in dropout decisions for regular students, but also for online students.
- Tutorial services: Tutorial services, both face-to-face and online, significantly improve persistence.
- Support infrastructure: Institutional support infrastructure factors influence distance learners' dropout decisions.
- Orientation: Course orientation increases the chances of online learners persisting.
- Support for technology: Lack of technology support and access issues may impact persistence, with learners' perception of being unsupported being a significant concern.
- Understanding learners' needs: Institutional understanding of online learners' needs and circumstances is essential to prevent dropout.

3. Curriculum intricacy:

Online course category and complexity level influence learners' persistence.

- Course category and complexity level: The course category and its complexity level are associated with retention in online settings.
- Curriculum difficulty: Online learners may drop out if the curriculum is either too easy or too difficult.

D. Persistence factors related to online instructors

Encouraging faculties to enhance the quality of online courses is very important (Parker, 2013). The significance of online course facilitators cannot be overstated, as they play a vital role in maintaining learners' interest, sustaining motivation, and ensuring the successful completion of online courses and programs.

1. Role of Instructors:

The evolving role of instructors in online settings is seen as a significant challenge, which might affect learners' engagement and persistence.

- Ways of teaching: The adoption of a learner-centered approach has reshaped the role of instructors, turning them into guides tasked with aligning content delivery according to the learners' needs.
- Instructor's interest in online classes: Instructors' disinterest in teaching online may contribute to student dissatisfaction and potential dropouts.
- Time invested by instructors: The additional time required for preparing and teaching online classes is linked to student retention up to a certain extent, suggesting that time constraints may impact learners' persistence.

2. Faculty interactions:

Lack of faculty interaction is identified as a retention factor, and its absence can contribute to dissatisfaction and dropout decisions.

- Learner's interaction with faculty: The significant link between online learners' interaction with faculty and dropout rates suggests that poor interaction might contribute to students leaving the course.
- Effective communication: Effective communication from course facilitators is essential for learner persistence, implying that poor communication may be a factor in dropout decisions.

3. Feedback:

Positive feedback from faculty is associated with better outcomes for online learners, implying that the absence or lack of feedback could contribute to dropout rates.

- Feedback pattern: The feedback provided by faculty shapes students' perception of course content, and the pattern of feedback directly impacts their ability to successfully complete an online course.
- Encouraging and timely feedback: Students' persistence is significantly influenced by positive, timely, valuable, and encouraging feedback, along with faculty readiness to address learner needs.
- Sufficient and personalized feedback: Retention is negatively impacted by insufficient or inadequate feedback on learning. Feedback needs to be both consistent and personalized for each student.

3. Facilitation of social connectedness:

The sense of social connectedness is crucial, as feelings of isolation may negatively impact the overall learning experience and contribute to dropout decisions.

- Sense of belonging: Challenges in creating a sense of belonging in online learning environments may result in isolation and a sense of community deprivation, potentially influencing dropout rates.
- Shared purpose and norms: Assisting online learners in developing shared purpose and norms is crucial to reducing dropout rates, as learners without a common purpose may be more prone to dropout.
- Fostering online communities: The role of online instructors in promoting online communities is highlighted as important for increasing learners' chances of persistence.

4. Learning facilitation:

Online instructors play a key role in facilitating the learning process, suggesting that effective facilitation may positively impact learner persistence.

- Guidance and presence: Instructors' presence in nurturing the knowledge attainment process is valued by online learners, indicating that insufficient guidance may influence dropout decisions.
- Assignments: The type of assignments, especially a preference against group assignments, may impact learners' decisions to continue with the course and potentially contribute to dropout rates.

E. Actions to reduce dropout rates in online courses

In order to reduce dropout rates in online courses it is necessary to implement different proactive measures. Some of these measures are related to course organization and planning student activities, while others are relating to setting different systems as well as control and quality measures on the level of the institution.

In this section concrete actions that can be taken to reduce dropout rates in online courses are given. These actions are not all encompassing, however, they give proactive steps for higher education institutions on how to reduce dropout rates in online courses through:

- Course and lesson planning
 - Highlighting prerequisites
 - Structuring the course into manageable sections
 - Providing clear expectations
 - Including time estimates for course content and activities
 - Planning active learning strategies
- Plan and use intervention mechanisms

- Using student orientation
- Tracking student progress and providing regular feedback
- Providing proactive academic advisory
- Implementing continuous quality assurance
- Consider student comments

Ensuring internal quality assurance within the institution.

Highlighted actions can help in setting up a supportive learning environment, and hence, set the tone with course expectations that are of vital importance in helping students with maintaining the motivation and student engagement with the goal to reduce the dropout rates in online classes.

F. Course and lesson planning

Even though there are many factors which can influence student dropout from online courses, out of which most are learner factors, lesson design and careful planning of course content, deadlines, assignments and assessments can have a significant impact on students' retention and dropouts. High course workload along with student unrealistic expectations can impact student motivation, performance and time availability. Keeping in mind that the course has to fulfill the curriculum's learning outcomes and objectives, each lesson should be carefully planned keeping in mind course workload, difficulty level, complexity and extensiveness of course content and assignments, etc. Careful planning is especially important in the large class where it is very difficult for instructors to facilitate flexible assignments, deadlines and personalized feedback. Hence, the instructor's support, feedback and appropriate continuous communication to students will help students overcome even more complex tasks. In an online classroom setting it becomes of vital importance to adequately plan each lesson, along with its activities, content, assignments and test, keeping in mind the level of support students will receive during their work.

Highlighting prerequisites

Course instructors should set transparent expectations from the very beginning of the course by defining the course prerequisites in the course syllabus. These highlights should include information not only about the potential prerequisite course, but also any prerequisite skills and knowledge that are required for students to be able to participate in the course. Whenever possible, and it is in line with course objectives, it is recommended to provide students with additional literature or external sources that will help students bridge existing knowledge and skills gaps with course requirements. This will increase students' chances to actively progress and succeed in the course, and moreover, it is setting up a supportive learning environment that allows students to be proactive in acquiring

their prerequisite knowledge. By clearly defining course prerequisites, the course instructor is promoting transparency and accountability as students can make informed decisions about the course enrollment.

Structuring the course into manageable sections

Providing students with learning roadmaps can provide additional support and easy navigation through the course content and activities. This presumes for the course instructor to plan the course into manageable sections for students. Structuring the course in sections allows students to focus on the specific topic or learning objectives without feeling overwhelmed with too much content at once. At the same time, this approach can help students to be more effective in their course time management by allocating their time to different sections of the course, when needed. Another benefit about structuring the course into smaller sections is to provide the course structure that will allow the course instructor to effectively track student progress. In this way, the course instructor can implement any intervention methods for a specific part of the course, which is more manageable to monitor specific learning outcomes for both the instructor and students. Furthermore, by sensing their own accomplishments students will remain motivated to learn and engage in the course activities, which will in return enhance their learning experience in the online course.

Providing clear expectations

Providing clear instructions to students allows students to understand what is expected of them in the course and allows them to meet their academic requirements. Without clear instructions on what expectations are in the course, students may feel overwhelmed which could lead to frustrations and motivation loss. In order to prevent any misunderstanding, instructors should provide detailed instructions, requirements and grading specifications for all assignments. This instruction can be in written format, but depending on the course and assignment, can be aided with additional video tutorials (i.e. how to use learning environments, how to complete and upload assignments, etc.). Providing clear instructions in the course includes defining transparent instructions and expectations on the course assignments, assessments, assignments and assessments deadlines, and grading policy. Structuring the expectations framework in this way will ensure that students are aware of how and when their work will be evaluated. This provides a step towards an effective communication between the instructor and students, leaving out ambiguities as much as possible.

Including time estimates for course content and activities

Just like in planning other parts of the lesson and including transparency in the course expectations, another mechanism that can help students to better organize their time management in the course is to help students realize what is the needed time commitment. Due to this reason, providing time estimates for covering sections of course content, lessons and time needed to complete assignments, assessments, and other course activities can help students to allocate sufficient time throughout the course. Providing time estimates needed for students to complete course requirements will help students to bridge the gap between what is actually expected in the course and their perception about the requirements of online courses. Specifying times when students are expected to be online will allow them to plan their time availability and commitment to the class. This can reduce the chance of students dropping out due to scheduling conflicts. Including time estimates of the course activities serves to contribute to instructors transparency in teaching, expectations and grading policy in the course, which represents a proactive measure to set clear expectations, promote time management skills, and ultimately reduce dropout rates in online courses.

Planning active learning strategies

Incorporating active learning methodologies in course activities can contribute to fostering student engagement, motivation, and retention. In an online environment dynamic and interactive experience can be created by incorporating methodologies such as project-based learning, problem-based learning, and collaborative learning. These active learning methodologies involve students to work on assignments that are relevant to their interests and goals. By engaging them actively to find solutions to their assigned topics and tasks, students take ownership of their learning, develop critical thinking skills, and apply theoretical knowledge to practical scenarios. Active learning approaches not only enhance student motivation and interest but also promotes a sense of accomplishment and self-efficacy. Additionally, collaborative learning emphasizes peer interaction and teamwork, allowing students to learn from each other, share perspectives, and collectively solve problems. Through collaborative activities such as group discussions, peer reviews, and team projects, students develop communication skills, build relationships, and feel connected to their peers and instructors, which can positively impact their motivation and engagement in the course.

Active learning methodologies are not always easy to implement, but the instructor should plan different methodologies based on the course difficulty level and their teaching context. Aforementioned active learning methodologies are not all encompassing, and different approaches can be taken.

G. Plan and use intervention mechanisms

Organize student orientation for the course

Organizing an initial session as a student orientation session for the course can help in setting student expectation and engagement level as early as the first day of the class. In order to make the most out of the student orientation instructor can create a welcome message to the course that will set up the supporting learning environment tone in the course. This welcome message can include various facts about the course such as explanations for course expectations, explanation about the course grading policy, explanation about the academic and ethical standards and expected behavioral norms, share detailed syllabus with assignment due dates, course goals, required materials, technological requirements, etc. (welcome message, syllabus, due dates course goals. A well organized and informative orientation session will set the tone for the support in student learning journey and their understanding of importance of their course participation and engagement levels.

Tracking student progress and providing regular feedback

One of the key steps in achieving an effective and successful educational process in online courses is understanding students' progress during their learning. Tracking student progress involves monitoring their engagement, performance, and completion of course activities over time. One way to assess student progress during learning is by using learning analytics on student data. Universities are increasingly using digital tools in their daily activities, thereby collecting a large amount of data. Understanding how students are progressing in the course and actively acting on their lack of engagement allows instructors to support individual learning, improve course and course assignment implementation, and overall teaching quality. Analyzing student progress data can allow instructors to identify students who are at risk of dropping out of the course and to intervene by providing additional support and guidance.

Using learning analytics in tracking all class activities online, including tasks and assignments of active learning methodologies in online learning can be challenging due to some practical reasons of its implementation, as well as ethical challenges. When thinking about active learning methodologies, it usually does not mean that all student activities will be online. However, for any approach to learning analytics, it is necessary to have student data. Therefore, incorporating activities that can be tracked for student progress, especially when considering specific metrics, can be quite challenging. When planning the class, not only should activities be planned along with learning outcomes, knowledge assessments, and other parts of the class, but also consider how to track student progress and which metrics will be used. The benefits of using active learning

methods are twofold: (i) students will be more engaged and active in their learning, and (ii) students will produce a large amount of data during their learning. Since this data will be stored in learning management tools, access to data is more or less straightforward. However, when external tools are used, it should be considered how to track their progress and activity levels using them as well.

Timely and constructive instructor's feedback on course assignments and course activities will help guide students in their learning journey and can help to clarify the expectations. Timely feedback can guide students in their understanding of their strengths but also necessary areas needing improvement. Whenever possible, personalized feedback should be tailored to individual student needs, which will further strengthen the collaborative learning environment for each student demonstrating the instructor's investment in student success and will encourage further active participation.

Providing proactive academic advisory

To reduce dropout rates in online courses, implementing a comprehensive support system is important in ensuring students' success. Providing academic advisory can be course based, institution based, or both. On the institution level, academic advisory support can include offering guidance and support to students before they encounter academic challenges, helping them make informed decisions about their course selections and ensuring they are academically prepared for the coursework. By identifying potential prerequisites and providing academic advisory support, institutions can assist students in enrolling in appropriate classes, increasing their likelihood of success.

On the other hand, when tailoring advisory specifically to the specific online course, course tutors and instructor support can be utilized. Course tutors can provide personalized support to students who may be struggling or facing obstacles in their learning. In addition to course tutors, it is always recommended that students have open communication channels with course instructors. Teachers can use several channels that students can use to receive feedback from setting up the FAQ document covering most frequent issues students may have, offering email and instant message (chat) support to encouraging students to talk to each other through group conversation (i.e. setting up break out rooms in Discord).

H. Implementing continuous quality assurance

Instructors can receive valuable feedback on the course quality and conducted activities when asking students directly. Actively soliciting student opinion can help course instructors to identify different factors contributing to student positive or negative learning experience, which also includes identifying level of motivation and factors that influence student motivation. Understanding these factors can allow instructors to take proactive measures to address these factors and potential issues in student learning, which can help mitigate barriers to student success and improve overall course satisfaction. Actively listening and reacting on student comments contributes to student-centered learning and fosters course improvements for future student cohorts. Even though it is recommended that each instructor takes into consideration improvements of the course with each student group based on the comments of the previous group of students, or improving the course during the semester considering student comments as it is happening, it is very important to set up an institutional mechanisms that will allow continuous quality assurance and improvements of different online courses.

Ensuring internal quality assurance within institution

Establishing internal quality assurance mechanisms in higher education institutions is crucial for reducing dropout rates in online courses. By implementing a robust quality assurance framework, institutions can ensure that online courses meet high standards. Quality assurance framework for institution should considering the following:

- Development of quality standards for course design, content, and delivery.
- Development of guidelines that will allow continuous evaluation and adaptation of evolving educational needs of students and emerging technologies by involving stakeholders, such as instructors, learners, and administrators, in the review and evaluation process.
- Existence of a guidance, counseling and psychological support office for students.
- Direct pedagogical supervision practices that allow teachers to have a sustained and systematic reflection on how the stated practices are effectively operationalized and also on their effectiveness in meeting the goal of preventing student demotivation and the consequent failure and dropout.
- Ensuring that course content is accessible to all learners, regardless of their abilities or technological limitations.
- Collecting and analyzing data that will be used to define necessary improvements in course design, content, delivery, student engagement and motivation. Based on the data analysis, decisions on the necessary improvements should be made in order to enhance the learning experience in online courses.

I. Conclusion

In this analysis, according to literature, we named essential factors influencing persistence, both positively and negatively and categorized the identified factors into three broad groups, each containing sub-groups. The first group encompasses factors related to online learners, such as demographic properties, past educational experiences, management and technological skills, behavioral and psychological attributes, and personal variables like responsibilities, support, health, and finances. This group predominantly discusses factors associated with online learners. The second group includes factors related to online course design and structure, support from course providers, and the complexity level of online courses. The third group addresses factors related to online course instructors, focusing on their role in online settings, facilitation of online learning, promotion of various interactions, and their interest in the online mode of delivery.

Researchers have observed that the interaction between these factors determines whether online learners persist or drop out. Consequently, the categorization provided in this review serves as a valuable resource for fellow researchers, enabling them to explore relationships within and between categories while studying the combined impact of various factors on persistence or dropout decisions. The findings will guide future research in critically examining these relationships and proposing empirically validated improvements. Additionally, researchers can validate the results in diverse scenarios and contexts related to online learning. Course instructors and providers can use this information to address specific problem areas and enhance the persistence of online courses and programs.

Proactive measures outlined in the text provide a comprehensive approach to addressing dropout rates in online courses. By focusing on course organization, intervention mechanisms, and continuous quality assurance, higher education institutions can enhance the learning experience and mitigate dropout rates.

These measures underscore the importance of setting clear expectations, providing support services, and implementing effective feedback mechanisms to promote student engagement and success. Emphasizing continuous improvement and adherence to quality standards ensures that online courses meet evolving educational needs and contribute to student retention and satisfaction.

J. References

Johnson, N., Bates, T., Donovan, T., and Seaman, J. (2019). Tracking Online Education in Canadian Universities and Colleges: National Survey of Online and Digital Learning 2019 National Report.

<https://eduq.info/xmlui/bitstream/handle/11515/37850/johnson-tracking-online-education-canadian-universities-colleges-cdlra-2019.pdf;sequence=5>

Limperos, A. M., Buckner, M. M., Kaufmann, R., and Frisby, B. N. (2015). Online teaching and technological affordances: an experimental investigation into the impact of modality and clarity on perceived and actual learning. *Comput. Educ.* 83, 1–9.

[doi: 10.1016/j.compedu.2014.12.015](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2014.12.015)

Seaman, J. E., Allen, I. E., and Seaman, J. (2018). Grade Increase: Tracking Distance Education in the United States. Babson Survey Research Group.

<https://bayviewanalytics.com/reports/gradeincrease.pdf>

Kumar, P., Kumar, A., Palvia, S., and Verma, S. (2019). Online business education research: systematic analysis and a conceptual model. *Int. J. Manag. Educ.* 17, 26–35.

[doi: 10.1016/j.ijme.2018.11.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2018.11.002)

Zimmerman, T. D. (2012). Exploring learner to content interaction as a success factor in online courses. *Int. Rev. Res. Open Dist. Learn.* 13, 152–165.

[doi: 10.19173/irrodl.v13i4.1302](https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v13i4.1302)

Shaikh UU and Asif Z (2022) Persistence and Dropout in Higher Online Education: Review and Categorization of Factors. *Front. Psychol.* 13:902070.

[doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2022.902070](https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.902070)

Toquero, C. M. (2020). Challenges and opportunities for higher education amid the COVID-19 pandemic: the Philippine context. *Pedagogical Res.* 5:7947.

[doi: 10.29333/pr/7947](https://doi.org/10.29333/pr/7947)

Rahmat, T. E., Raza, S., Zahid, H., Abbas, J., Sobri, F. A. M., and Sidiki, S. N. (2022). Nexus between integrating technology readiness 2.0 index and students' e-library services adoption amid the COVID-19 challenges: implications based on the theory of planned behavior. *J. Educ. Health Promot.* 11:50.

[doi: 10.4103/jehp.jehp_508_21](https://doi.org/10.4103/jehp.jehp_508_21)

Xavier, M., and Meneses, J. (2020). Dropout in Online Higher Education: A Scoping Review From 2014 to 2018. Barcelona: ELearn Center, Universitat Oberta de Catalunya.

Friðriksdóttir, K. (2018). The impact of different modalities on student retention and overall engagement patterns in open online courses. *Comput. Assist. Lang. Learn.* 31, 53–71.

[doi: 10.1080/09588221.2017.1381129](https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2017.1381129)

Mishra, S. (2017). Open Universities in the Commonwealth: At a Glance.

<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/2786> (Accessed August 21, 2021).

Gomez, D. (2013). Leadership behavior and its impact on student success and retention in online graduate education. *Acad. Educ. Leadersh. J.* 17, 13–37.

Murphy, C. A., and Stewart, J. C. (2017). On-campus students taking online courses: factors associated with unsuccessful course completion. *Internet High. Educ.* 34, 1–9.

[doi: 10.1016/j.iheduc.2017.03.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2017.03.001)

Choi, H. J., and Park, J.-H. (2018). Testing a path-analytic model of adult dropout in online degree programs. *Comput. Educ.* 116, 130–138.

[doi: 10.1016/j.compedu.2017.09.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2017.09.005)

Gaytan, J. (2015). Comparing faculty and student perceptions regarding factors that affect student retention in online education. *Am. J. Dist. Educ.* 29, 56–66.

[doi: 10.1080/08923647.2015.994365](https://doi.org/10.1080/08923647.2015.994365)

Roland, N., Frenay, M., and Boudrenghien, G. (2018). Understanding academic persistence through the theory of planned behavior: normative factors under investigation. *J. Coll. Stud. Retent. Res. Theory Pract.* 20, 215–235. [doi: 10.1177/1521025116656632](https://doi.org/10.1177/1521025116656632)

Parker, J., Maor, D., and Herrington, J. (2013). “Authentic online learning: aligning learner needs, pedagogy and technology,” in *Issues in Educational Research*, Vol. 23, 227.

<https://search.informit.org/doi/10.3316/ielapa.354613892620670>

PreMETS

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training.

Module TN3: Inclusion of groups at risk and personalized education
[Booklet]

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A. Introduction

In the rapidly evolving landscape of predictive maintenance, where technological advancements and industry demands continue to shape the future, the paradigm of education undergoes a transformation. The introduction of inclusive and personalized education strategies emerges as a cornerstone, heralding a new era in the realm of predictive maintenance. This introduction delves into the significance and impact of these strategies, particularly in the context of online deliveries in higher and vocational education and their broader implications. As industries embrace the digital age, the need for a skilled and adaptive workforce in predictive maintenance becomes increasingly apparent. In this context, the importance of fostering inclusion cannot be overstated. The traditional one-size-fits-all approach to education proves inadequate in addressing the diverse learning needs within the predictive maintenance domain. Inclusive education, by recognizing and accommodating a spectrum of learning styles and preferences, sets the stage for a collaborative learning environment that values contributions from individuals with varied perspectives. Moreover, the call for personalized education resonates powerfully in the predictive maintenance sector. Tailoring educational content to individual needs, adapting to varied skill levels, and encouraging self-paced learning become imperatives. Real-world relevance is paramount, requiring curriculum and learning experiences that directly align with the practical demands and evolving challenges of predictive maintenance in industries at large.

Background

The field of predictive maintenance, a crucial pillar in ensuring the operational efficiency and longevity of industrial assets, stands at the intersection of technology, innovation, and real-world applications. As industries transition towards Industry 4.0, embracing cutting-edge technologies and methodologies, the demand for a skilled and adaptive workforce becomes increasingly pronounced. In response to these evolving industry needs, the paradigm of education within predictive maintenance undergoes a profound transformation, necessitating a comprehensive exploration of inclusive and personalized education strategies.

Diversity, Equity & Inclusion. Learning how to get it right | Asif Sadiq | TEDxCroydon

Evolution of Predictive Maintenance

Traditionally, maintenance practices operated on reactive models, addressing issues as they arose. However, the advent of predictive maintenance brought forth a paradigm shift. Leveraging advanced technologies such as sensors, data analytics, and machine learning, predictive maintenance allows for the proactive identification of potential failures, thereby minimizing downtime and optimizing operational efficiency. This shift, coupled with the dynamic nature of Industry 4.0, underscores the importance of aligning educational approaches with the ever-evolving demands of the predictive maintenance landscape.

Changing Dynamics in Education

As industries adapt to the digital age, the traditional modes of education face challenges in meeting the diverse and dynamic learning needs of individuals aspiring to join the predictive maintenance workforce. Recognizing the limitations of standardized, one-size-fits-all educational models, the spotlight turns towards inclusive and personalized education strategies. In this context, the background section delves into the journey of educational transformation, emphasizing the need for a tailored approach that accommodates a spectrum of learning styles and preferences.

Rise of Online Deliveries

The rise of online deliveries in higher and vocational education emerges as a pivotal aspect of this educational evolution. The digital shift, accelerated by global events and technological advancements, provides unprecedented opportunities for accessible and flexible learning experiences. Online deliveries, when strategically aligned with inclusive and personalized education, become the conduits through which individuals can access tailored content, adapt to their unique learning paces, and engage in collaborative environments that reflect the real-world challenges of predictive maintenance.

Necessity for Inclusive and Personalized Education

The predictive maintenance industry, by its nature, involves interdisciplinary skills and a deep understanding of technological nuances. Inclusivity in education becomes imperative to ensure that individuals from diverse backgrounds, irrespective of abilities or socioeconomic status, have equal access and opportunities within this sector. Simultaneously, personalized education becomes vital to cater to the varying proficiency levels, learning speeds, and preferences of individuals pursuing education in predictive maintenance.

Significance of Inclusion and Personalized Education in Predictive Maintenance

Fostering Diversity and Inclusion

Addressing Diverse Learning Needs

The prioritization of inclusion and personalized education in predictive maintenance ensured that the educational landscape mirrored the diverse and dynamic nature of the field. Recognizing and accommodating a spectrum of learning styles and preferences within the predictive maintenance domain.

Enhancing Access for All

Breaking down barriers to education by ensuring inclusivity for individuals from diverse backgrounds, irrespective of their abilities, socioeconomic status, or prior educational experiences.

Creating a Collaborative Learning Environment

Promoting an inclusive culture that valued contributions from individuals with varied perspectives, fostering a rich learning environment.

Tailoring Education to Individual Needs

Adapting to Varied Skill Levels

Tailoring educational content and approaches to cater to learners at different proficiency levels in predictive maintenance concepts.

Encouraging Self-Paced Learning

Empowering learners to progress at their own pace, fostering a sense of autonomy and personalized growth.

Real-world Relevance

Designing curriculum and learning experiences that directly aligned with the practical demands and evolving challenges of predictive maintenance in industries.

Addressing Challenges in Traditional Approaches

Overcoming One-Size-Fits-All Models

Moving beyond traditional, standardized educational models to accommodate the diverse needs and requirements of learners.

Mitigating Exclusionary Practices

Identifying and rectifying exclusionary practices that hindered certain groups from fully participating in and benefiting from predictive maintenance education.

Preparing for Industry 4.0

Aligning with Technological Advancements

Recognizing the importance of adaptive education to align with the latest technologies and methodologies in predictive maintenance.

Nurturing Agile and Adaptable Professionals

Developing a workforce that was not only well-versed in predictive maintenance but also agile and adaptable to the ever-evolving landscape of Industry 4.0.

B. Challenges in Traditional Education

Limitations and Barriers

Traditional educational models, rooted in conventional classroom settings and standardized approaches, face inherent limitations and barriers when applied to the dynamic domain of predictive maintenance. These challenges hinder the effective preparation of individuals for the evolving demands of Industry 4.0.

Lack of Flexibility

Issue: Traditional education often follows rigid schedules and structures, limiting the flexibility required to adapt to the varying learning paces and preferences of individuals.

Impact: This lack of flexibility can lead to disengagement and frustration among learners, hindering their ability to grasp the complexities of predictive maintenance.

Inadequate Integration of Technology

Issue: Many traditional educational institutions struggle to seamlessly integrate technology into their curricula, resulting in a gap between theoretical knowledge and practical, real-world applications.

Impact: Without exposure to the latest technological advancements, learners may graduate without the essential skills needed for predictive maintenance roles.

Limited Accessibility

Issue: Traditional education often relies on physical attendance, limiting accessibility for individuals with geographical constraints, work commitments, or physical disabilities.

Impact: This limitation excludes diverse talents from entering the predictive maintenance field, contributing to a potential skills gap.

Gaps in Catering to Diverse Learning Needs

Predictive maintenance demands a workforce with diverse skills and a deep understanding of complex technologies. Traditional education, however, struggles to address the unique learning needs of individuals, resulting in significant gaps.

One-Size-Fits-All Approach

Issue: Traditional educational models tend to adopt a uniform approach, assuming that all learners have similar learning styles and preferences.

Impact: This approach neglects the diverse needs of individuals, hindering the development of a workforce with varied skills and perspectives.

Limited Adaptability to Learning Styles

Issue: The traditional classroom setting may not adequately accommodate different learning styles, such as visual, auditory, or kinaesthetic.

Impact: Learners with alternative learning styles may struggle to engage with the material, leading to suboptimal understanding and retention.

Insufficient Practical Application

Issue: Traditional education often focuses on theoretical knowledge, neglecting practical application and hands-on experiences crucial for predictive maintenance roles.

Impact: Graduates may face challenges when transitioning to real-world scenarios, as the gap between theory and practical skills remains unaddressed.

C. Groups at Risk in Educational Settings

Identifying Vulnerable Student Groups

In the pursuit of inclusive and personalized education, it is essential to recognize and address the challenges faced by vulnerable student groups in the context of predictive maintenance education. Identifying these groups is crucial for implementing targeted strategies to ensure equal access and opportunities for all.

Vulnerability: Finding Your Voice | Delin Liu | TEDxYouth@StMarksSchool

Students with Disabilities

Identification: Individuals with disabilities, including physical, sensory, cognitive, or learning impairments, constitute a significant group facing unique challenges.

Challenges: Accessibility issues, the need for adaptive technologies, and accommodating diverse learning styles are essential considerations for ensuring inclusivity.

Economically Disadvantaged Students

Identification: Students facing economic challenges, with limited access to resources or support systems, fall into this vulnerable group.

Challenges: Affordability of education, access to necessary technologies, and opportunities for practical experiences may be limited.

Underrepresented Minorities

Identification: Minorities, including individuals from marginalized racial, ethnic, or cultural backgrounds, may face disparities in educational settings.

Challenges: Overcoming stereotypes, ensuring cultural sensitivity, and promoting diversity within the predictive maintenance field are crucial.

Challenges Faced by At-Risk Groups in Predictive Maintenance Education

Limited Access to Technology

Challenge: Students from poor backgrounds or regions may lack access to essential technologies required for online predictive maintenance education.

Impact: This limitation hinders their ability to engage with digital content, access online resources, and participate fully in educational experiences.

Insufficient Learning Support

Challenge: Students with disabilities or unique learning needs may require additional support, such as adaptive technologies, learning accommodations, or personalized assistance.

Impact: Without adequate support, these students may face barriers in understanding complex predictive maintenance concepts and applying them effectively.

Lack of Representation

Challenge: Underrepresented minorities may struggle with a lack of representation in educational materials, faculty, and industry role models within the predictive maintenance domain.

Impact: This absence may lead to feelings of isolation, reduced motivation, and hindered career aspirations among these students.

Limited Inclusive Curriculum

Challenge: The absence of an inclusive curriculum that recognizes and accommodates diverse perspectives and experiences may impact the engagement of vulnerable student groups.

Impact: Students may find it challenging to relate to the content, leading to disengagement and decreased interest in pursuing predictive maintenance careers.

D.Importance of Inclusion in Predictive Maintenance Education

Fostering inclusion in predictive maintenance education is not merely a moral imperative; it is a strategic necessity that contributes to the overall success of individuals and the industry.

The power of inclusive education | Ilene Schwartz | TEDxEastsidePrep

[Importance of Inclusion in Predictive Maintenance Education - EU Directives](#)

Advantages of Fostering Inclusion

Diverse Perspectives

Advantage: Inclusive education brings together individuals from various backgrounds, fostering a rich tapestry of perspectives within the predictive maintenance domain.

Impact: Diverse perspectives encourage innovative thinking, problem-solving, and a more comprehensive understanding of complex maintenance challenges.

Enhanced Problem-Solving Abilities

Advantage: Inclusive learning environments nurture collaboration and teamwork among students with varied skills and experiences.

Impact: Engaging with diverse problem-solving approaches prepares students to tackle real-world challenges in predictive maintenance more effectively.

Industry Relevance

Advantage: An inclusive education aligns closely with the diversity found in the predictive maintenance industry.

Impact: Graduates enter the workforce with a deep understanding of the industry's dynamics, facilitating smoother transitions and contributing to more inclusive workplaces.

Positive Outcomes for Student Engagement and Success

Increased Motivation

Outcome: Inclusive environments foster a sense of belonging, positively impacting students' motivation to actively participate in their education.

Impact: Motivated students are more likely to invest time and effort in mastering predictive maintenance concepts, leading to better academic performance.

Improved Learning Outcomes

Outcome: Inclusive teaching methods cater to diverse learning styles and needs, ensuring that content is accessible to all students.

Impact: Improved learning outcomes result in a more competent and skilled workforce entering the predictive maintenance industry.

Enhanced Career Preparedness

Outcome: Exposure to inclusive education prepares students for the realities of the diverse and dynamic predictive maintenance workplace.

Impact: Graduates are better equipped to navigate professional challenges, collaborate with diverse teams, and contribute meaningfully to their respective roles.

E. Personalized Education in Predictive Maintenance

In the realm of predictive maintenance education, personalized learning experiences stand as a transformative approach that caters to the unique needs, preferences, and aspirations of individual learners. This section delves into the definition of personalized education and explores how tailoring learning experiences to individual needs contributes to the overall success of learners in the predictive maintenance field.

Defining Personalized Education

Customized Learning Paths

Definition: Personalized education involves tailoring learning experiences to accommodate the diverse needs and preferences of individual learners.

Essence: The approach goes beyond a one-size-fits-all model, recognizing that each learner possesses distinct strengths, learning styles, and goals.

Adaptive Learning Technologies

Definition: Personalized education leverages adaptive learning technologies that dynamically adjust content and delivery based on individual learner progress and performance.

Essence: The use of technology allows for real-time adaptation, ensuring that learners receive content at their optimal pace and in alignment with their understanding.

Learner-Centric Approach

Definition: At its core, personalized education places the learner at the center of the educational experience, acknowledging their agency in shaping their learning journey.

Essence: Learners actively engage in decisions related to content, pace, assessments, and the overall structure of their educational experience.

Tailoring Learning Experiences to Individual Needs

Adaptive Curriculum Design

Approach: Personalized education involves designing adaptive curricula that allow learners to progress based on their mastery of concepts rather than a fixed timeline.

Impact: This approach ensures that each learner has the time and support needed to grasp predictive maintenance concepts thoroughly.

Varied Assessment Methods

Approach: Personalized learning employs a range of assessment methods, recognizing that individuals may excel in different ways of demonstrating understanding.

Impact: By diversifying assessments, educators gain a more comprehensive view of each learner's proficiency, allowing for targeted support.

Flexibility in Learning Resources

Approach: Personalized education provides learners with flexibility in accessing diverse learning resources, accommodating varied learning preferences.

Impact: Learners can choose resources that resonate with their preferred learning styles, fostering deeper understanding and engagement.

Predictive Maintenance with MATLAB: A Data-Based Approach

F. Technology in Predictive Maintenance Education

The integration of technology into predictive maintenance education serves as a catalyst for innovation, accessibility, and personalized learning experiences. This section explores the role of technology in personalized learning and examines the tools and platforms that facilitate online delivery in higher and vocational education. Additionally, solutions proposing assistive work-based learning technologies are presented to enhance inclusivity and accessibility.

Role of Technology in Personalized Learning

Adaptive Learning Systems

Role: Adaptive learning systems dynamically adjust content, pace, and assessments based on individual learner progress.

Impact: By tailoring the learning experience to each learner's needs, technology enhances personalization, promoting a deeper understanding of predictive maintenance concepts.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning

Role: AI and machine learning algorithms analyse learner data to predict individual needs, recommend personalized content, and adapt learning pathways.

Impact: These technologies enable proactive support, identifying areas of improvement and suggesting targeted interventions for optimal learning outcomes.

How to Use Machine Learning for Predictive Maintenance

Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR)

Role: VR and AR technologies provide immersive experiences, allowing learners to visualize complex predictive maintenance scenarios and interact with virtual equipment.

Impact: These technologies enhance engagement, providing practical insights and bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world applications.

How Augmented Reality Will Change The World Forever

Tools and Platforms for Online Delivery in Higher and Vocational Education

Learning Management Systems (LMS)

What is an LMS? A Guide to Learning Management Systems

Tool: LMS platforms streamline course administration, content delivery, and assessment, offering a centralized hub for online education.

Impact: LMS facilitates organized and accessible online courses, supporting effective communication and collaboration among educators and learners.

Video Conferencing and Collaboration Tools

Tools: Platforms such as Zoom, Microsoft Teams, and Google Meet enable real-time communication, collaboration, and interactive sessions.

Impact: These tools facilitate virtual classrooms, workshops, and discussions, promoting engagement and fostering a sense of community among learners.

Interactive E-Learning Modules

Tools: Interactive modules with multimedia elements, quizzes, and simulations enhance the online learning experience.

Impact: These modules cater to diverse learning styles, providing engaging and effective content delivery for predictive maintenance concepts.

Solution: Assistive Work-Based Learning Technologies

Inclusivity is paramount in predictive maintenance education. To address the needs of diverse learners, proposing assistive work-based learning technologies becomes essential.

What is Moodle LMS? | Moodle Academy

Solution 1: Text-to-Speech and Speech-to-Text Tools:

Assistive Technology: Text-to-speech tools assist learners with reading challenges, while speech-to-text tools aid those with writing or typing difficulties.

Impact: These tools ensure that content is accessible to learners with varying abilities, promoting an inclusive learning environment.

Solution 2: Captioning and Transcription Services:

Assistive Technology: Captioning and transcription services enhance content accessibility for learners with hearing impairments or those who prefer written formats.

Impact: These services contribute to a more inclusive educational experience, accommodating diverse learning needs.

Solution 3: Screen Readers and Magnification Tools:

Assistive Technology: Screen readers and magnification tools assist learners with visual impairments in accessing digital content.

Impact: By providing alternative ways to interact with online materials, these tools ensure that all learners can participate fully in the learning process.

G. Adaptive Learning Methods

Adaptive learning methods leverage data analytics and the wealth of information available in predictive maintenance datasets to tailor learning experiences for individual students. This section explores the application of data analytics in crafting personalized learning paths and delves into the role of predictive maintenance data in shaping educational strategies.

Leveraging Data Analytics for Personalized Learning Paths

Using Data Analytics and AI to transform Education

Student Performance Analytics

Application: Data analytics assesses individual student performance, identifying strengths and areas for improvement.

Implementation: Adaptive learning systems use performance data to dynamically adjust the difficulty and focus of learning materials for each student.

Learning Style Analysis

Application: Data analytics analyse how students prefer to learn, whether through visuals, auditory methods, or hands-on experiences.

Implementation: Adaptive systems incorporate preferred learning styles, optimizing content delivery for enhanced understanding and engagement.

Real-time Feedback Mechanisms

Application: Continuous analysis of student interactions with learning materials provides real-time insights into their comprehension levels.

Implementation: Adaptive systems offer immediate feedback, guiding students through challenging concepts and reinforcing their understanding.

Predictive Maintenance Data and Its Role in Education

Industry-Relevant Case Studies

Role: Incorporating real-world predictive maintenance case studies provides students with practical insights into industry challenges and solutions.

Impact: Students gain a contextual understanding of how theoretical knowledge applies in professional settings.

Simulation and Scenario-Based Learning

Role: Utilizing predictive maintenance data in simulations allows students to engage in realistic scenarios, enhancing their problem-solving skills.

Impact: Practical application of data in simulations prepares students for the complexities of predictive maintenance tasks.

Data-Driven Performance Metrics

Role: Analysing performance metrics derived from predictive maintenance data helps educators assess the effectiveness of teaching strategies.

Impact: Data-driven insights inform continuous improvement, ensuring that educational approaches align with industry demands.

H.Guidance for Educators

Educators play a pivotal role in fostering inclusive and personalized education in predictive maintenance.

Strategies for Implementing Inclusive and Personalized Education

Diverse Content Representation

Recommendation: Ensure that learning materials represent a diversity of voices, perspectives, and experiences within the predictive maintenance field.

Impact: Diverse content fosters a more inclusive learning environment, allowing students to connect with the material on a personal level.

Flexible Assessment Methods

Recommendation: Implement varied assessment methods that accommodate different learning styles and abilities.

Impact: Flexibility in assessments enables a fair evaluation of diverse skills, promoting an inclusive approach to student evaluation.

Active Student Participation

Recommendation: Encourage and facilitate active participation from all students, creating an environment where everyone feels valued.

Impact: Active participation fosters a sense of belonging, enhancing the overall engagement and success of students.

Institutional and Policy Recommendations

Resource Allocation

Recommendation: Allocate resources to support the integration of technology, adaptive learning systems, and assistive technologies in predictive maintenance education.

Impact: Adequate resources ensure that institutions can provide inclusive and personalized learning experiences for all students.

Professional Development

Recommendation: Provide ongoing professional development opportunities for educators to stay informed about the latest technologies and inclusive teaching practices.

Impact: Continuous learning empowers educators to create dynamic and relevant learning environments, benefiting students and institutions alike.

Policy Support for Accessibility

Recommendation: Establish policies that prioritize accessibility and inclusion in predictive maintenance education.

Impact: Institutional policies supporting accessibility contribute to a more equitable educational landscape, fostering success for all students.

I. Conclusion

In the ever-evolving landscape of education and the dynamic field of predictive maintenance, this handbook has endeavoured to shed light on the critical aspects of inclusive and personalized education. We have explored strategies for online deliveries in higher and vocational education, aiming to equip educators, institutions, and stakeholders with the knowledge and tools necessary to foster a learning environment that is accessible, adaptive, and tailored to individual needs.

Embracing Diversity in Predictive Maintenance Education

The journey through this handbook began with an exploration of the evolution of predictive maintenance, emphasizing the paradigm shift from reactive models to proactive identification of potential failures. Recognizing the changing dynamics in education, we delved into the challenges faced by traditional approaches and the necessity for inclusive and personalized education. The spotlight then turned to the rise of online deliveries, acknowledging their pivotal role in providing accessible and flexible learning experiences.

Significance of Inclusion and Personalization

The section on the significance of inclusion and personalized education underscored the transformative impact of fostering diversity and tailoring education to individual needs. Inclusivity became more than a concept; it became a guiding principle that breaks down barriers to education, enhances access for all, and creates collaborative learning environments. Simultaneously, personalized education emerged as the cornerstone for adapting to varied skill levels, encouraging self-paced learning, and ensuring real-world relevance in predictive maintenance education.

Challenges in Traditional Education

As we explored the challenges in traditional education, we identified limitations and barriers that hinder the effective preparation of individuals for the demands of predictive maintenance. The lack of flexibility, inadequate integration of technology, and limited accessibility were recognized as impediments that must be addressed to bridge the gap between education and industry needs. Furthermore, we explored the gaps in catering to diverse learning needs, emphasizing the need for adaptive approaches to accommodate varying learning styles, proficiency levels, and preferences.

Empowering Vulnerable Student Groups

The focus then shifted to identifying and addressing vulnerable student groups in educational settings. By recognizing the challenges faced by students with disabilities, poor students, and underrepresented minorities, we aimed to highlight the importance of targeted strategies to ensure equal access and opportunities for all. The challenges faced by these groups were examined, including limited access to technology, insufficient learning support, lack of representation, and the need for an inclusive curriculum.

Advantages of Fostering Inclusion

Moving to the advantages of fostering inclusion, we explored the benefits of diverse perspectives, enhanced problem-solving abilities, and industry relevance. The positive outcomes for student engagement and success were emphasized, highlighting increased motivation, improved learning outcomes, and enhanced career preparedness resulting from inclusive educational practices.

Personalized Education in Predictive Maintenance

The section on personalized education elucidated the definition and essence of tailoring learning experiences to individual needs. Adaptive curriculum design, varied assessment methods, and flexibility in learning resources emerged as essential components of personalized education in predictive maintenance. These approaches ensure that learners progress based on their mastery of concepts, receive fair evaluations, and have access to diverse learning materials that resonate with their preferred styles.

Leveraging Technology for Personalization

Recognizing the pivotal role of technology, the exploration of technology in predictive maintenance education emphasized the role of interactive e-learning modules and proposed assistive work-based learning technologies. The use of assistive tools such as text-to-speech and speech-to-text, captioning and transcription services, and screen readers and magnification tools became integral to creating an inclusive and accessible online learning environment.

Adaptive Learning Methods

The final section delved into adaptive learning methods, leveraging data analytics and predictive maintenance data to tailor learning experiences for individual students. By leveraging the wealth of information available in datasets, adaptive

learning methods ensure that educational strategies align with the evolving demands of the predictive maintenance landscape.

Moving Forward: A Call to Action

As we conclude this handbook, it is imperative to recognize that the journey towards inclusive and personalized education in predictive maintenance is an ongoing endeavour. The integration of emerging technologies, ongoing professional development for educators, and the establishment of policies supporting accessibility will be crucial in sustaining these transformative practices. It is a collective responsibility to foster an educational landscape that not only meets the needs of the present but also prepares individuals for the challenges and opportunities of the future in the predictive maintenance field.

In the spirit of continual improvement and innovation, we encourage educators, institutions, policymakers, and industry stakeholders to collaborate, share insights, and implement strategies that promote inclusivity, personalization, and excellence in predictive maintenance education. This handbook serves as a catalyst for change, providing a foundation upon which to build a more accessible, adaptive, and empowering educational environment for all learners in predictive maintenance and beyond.

J. References

- Siemens, G., & Long, P. (2011). "Penetrating the Fog: Analytics in Learning and Education." *EDUCAUSE Review*, 46(5), 30-32.
- <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ950794>
- Anderson, C. A. (2019). "Improving Higher Education: The Role of Predictive Analytics." *Change: The Magazine of Higher Learning*, 51(4), 8-15.
- Unesco. (n.d.). Education for Sustainable Development Goals: Learning Objectives. UNESCO.org. <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/education-sustainable-development-goals-learning-objectives>
- Tindale, A., & Sewell, A. (2018). "Creating Inclusive Learning Environments in Higher Education: A Multifaceted Approach to Disability Support." *Journal of the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning*, 18(1), 124-142.
- Bitter, G. G., et al. (2018). "Using Technology to Support Inclusive Education." *TEACHING Exceptional Children*, 51(5), 336-346.
- West, R. E. (2018). "Inclusive Education: A Best Practice Guide." Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Education.
- Bell, P. (2017). "Preparing 21st Century Scientists: Promoting Students' Meta-Awareness of the Practices of Science in Metagenomics." *CBE—Life Sciences Education*, 16(4), es5.
- Page, S. (2008). *The difference: How the power of diversity creates better groups, firms, schools, and societies-new edition*. Princeton University Press.
- Hong, L., & Page, S. E. (2004). Groups of diverse problem solvers can outperform groups of high-ability problem solvers. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 101(46), 16385-16389.
- Cox, T. (1994). "Cultural Diversity in Organizations: Theory, Research, and Practice." Berrett-Koehler.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). "The 'what' and 'why' of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior." *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227-268.
- Hattie, J., & Timperley, H. (2007). "The power of feedback." *Review of Educational Research*, 77(1), 81-112.
- Gardner, H. (2006). "Five Minds for the Future." *Harvard Business Review*.

- Horn, M. B., & Staker, H. (2015). "Blended: Using disruptive innovation to improve schools." John Wiley & Sons.
- Knewton. (2019). "The State of Digital Learning Data."
- Darling-Hammond, L., & Ifill-Lynch, O. (2006). "If they'd only do it right: Techno-enthusiasts respond to the coming of the digital age." *Teachers College Record*, 108(8), 1484-1525.
- Merrill, M. D. (2009). "First principles of instruction." *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 57(1), 31-48.
- Mayer, R. E. (2019). "Multimedia Learning." Cambridge University Press.
- Clark, R. C., & Mayer, R. E. (2016). "E-learning and the science of instruction: Proven guidelines for consumers and designers of multimedia learning." John Wiley & Sons.
- Zajicek, M. (2003). "Voice and Speech Recognition Assistive Technology as a Computer Access Aid." In *Assistive Technology on the Threshold of the New Millennium* (pp. 459-464). IOS Press.
- Edmonds, C., & Lombardo, C. (2018). "The effects of captioning videos on academic achievement and student satisfaction." *TechTrends*, 62(5), 488-495.
- Paciello, M. G. (2000). "Web accessibility for people with disabilities." CMP Books.
- Siemens, G., & Gasevic, D. (2012). "Guest Editorial—Learning and Knowledge Analytics." *Educational Technology & Society*, 15(3), 1-2.
- Siemens, G. (2013). "Learning analytics: The emergence of a discipline." *American Behavioral Scientist*, 57(10), 1380-1400.
- Kovanović, V., Joksimović, S., Dawson, S., Gasevic, D., & Siemens, G. (2015). "Reflecting on the differences between IMS Learning Analytics and the xAPI." *IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies*, 8(1), 16-28.
- Winkle-Wagner, R., & McCoy, D. L. (2020). "Inclusive Teaching and Learning in Higher Education." Routledge.
- Villegas, A. M., & Lucas, T. (2007). "The culturally responsive teacher." *Educational Leadership*, 64(6), 28-33.
- Pellegrino, J. W., Chudowsky, N., & Glaser, R. (Eds.). (2001). "Knowing what students know: The science and design of educational assessment." National Academies Press.

Tinto, V. (2017). "Student success and the building of supportive educational communities." *Learning Communities Journal*, 9(1), 5.

Brown, M., DeMonbrun, R., McCormack, A. C., & Gavrin, A. (2015). "Economic diversity and the affordability of undergraduate education." *Change: The Magazine of Higher Learning*, 47(1), 6-13.

Darling-Hammond, L., Hyler, M. E., & Gardner, M. (2017). "Effective teacher professional development." Learning Policy Institute.

Burgstahler, S. (2015). "Universal design in higher education: From principles to practice." Harvard Education Press.

Equality Challenge Unit. (2016). "Inclusive curriculum design in higher education." Advance HE.

Importance of Inclusion in Predictive Maintenance Education - EU Directives

Video resources:

Diversity, Equity & Inclusion. Learning how to get it right | Asif Sadiq | TEDxCroydon - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HR4wz1b54hw>

Vulnerability: Finding Your Voice | Delin Liu | TEDxYouth@StMarksSchool - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=y1VGe3wWwM>

The power of inclusive education | Ilene Schwartz | TEDxEastsidePrep - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZIPsPRaZP6M>

Predictive Maintenance with MATLAB: A Data-Based Approach - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5ChEy3llqMQ>

How to Use Machine Learning for Predictive Maintenance - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BApzsgq32mM>

How Augmented Reality Will Change The World Forever - <https://youtu.be/sfsHfCAOBuQ?feature=shared>

What is an LMS? A Guide to Learning Management Systems - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=q-3VyQQ_wFM

What is Moodle LMS? | Moodle Academy - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aFtiVknKnk>

Using Data Analytics and AI to transform Education - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E0kmtQKRzTc>

PreMETS

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training.

Module TN4: Strategies for generating brain plasticity
and learning connections
[Booklet]

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A. Introduction

In this booklet we are going to talk about boosting the online learning efficiency of students. To achieve this, behavioural/neuroscience will be utilised to provide guidelines in terms of how the learning/teaching pace and structure should be developed and tailored for the identified needs (with the implicit transferability potential to other disciplines and even other types of formal education such as adult training).

The barriers associated with online learning correlate with some teachers' inability to build a personal relationship with their students and monitor their productivity during class. Providing the program content is only the first step, and probably not even the most important. Connecting with students should be an instructor's primary goal. Creating trust and convenient management of the virtual classroom for the user can be achieved by familiarizing oneself with the available technological tools.

Higher Education institutions have shifted towards online education in these past years due to the Corona pandemic. However, this presented a series of challenges for all parties involved, universities, teachers, and students. One of these challenges is related to finding the proper ways in which to support students become more efficient in their online learning. Different models and methods exist but there are still studies to be conducted in order to find the most appropriate way of doing things. Most likely there is not a single fit-all solution, and teachers and students alike need to experiment with several of these models and methods finding the one which best suits their needs.

One of these models is the AGES Model, standing for Attention-Generation-Emotion-Spacing, which is presented in detail in Section B.

Some strategies for boosting attention and motivating students are presented in Section C, with a focus on building engagement and motivation with course content and activities.

Strategies for generating brain plasticity and learning connections are discussed in Section D, with presentations of constructivism and connectivism alike.

Section E presents strategies for understanding timing and why it is important. Finally, Section F presents other strategies we find useful for this booklet.

B. The AGES Model

It is important to understand how human psychology and brain science would be useful for the needs of adult learners. One researcher who looked into this is Lila Davachi, Associate Professor of Psychology at New York University, who proposes the AGES model, standing for Attention-Generation-Emotion-Spacing.

Attention

Learning something new requires focused attention. To learn new information, it must be of interest or meaningful and there must be limited distractions. Multi-tasking requires that we attend to more than one thing at a time. Although it is physically possible to multi-task, studies show that performance on each additional task, including the first, reduces. So, multi-tasking comes at the expense of time to complete the task, or quality of the output. Furthermore, it is almost impossible to learn something new whilst multi-tasking. This suggests that multi-tasking is best suited to habitual behaviours that require little or no cognitive input. The implication for designers of learning and development programs is that learners need to be in an environment that encourages and allows single matter concentration for most powerful learning uptake.

Neuroscience research now tells us that the brain doesn't do tasks simultaneously as we thought, but switches tasks rapidly in a stop/start process. This is inefficient and better to focus on one task at a time. Edward Hallowell, MD, Director of the Hallowell Center for Cognitive and Emotional Health has reiterated that true multitasking is only but a myth¹. Though we are inclined to believe that we are doing multiple things at the same time, it is nothing but a misconception. This is because the cerebral cortex in the brain can focus on only one thing at a time. What happens is that the mind shifts from one thing to the other very quickly and in the process, the effectiveness of both is lost.

Generation

Adult learning differs markedly from childhood learning. Children absorb everything about their world in an uncensored way and place total confidence in the adults around them. Adults selectively choose what they learn based on what is relevant and of interest to them. Adults build on prior learning and take as much responsibility as they want for their ongoing learning (Illeris, 2010). As a result, self-directed learning methods are highly effective in adults.

“The brain is a dynamic, plastic, experience dependent, social and affective organ” and is not just engaged in, but driving, its own learning (Immordino-Yang & Fischer, 2010). By extension, the more the brain is proactively involved in its learning, the

¹ <https://www.webmd.com/mental-health/features/why-multitasking-isnt-efficient>

more effective it becomes. This is why the self-generation of ideas, strategies and actions is so critical in adult learning. With the focus on relevance and immediacy, adults learn best by taking a problem-centered, rather than a subject-centered, approach (Merriam, 2010). This includes defining and analysing the problem, challenging the learners' thinking, determining approaches to its resolution, and encouraging team debate. The key is that ownership of the process, as well as its outcomes, is with the learner.

Emotion

Emotions bind memory. Like adding fuel to a flame, an emotional cue ignites more neuronal activity in more brain centres and, consequently, burns a deeper pathway. The vivid recollections we have of events in our life that carry rich emotional content are embedded through the activity of many thousands more neurons than is the case for 'normal' or unemotive events.

Emotion, of course, does not need to be negative. We learn better when we are in a happy, positive mood and when we are having fun. Research, for example, shows that including games in learning programs with relevant context, requiring challenging technical skills and appropriately debriefed on completion, add to the learning outcomes of all four of the Kolb learning styles (concrete experiences, reflective observation, abstract conceptualisation, and active experimentation) (Dieleman & Huisinigh, 2006).

Spacing

A relatively simple, but underutilised, way of improving learning outcomes is to reconsider how we 'space' content. The limitations to prefrontal cortex capacity come into direct play when we are learning, as new information must take this route to be embedded as acquired skills and knowledge. So, learning programs that begin at 8:00 AM and cram content back-to-back until 5:00 PM, with only brief comfort and food breaks, contravene our biological limitations and invariably limit learning uptake. The law of diminishing returns applies to learning due to our cognitive capacity. We need to respect our biology more and work with, not against, its limitations.

With this in mind, program designers should consider staging learning content - within and across days. For example, a leadership program that introduces new content, such as leadership models, in the morning session, then applies this content all afternoon in interactive and engaging ways, will achieve a much better learning outcome than a full day of new content alone. Programs that stagger sessions over consecutive or even intermittent days allow for the benefits of memory consolidation during sleep to improve outcomes.

C. Strategies to boost attention and motivate students

Higher education institutions are expected to produce skilful, problem solver, and competent graduates. This becomes possible when the instructors are using the appropriate teaching methodology and the learners are active and empowered in the teaching-learning process. Of the factors that influence student learning, motivation is surely one of the most potent (Svinicki, 1999). An instructor can improve a student's intrinsic motivation through external stimuli, by setting realistic incremental task-based goals, and by allowing students to work autonomously through them.

There are hundreds of studies which show evidence to support the notion that goal setting increases success rates (e.g., Turkay, 2014). "Task-based goals had large and robust positive effects on the level of task completion, and [...] also increased course performance" (Clark et al. 2016). According to Clark et al. (2016) "goal setting is a low-cost, scalable and feasible intervention that could improve college outcomes and could be built into the technology used to deliver these course components". Engagement is fostered by allowing students to study on their own terms; anytime, anywhere. Studies into workforce productivity have shown that allowing people to work from anywhere led to as much as a 50% increase in productivity (Koulopoulos and Keldsen, 2016).

Why do we perceive that productivity in the workplace should differ from productivity in education? People who are actively engaged, no matter the situation, are more productive. Nearly 50% of the connected generation prefer working non-traditional hours and over 60% use mobile devices to manage their lives (Aruba, 2014), this should be used to educators' advantage. On average people spend around five and a half hours daily, actively engaged on some form of Internet-connected device, these figures are massively augmented, up to thirteen hours a day, for younger generations (Koulopoulos and Keldsen, 2016).

Educators need to harness this mobile potential and, if only utilising a fraction of this time, can massively enhance learning outcomes. However, even though technology can aid motivation and engagement, it does not automatically lead to better learning, it is only when this engagement can be harnessed for learning that there will be any academic benefit (Higgins, 2012), again stressing the need for pedagogically sound implementation.

Empowerment is improved through increased student agency and autonomy, as well as interdependency, these are all supported by student-centred methodologies which aim to improve the "students' capacity to act or exert themselves into their learning" (Sheninger and Murray, 2017). An example is differentiated instruction, this is a pedagogical strategy that allows students to work collaboratively on meaningful tasks at their own level and pace (Prensky,

2001) through activities such as task-based learning. Meta-analysis studies have consistently shown that collaborative learning has wide-spread positive influence on academic achievement, self-esteem, quality of interpersonal interactions as well as student attitudes (Prince, 2004).

The number of collaborative tasks implemented also has an effect on the results. Springer et al. (1999) investigated this further and found that the best results, in terms of positive effect size, were to be obtained through medium amounts group work. However, it has also been said that self-directed learning may have a negative effect (Colliver,2000). According to Pitler et al. (2007), it is, therefore, critical to correctly implement technology into instructional scenarios to increase learner agency and facilitate “analytical and critical thinking and the collaboration championed in the constructivist approach to education”.

Build Engagement and Motivation with Course Content and Activities²

PROVIDE STUDENTS WITH A VARIETY OF CONTENT

Open Educational Resources and other forms of readily available media can help by providing a broader perspective. Textbooks, journal articles, multimedia and interactive learning objects are just some of types of content you can provide your students.

CREATE A SHORT INTRODUCTION TO EACH MODULE

One of the most important aspects—if not the most important aspect—of any student’s learning is you, the instructor. Short introductions to content and course activities from you the instructor can draw attention to important concepts and provide purpose and clarity.

PROVIDE CLEAR GUIDANCE FOR COMPLETING COURSE ACTIVITIES AND GAINING DEEPER UNDERSTANDING OF COURSE CONTENT

Active learning strategies help students to think critically and to make connections with content and course activities. Take the next step beyond posting assigned readings or static instructional presentations and really be present in your online course, helping them focus their attention on what is most important. It is essential for students to have specific guidance on how the course materials align with the objectives of the course. Today’s university students come from a wide variety of backgrounds and experiences. These students may need additional guidance and may need to put a face and voice to the instructor. Instructor presence and intentional engagement are critical to the success of an online student. Share your perspectives through microlectures to synthesize key concepts in the course materials, create a weekly introduction to just-in-time due dates and important

²<https://www.niu.edu/citl/resources/guides/increase-student-engagement-in-online-courses.shtml>

course activities, and challenge students to improve their work with timely feedback. Find more tips for managing your online presence.

SEND OUT HOMEWORK DUE DATE REMINDERS FOR EACH ASSIGNMENT

Use Blackboard announcements, email, or Teams. Students appreciate these reminders, and it helps them stay on track.

ENCOURAGE YOUR STUDENTS TO ASK QUESTIONS

Use opportunities like office hours and breakout groups (on Zoom, Teams, or Collaborate, for example) to encourage discussion among peers. Also, utilize discussion forums to solicit questions from your students. All students can benefit from a question asked from one student.

ALLOW STUDENTS TO SHARE REFLECTIONS ON THEIR LEARNING

Metacognition is a strong motivator in student learning. Ask students to write out their course goals or to keep a course journal.

SUPPORT STUDENTS' ABILITY TO EXPLORE, EDIT AND CREATE

The creative skills of students can be a great asset. If appropriate, offer student choice in how they complete an assessment or ask them to find their own content which fits your parameters.

D.Strategies for generating brain plasticity and learning connections

Neuroplasticity is the brain's ability to change and adapt as a result of experience. It is also known as brain plasticity, However, when people say that the brain possesses plasticity, they are not suggesting that the brain is similar to plastic³.

Plasticity refers to the brain's malleability, which is defined as being "easily influenced, trained, or controlled." Neuro refers to neurons, the nerve cells that are the building blocks of the brain and nervous system. Thus, neuroplasticity is when nerve cells change or adjust.

HOW DOES SYNAPTIC PLASTICITY RELATE TO LEARNING AND MEMORY? (Owens & Tanner, 2017)

Researchers have repeatedly shown that neural connections in many different parts of the brain can change, and that this synaptic plasticity is associated with and leads to behavioural learning and the formation of memories. For instance, neuroscientists found that training mice in a novel motor task induced an outgrowth of new synapses very quickly, within an hour, in the motor cortex, a part of the brain dedicated to planned movements. Furthermore, they found that further training stabilized some of the new synapses so that they remained present for weeks, months, and possibly years (Xu et al., 2009; Yang et al., 2009). We also know that blocking specific processes and molecules important for synaptic plasticity, such as particular neurotransmitter receptors, prevents behavioural learning, giving a causal connection between synaptic plasticity and learning (Morris et al., 1986). These are just some of the thousands of studies in all sorts of animal models that link synaptic plasticity between neurons to the changes in behaviour that indicate learning and memory formation (Takeuchi et al., 2014).

³ <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-brain-plasticity-2794886>

Owens and Tanner present a table of various teaching techniques and their possible neuronal bases:

Neuroscientific principle discussed in this Feature	Psychological or educational findings or ideas that may correspond to the neuroscientific principle.	Teaching techniques that may harness the corresponding principle.
Synaptic plasticity is specific to the particular neurons that are active together.	Active forms of studying improve performance over passive forms.	Frequent, active homework.
	Deliberate practice is important for gaining expertise.	Deploying varied types of Assessments. Giving students time in class to discuss, write, and solve problems.
Memories are encoded as synaptic networks.	Encoding knowledge relationally helps in remembering it.	Concept maps.
		Preassessments that tie new material to pre-existing knowledge.
		Activities that ask students to compare, synthesize, and evaluate.
Dopamine and ACh, released during states of motivation and attention, boost synaptic plasticity.	Motivation and attention increase learning.	Problem-based learning.
		Tailoring examples and activities to identified student interests.
		Using culturally diverse examples.
Cortisol, released during stress, depresses synaptic plasticity.	Stereotype threat undermines learning and performance.	Values affirmation.
		Equity strategies.

The constructivism learning theory has evolved to be in today's era of social media a connectivism learning theory that considers that learning occurs through connections learners make with each other as well as with the learning content.

Learning through connections is an important piece of putting the learner at the centre of the learning process; a process that empowers the learner to be fully engaged in the learning process and to be the builder of her own knowledge using her curiosity and imagination. Constructivism has been and continues to be a hot topic in learning theories.

In online learning environments, cognitive learning theories provide a framework for a learner centered approach to instructional design.

These theories emphasize constructivist orientations to learning, such as generative learning (Jonassen, 1988), situated learning (Chiou, 1992), and problem-based learning (Savery, J. R., & Duffy, T. M., 1995). Constructivist orientations aim to assist the learner in selecting appropriate information pertaining to the learning content, organizing information into internally consistent concepts, and integrating new knowledge, making it personally relevant and meaningful (Lawson, 2011).

The constructivist model of education provides a significant environment for authentic learning, active learning, and reflective learning.

The six main characteristics of constructivist learning environments as noted by (Jonassen, 1994) are:

1. Constructivist learning environments provide multiple and complex representations of reality, avoiding simplifications.
2. Constructivist learning environments emphasize knowledge construction in relation to its content instead of knowledge reproduction.
3. Constructivist learning environments emphasize authentic tasks in a meaningful context rather than abstract instruction out of context.
4. Constructivist learning environments provide learning environments such as real-world setting or case-based learning instead of predetermined sequences of instruction.
5. Constructivist learning environments encourage practices based on thoughtful reflection.
6. Constructivist learning environments support collaborative learning through social negotiation, instead of competition among learners.

As an extension of constructivism, connectivism emerged recently in the digital age of a networked era as an educational pedagogy, in which learning is the

process of building networks of information, contacts, and resources that are applied to real problems (Downes, 2007) (Siemens, 2007).

“Connectivist learning focuses on building and maintaining networked connections that are current and flexible enough to be applied to existing and emergent problems.

Connectivism also assumes that information is plentiful, and that the learner’s role is not to memorize or even understand everything, but to have the capacity to find and apply knowledge when and where it is needed.” (Anderson and Dron, 2011).

Siemens (2005), who is considered as the father of connectivist learning theory, states the following as 8 principles of connectivism:

- Learning through Learning and knowledge rest in diversity of opinions.
- Learning is a process of connecting specialized nodes or information sources.
- Learning may reside in non-human appliances.
- Capacity to know more is more critical than what is currently known.
- Nurturing and maintaining connections is needed to facilitate continual learning.
- Ability to see connections between fields, ideas, and concepts is a core skill.
- Currency (accurate, up-to-date knowledge) is the intent of all connectivist learning activities.
- Decision making is itself a learning process. Choosing what to learn and the meaning of incoming information is seen through the lens of a shifting reality. While there is a right answer now, it may be wrong tomorrow due to alterations in the information climate affecting the decision.

E. Strategies for understanding timing

Make a schedule⁴

Without a professor regularly checking in, it's important to leverage your time management skills. Glance over the syllabus before your first day of class and make note of major assignments. Mark them on a calendar you check regularly so you know what workload is coming in the weeks ahead. Don't forget to factor in prior commitments that may interfere with your regular study schedule, such as weddings or vacations, so you can give yourself enough extra time to complete assignments.

Commit to making your online coursework part of your weekly routine. Break up your workload into chunks by dedicating certain hours each week to reading, watching lectures, writing assignments, studying, and participating in forums. Then, set reminders for yourself to complete the tasks. Treat these blocks of time as seriously as you would a face-to-face lesson by showing up, letting others know you are unavailable during those times, and consistently using your designated workspace. Set a timer and give yourself permission to move on to other tasks once the time is up.

SMART Objectives⁵

A S.M.A.R.T. goal is defined as one that is Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Results-focused, and Time-bound. These types of goals will help provide structure and guidance throughout your assessment, ensure good communication among you and any team members, and will better identify what you wish to accomplish.

Specific: When setting your goals being clear and specific will help focus your efforts. You can use the essential "W"s as a starting point to draft your goals.

WHO - Who is involved? WHO are my stakeholders?

WHAT - What do I want to accomplish?

WHEN - Establish a time frame to complete your assessment.

WHY - Why is this important?

What are the specific reasons, purpose or benefits of moving forward with the assessment? Being specific will help remind you that your objectives should relate back to the goals of your department/organization.

Measurable: Your goals should be measurable so that you have tangible evidence you've accomplished what you set out to do. Measurable goals will help you stay

⁴ <https://www.northeastern.edu/bachelors-completion/news/successful-online-learning-strategies/>

⁵ <https://guides.library.ucla.edu/assessment/smartgoals>

on track, reach deadlines and target dates. Data collection is an excellent indicator to track progress, however you do not necessarily need numbers or statistics to know you are working towards your objectives. The main question to ask yourself:

- How much?
- How many?
- To what degree?
- How will I know the goal has been accomplished?

Achievable: The goal(s) should be realistic, and possible to achieve. It may help you to break down the steps of your assessment into smaller stages and establish a timeframe to allow you to carry out those steps. This can help you achieve an overall objective that seemed impossible at the start. Ask yourself:

How can I accomplish this goal?

How realistic is the goal, based on other constraints and factors (i.e., financial, time commitments)?

Do I have the necessary knowledge, skills, abilities, and resources to accomplish the goal?

Results-Focused: Your goals should be aligned with the strategic outcomes of your department/organization, and focus on results. Remember that your goals should be measuring outcomes, not focusing on the activities you used to get there. Questions to ask include:

Can I attain this goal with the available resources within the given timeframe?

What will I/my organization gain from accomplishing this goal?

Time-Bound: Finally, you should have a target date in mind - with a deadline to work towards you create a practical sense of urgency for yourself. As mentioned previously, it may have to help mini-deadlines for steps along the way in your assessment, in addition to the final target date of completion. Keep in mind to make these deadlines realistic and flexible for yourself. Missing a deadline should not completely derail your assessment - adjust as needed and keep yourself motivated.

F. Other strategies

Our education needs to be more creative than ever. There are some examples of creative approaches such as (Motie et als, 2020):

Use of gamification in training: Use common elements of the game (for example, scoring, competing with others, rules of the game) in the field of education. The excitement of the game enters into training and learning is like a game.

Lesson storytelling: In this student-centred creative approach, the student teaches part of the training in the form of a story, novel, or summary for other students. Each student assumes a part in the training. increase the sense of responsibility in student cause to increase learning. This approach is suitable for theoretical courses whose references are clear.

Holding large online scientific competitions: These competitions are to encourage students to study their courses individually. These competitions can have different facilities (such as tuition discounts or cash prizes) for the students.

Group Activities: This extends more collaborative behaviour and mutual learning.

G. References

- Svinicki, Marilla D. "New directions in learning and motivation." *New directions for teaching and learning* 1999, no. 80 (1999): 5-27.
- S. Turkay, "Setting Goals: Who, Why, How?," Manuscript, 2014.
- D. Clark, M. Rush, V. Prowse, and M. Rush, "Using goals to motivate college students: Theory and evidence from field experiments," *IZA Discuss. Pap.*, no. 10283, 2016.
- T. Koulopoulos and D. Keldsen, *Gen Z Effect: The Six Forces Shaping the Future of Business*. Routledge; 1 edition (December 1, 2016), 2016.
- Aruba, "Are you ready for #GenMobile: How a new group is changing the way we work, live and communicate.," 2014.
- S. Higgins, Z. Xiao, and M. Katsipataki, "The Impact of Digital Technology on Learning: A Summary for the Education Endowment Foundation Full Report," *Educ. Endow. Found.*, vol. November, no. November 2012, p. Available at: <https://educationendowmentfoundation>, 2012.
- E. C. Sheninger and T. C. Murray, *Learning Transformed: 8 Keys to Designing Tomorrow's Schools, Today*. ASCD, 2017.
- M. Prensky, "Digital Natives, Digital Immigrants," *Horiz.*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 1–6, 2001.
- M. Prince, "Does Active Learning Work? A Review of the Research," *Excell. Coll. Teach.*, vol. 93, no. July, pp. 223–231, 2004.
- L. Springer, M. E. Stanne, and S. S. Donovan, "Effects of Small-Group Learning on Undergraduates in Science, Mathematics, Engineering, and Technology: A Meta-Analysis," *Rev. Educ. Res.*, vol. 69, no. 1, pp. 21–51, 1999.
- J. A. Colliver, "Effectiveness of Problem-based Learning Curricula: Research and Theory," *Acad. Med.*, vol. 75, no. 3, pp. 259–266, 2000.
- Pitler, E. R. Hubbell, M. Kuhn, and K. Malenoski, *Using Technology with Classroom Instruction That Works*, vol. 22, no. 1. 2007.
- Owens, M.T. and Tanner, K.D., 2017. Teaching as brain changing: Exploring connections between neuroscience and innovative teaching. *CBE—Life Sciences Education*, 16(2), p.fe2.
- Xu L, Ramirez S, Pan PT, Puryear CB, Govindarajan A, Deisseroth K, Tonegawa S (2012). Optogenetic stimulation of a hippocampal engram activates fear memory recall. *Nature* 484, 381-385.

- Morris RG, Anderson E, Lynch GS, Baudry M (1986). Selective impairment of learning and blockade of long-term potentiation by an N-methyl-d-aspartate receptor antagonist, AP5. *Nature* 319, 774-77615
- Yang G, Pan F, Gan W-B (2009). Stably maintained dendritic spines are associated with lifelong memories. *Nature* 462, 920-924
- Takeuchi T, Duzskiewicz AJ, Morris RGM (2014). The synaptic plasticity and memory hypothesis: encoding, storage and persistence. *Phil Trans R Soc B* 369, 1-14.
- Jonassen, D.H., 1986. Hypertext principles for text and courseware design. *Educational psychologist*, 21(4), pp.269-292.
- Savery, J.R. and Duffy, T.M., 1995. Problem based learning: An instructional model and its constructivist framework. *Educational technology*, 35(5), pp.31-38.
- Chiou, G.F., 1992. Situated learning, metaphors, and computer-based learning environments. *Educational Technology*, 32(8), pp.7-11.
- Jonassen, D.H., 1994. Thinking technology: Toward a constructivist design model. *Educational technology*, 34(4), pp.34-37.
- Downes, S., 2007. Learning networks in practice. *Emerging technologies for learning*, 2(4), p.20.
- Siemens, G., 2007. Connectivism: Creating a learning ecology in distributed environments. *Didactics of microlearning. Concepts, discourses and examples*, pp.53-68.
- Motie, M., Dehnavieh, R. and Kalavani, K., 2020. Increasing the effectiveness of Virtual Learning during COVID-19. *Arch Community Med Public Health*, 6(2), pp.174-175.
- Vorhauser-Smith, S., THE NEUROSCIENCE OF LEARNING & DEVELOPMENT PAGEUP PEOPLE WHITE PAPER, February 2011
- Illeris, K. (2010). Characteristics of adult learning.
- Immordino-Yang, M.H. & Fischer, K.W. (2010). Neuroscience bases for learning.
- Merriam, S.B. (2010). *Adult education – adult learning, instruction and program planning*. Elsevier.
- Dieleman, H. & Huisingh, D. (2006). Games by which to learn and teach about sustainable development: exploring the relevance of games and experiential learning for sustainability. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 14, 837-847

Davachi, L., Kiefer, T., Rock, D. and Rock, L. (2010) Learning that lasts through AGES. NeuroLeadership Journal. Issue 3, 2010.

PreMETS

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training

**Module TN5: Qualitative & effective open educational
resources (OERs)
[Booklet]**

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the European Union**

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A. Introduction

In the dynamic realm of predictive maintenance, where technological advancements occur at an unprecedented pace, the role of educational innovation and technological evolution emerges as an imperative catalyst to meet the multifaceted demands of this ever-evolving field. To empower trainers in meeting the dynamic demands of this field, this comprehensive booklet on Open Educational Resources (OERs) is specifically tailored for Predictive Maintenance Trainers.

This booklet endeavors to serve as a compass, navigating through the expansive landscape of OERs, offering insights into their definition, historical development, characteristics, advantages, challenges, future trends, and practical recommendations. Additionally, it provides a curated list of OER repositories and demonstrative videos, enriching the training experience and facilitating a seamless integration of open educational resources into predictive maintenance modules.

B. Definition and History

The core principle behind Open Educational Resources is based on a straightforward but impactful idea: making educational materials freely and legally accessible, open for anyone to use, amend, contribute to and forward. While this idea seems simple enough, a definition and academic integration only developed at the turn of the last century. Since then, there has been significant improvement in terms of dissemination and accessibility of the concept, however, OERs are still not implemented in all academic levels and disciplines.

The academic uptake and development of OERs took place in the late 1990s and early 2000s and aligns with a broader shift in higher education towards openness and democratization of sources. This is highly related to other movements like Open Source Software or Open Access (Hylan, 2006), which were part of the emergence of the culture of open knowledge in the late 20th century. One of the first accelerators for Open Education was the 1997 founding of MERLOT, a California State University-led program that curated mostly free materials for higher education. The publication of PLOS and the Budapest Open Access Initiative are also listed as initial events that kickstarted the evolution of OERs. Other notable projects are the Rice University's OpenStax programme and the MIT's OpenCourseWare, which both facilitate open source educational content (Bliss & Smith, 2017).

While the concept of sharing educational content is certainly not exclusive to the 21st century, the term "Open Educational Resources" was coined during a 2002 conference by United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) in which OERs were defined as "The open provision of educational resources, enabled by information and communication technologies, for consultation, use and adaptation by a community of users for non-commercial purposes." (UNESCO, 2008). In a more updated definition, UNESCO states that the concept of Open Educational resources "describes any educational resources (including curriculum maps, course materials, textbooks, streaming videos, multimedia applications, podcasts, and any other materials that have been designed for use in teaching and learning) that are openly available for use by educators and students, without an accompanying need to pay royalties or license fees" (UNESCO, 2015).

Similarly, the Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development (OECD) defines OERs as: "digitised materials offered freely and openly for educators, students, and self-learners to use and reuse for teaching, learning, and research. OER includes learning content, software tools to develop, use, and distribute content, and implementation resources such as open licences" (OECD, 2007). Following UNESCO's and OECD's findings, the collaborative manifesto "Cape Town Open Education Declaration" was released, which advocated for the free

distribution of publicly funded educational materials (Cape Town Open Education, 2007).

The years 2011-2015 marked the acceleration of development in the OER ecosystem through the involvement of federal governments, particularly led by the OECD (Bliss & Smith, 2017). However, OER awareness among trainers is only gradually improving, as a 2018 survey in the U.S. revealed that 47% of instructors were unfamiliar with OER. Although a significant number of instructors remain unaware of OERs, the percentage has decreased by 19% since 2014, signifying a noteworthy growth in awareness (Southern Alberta Institute of Technology, 2022).

The uptake of Open Educational Resources showed only modest growth during the Covid-19 pandemic, however, Atkinson et al argue that it is crucial to revisit OERs as a sustainable and cost-effective way to resource and deliver education even after the pressure for remote teaching has subsided (Atkinson & Fields, 2023). For a more in-depth exploration of the history of OERs and their application, please find a list of video resources in chapter I.

C. Characteristics of Open Educational Resources

In the preceding chapter, various definitions have been presented and certainly, one is encouraged to formulate their own interpretation as within academic circles, there exists no standardized guideline for this matter.

However, it is crucial, for the purpose of this module's objectives, to establish a distinct and comprehensive set of guidelines outlining the characteristics that will be employed in the identification of Open Educational Resources (OERs).

David Wiley defines OERs with the help of the 5R activities/permissions:

“The term ‘open content’ describes any copyrightable work (traditionally excluding software, which is described by other terms like “open source”) that is licensed in a manner that provides users with free and perpetual permission to engage in the 5R activities:

1. **Retain** — the right to make, own, and control copies of the content (e.g., download, duplicate, store, and manage)
2. **Reuse** — the right to use the content in a wide range of ways (e.g., in a class, in a study group, on a website, in a video)
3. **Revise** — the right to adapt, adjust, modify, or alter the content itself (e.g., translate the content into another language)
4. **Remix** — the right to combine the original or revised content with other open content to create something new (e.g., incorporate the content into a mashup)
5. **Redistribute** — the right to share copies of the original content, your revisions, or your remixes with others (e.g., give a copy of the content to a friend). (Wiley, n.d.)

Based on these principles, an Open Educational Resource should be accessible for all forms of amendment and redistribution.

While sometimes referred to as such, any materials accessed through library's subscription or online catalogues are not considered OERs, as they cannot be amended or redistributed, as shown in the below table:

Material Type	Openly Licensed	Freely Available	Modifiable
Open educational resources	Yes	Yes	Yes
Accessible online resources under all rights reserved copyright	No	Yes	No
Digital materials available through the Library	No	Maybe	No
Print materials available through the Library	No	Maybe	No

Table 1: Comparisons of Learning Resources

(Southern Alberta institute of Technology, 2022)

D. Advantages of Open Educational Resources

Open Educational Resources bring compelling advantages to the forefront of modern education. OERs, accessible to all through digital platforms, have redefined the educational landscape by offering a myriad of benefits. From mitigating financial barriers for learners and institutions to fostering collaborative and adaptable teaching practices, the advantages of OERs extend across various dimensions.

The arguments for **institutional involvement** in OER can be summarized as follows:

- Altruistic argument: Embracing the ethos of sharing knowledge aligns with established academic traditions, asserting that contributing to the collective intellectual wealth is inherently virtuous.
- Financial Utilization of Public Resources: Educational institutions have the opportunity to optimize taxpayers' funds by endorsing the free sharing and reuse of educational resources. This ensures that public investments in education are maximized for the benefit of a wider audience.
- Cost-Efficient Content Development: The practice of sharing and reusing educational materials serves as a pragmatic approach to curbing costs associated with content development. This, in turn, facilitates a more judicious utilization of available resources.
- Enhanced Public Image and Student Attraction: Actively participating in open sharing not only enhances institutional reputation but also serves as a public relations asset, acting as a showcase to attract new students seeking institutions committed to collaborative knowledge exchange.
- Exploration of Innovative Revenue Models: Institutions recognizing the significance of OER involvement acknowledge the need for novel business models and alternative revenue streams. This adaptive approach reflects a commitment to staying abreast of evolving educational paradigms (Huyen, 2006).

The arguments for **individual involvement** in OERs can be summarized as follows:

- Ubiquity of Open Educational Resources (OERs): Open Educational Resources are readily available on a global scale, ensuring accessibility for individuals from diverse backgrounds and locations.
- Cost-Effective Sharing Enabled by Technology: The advent of technology has rendered the sharing of OERs nearly cost-free, providing individuals with an economical means to disseminate and access educational content.
- Adaptability through Digital Nature: Owing to their digital format, OERs possess a malleability that allows for easy modification, catering to a myriad of individual learning needs and preferences.

- **Contributing to the Progress of Knowledge:** Active involvement with OERs serves as a catalyst for advancing human knowledge, fostering a collaborative environment that encourages the continuous evolution of educational materials.
- **Rapid Dissemination with Technological Advancements:** OERs, benefiting from ongoing technological enhancements, surpass traditional print textbooks in reaching learners swiftly, ensuring timely access to educational resources.
- **Significant Savings for Students and Parents:** Utilizing OERs translates to substantial cost savings for both students and parents, offering a financially prudent alternative to traditional educational materials.
- **Fostering Self-Directed Learning:** OERs play a pivotal role in promoting self-directed learning, empowering individuals to take charge of their educational journey and tailor their learning experiences.
- **Global Reach Irrespective of Location:** The reach of OERs extends globally, simultaneously catering to a large number of learners, irrespective of their geographical location, fostering inclusivity in education.
- **Transforming Distant Education Approaches:** OERs have revolutionized the educational landscape for remote students and long-distance learners, offering them a versatile and accessible approach to education.
- **Facilitating Comprehensive Peer Review Processes:** Engaging with OERs allows for an expansive peer review process, enabling a more thorough examination and refinement of educational materials through collaborative efforts.

E. Challenges of Open Educational Resources

The last chapter outlined some of the many advantages and potential of OERs. However, some still express reservations about the drawbacks of OERs, a concern that, while not as prominent as in the past, warrants careful examination.

The following challenges should always be considered when working with OERs:

- **Quality Assurance:** As these resources are subject to real-time edits by various contributors, the information they carry may lack consistency, reliability and accuracy. This poses a challenge to the traditional expectation of authoritative teaching materials, leading faculty members to question the dependability of OERs compared to longstanding trusted sources.
- **Intellectual property:** While the 'fair use' provision traditionally protected faculty when sharing excerpts from copyrighted materials, OERs operate under different principles. The intricacies of Creative Commons licenses, often associated with OERs, remain confusing for many professors. The frequent shift from "All rights reserved" to "Some rights reserved" raises uncertainty, requiring faculty to navigate complex copyright and permission issues.
- **Technological limitations:** Questions arise about the existence of seamless access tools and the quality of shared files. Despite technology's support for OER proliferation, it simultaneously poses challenges, particularly for students with limited internet access or those unable to download required software for remote educational material access. While affecting a small percentage of students, this highlights the persisting digital divides (Roncevic, 2021).
- **Sustainability:** The proliferation of OER initiatives in recent years has intensified competition for funding. Despite certain projects receiving robust institutional support, the predominant reliance on startup funding suggests a potential cessation after an initial period. Consequently, there arises a critical imperative to deliberate on sustainable strategies for these initiatives in the long term (Hysten, 2006).
- **Reinforcement of inequities:** The inherent openness and accessibility of Open Educational Resources (OERs) present a potential avenue for exacerbating systemic injustices within the educational landscape. A prime illustration is the substantial financial burden imposed by the exorbitant costs associated with commercial textbooks. While OERs offer a viable solution to mitigate these economic challenges, it becomes imperative to scrutinize the origins of OERs and the specific types of knowledge they perpetuate. Understanding the provenance of OERs is essential for assessing whose knowledge is being disseminated and determining which perspectives and forms of knowledge are being replicated. In essence, while OERs hold the promise of alleviating economic disparities in education, a

critical examination of their origin is necessary to ensure that they contribute to a more equitable and diverse educational environment (Veletsianos, 2020).

F. Future Trends and Opportunities

As outlined in the chapter on the definition and history, OERs have developed significantly within the last two decades. It is only logical, that the next decades will bring much evolution in the field as well. We suspect that the following areas and challenges will mould the development of OERs in the near future:

Copyright issues as a driver in implementation:

The current copyright regulations and agreements are not in sync with the demands of the digital era, leading to practical challenges and uncertainties in educational practices. This issue becomes more pronounced with the increasing use of digital materials. As legal restrictions and uncertainties intensify, OERs gain attractiveness as a viable alternative. The lack of substantial copyright reforms in the education sector is anticipated to fuel growing interest in OER. Conversely, introducing measures like a general education exception might be expected to reduce the appeal of OER.

Wider dissemination of digital media:

The evolution of Open Educational Resources (OER) perspectives is intricately connected with the digitization of media. Digital platforms facilitate the seamless distribution and manipulation of educational materials. Within the realm of continuing education, the momentum of digitization is not solely attributed to the adoption of E-learning but extends to the provision of work and learning materials during in-person sessions. Notably, there is a growing trend among trainers and educators to eschew traditional printed materials, opting instead to deliver resources in digital formats. While OER can theoretically be applied to analogue materials, the advantages of digital formats, including simplified discovery, copying, modification, and sharing processes, significantly enhance the conditions for the effectiveness of OER initiatives.

Stronger cooperation between educational institutions:

Open-licensed materials are accessible for universal reuse, enabling content developed for one educational domain to be applied in another. This interchangeability occurs at both individual and institutional levels, fostering collaborations between adult education centers and universities. A strategic example is the Hamburg Open Online University, initiated in 2015, where Hamburg universities collaborate under its umbrella to create and publish OER. Utilizing OER removes barriers to cross-domain cooperation, making the creation of OER a potential starting or focal point for collaborative projects.

Establishment of central platforms for OERs:

Creating user-friendly central platforms on the internet is crucial for practitioners in continuing education who regularly produce their own materials. While many are willing to share, a low barrier is essential. Complex individual publication structures and post-release maintenance deter potential OER publishers. Simplifying these processes through accessible central platforms can effectively reduce these barriers (Blees et al., 2015).

Growing education about OERs:

Increasing awareness and education on open resources is crucial to dispel misconceptions about their quality and highlight shared benefits. Despite the common perception that freely available resources may be of lower quality, recent advancements in supporting OERs include valuable teaching aids such as test banks, instructor manuals, and lecture slides (Jhangiani & Biswas-Diener, 2017). Beyond the cost advantages, it is imperative to recognize the broader implications of freely sharing, replicating, and reproducing intellectual knowledge. Academia should acknowledge that students not only gain free, enduring access to course materials but also receive permissions to revise, replicate, and reproduce both content and pedagogy (Bain, 2023).

G. Recommendations

After learning about the background of development, the advantages and challenges, as well as the future trends of OERs, this chapter aims to give you specific recommendations on how to use OERs in your training and give information on how to avoid common pitfalls:

H. Strategies:

Trainers can employ several strategies to effectively implement Open Educational Resources (OER) into their teaching:

Understand OER Principles: Trainers should be able to familiarize themselves with the principles of OER, including the ability to freely use, adapt, and share resources. This understanding forms the foundation for successful integration. Trainers in predictive maintenance can leverage OER principles to freely access, adapt, and share resources related to emerging technologies, such as machine learning algorithm and data analytics used in predictive maintenance. Understanding these principles sets the stage for collaborative learning and resource development within the predictive maintenance community.

Needs Assessment: Conducting a needs assessment helps identify gaps in current predictive maintenance training programs. Trainers can use OER to supplement existing materials, addressing specific learning objectives or emerging trends in the field, ensuring that the curriculum remains up-to-date and relevant. After navigating through the OER material and familiarizing themselves with it, trainers can conduct a needs assessment on the training material. They should be able to record any gaps or complex information that may be misleading, indicating a necessity for amendment or clearer explanation, respectively. Such assessments are a common practice in educational procedures, and trainers are competent enough to carry them out.

Curate OER Repositories: Explore reputable OER repositories such as [MIT OpenCourseWare](#), OpenStax, MERLOT, or OER Commons to discover relevant materials aligned with the predictive maintenance course content. Curation ensures the selection of high-quality and contextually appropriate resources.

Modify and Customize: OER's flexibility allows trainers to customize materials for specific industries, equipment types, or maintenance challenges. Trainers can tailor resources to suit the needs of their students, making the content more applicable to real-world scenarios in predictive maintenance. The combination of needs assessment, literature review, and trainers' expertise allows the modification of the context. The training material on OER is a dynamic process that needs to

align with trainers' individual styles. This stands as another important advantage of OER content compared to the conventional way of teaching, facilitating easier interpretation and modification of the material at any time. This characteristic contributes significant value to the content, ensuring it remains up-to-date.

Provide Attribution: Emphasize the importance of providing proper attribution when using or modifying OER. This not only adheres to licensing requirements but also contributes to the ethos of openness and collaboration.

Promote Collaboration: Encourage collaborative content creation among trainers, sharing experiences and insights about effective OER use. Collaborative efforts can lead to the development of shared resources that benefit a wider community. Several of the OER Repositories offered in the next chapter also foster a community of educators, in which users are highly encouraged to contribute educational materials and modify existing ones. Shared resources can cover case studies, practical applications, and evolving technologies, benefiting a wider community of educators and learners in the field.

Offer Training to Peers: Conducting workshops or training sessions for fellow educators promotes the adoption of OER in predictive maintenance education. Educators can share insights into effective integration, encouraging a culture of openness and collaboration among peers.

Integrate OER Gradually: Trainers can introduce OER gradually into predictive maintenance courses, starting with specific modules or supplementary materials. This approach allows for a smoother transition, enabling both trainers and students to adapt to the new resources.

Leverage Technology: Educational technology platforms can facilitate easy access to and distribution of OER in predictive maintenance courses. Collaborative editing tools can enhance the development of shared resources, fostering an interactive and engaging learning environment.

Assess and Evaluate: Regular assessment of OER impact on student learning outcomes is crucial. Trainers can solicit feedback from students and colleagues to refine and improve the use of OER continually. In a field like predictive maintenance, where technologies and best practices evolve, ongoing evaluation ensures the materials remain current and effective. This can be enhanced by incorporating an additional module on OER containing Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs), addressing either how to use OER functions or common inquiries from students about Predictive Maintenance. The purpose of the FAQ section is to deliver essential information promptly, saving time that would otherwise be spent navigating throughout the entire material.

By incorporating these strategies, trainers can not only seamlessly integrate OER into their teaching but also contribute to the broader culture of open education.

I. Common Pitfalls

To avoid common pitfalls when using Open Educational Resources (OERs), trainers can adopt the following strategies:

Check Licensing and Permissions: Before integrating OER into predictive maintenance courses, trainers should thoroughly review and understand the licensing terms. This ensures compliance with permissions and helps avoid legal issues related to the use of copyrighted material.

Verify Content Quality: Trainers should conduct a rigorous evaluation of the quality of OER content to ensure alignment with the predictive maintenance curriculum. This involves confirming accuracy, relevance, and currency of the resources, promoting a positive impact on learning objectives.

Provide Proper Attribution: Emphasize the importance of providing proper attribution to the original creators of OER materials. Trainers should educate students on the significance of attribution, fostering a culture of respect for intellectual property and collaboration.

Ensure Accessibility: Confirm that the chosen OERs are accessible to all students, including those with disabilities. Accessibility issues can hinder the learning experience for some students, violating the principles of inclusivity.

Avoid Overreliance: While OER is valuable, trainers should avoid overreliance on these resources. Balancing OER with other teaching materials, such as proprietary textbooks and hands-on experiences, ensures a well-rounded educational experience in predictive maintenance.

Regularly Update Resources: OER materials may become outdated, and links may break. Regularly check and update the resources to ensure that students have access to accurate and relevant content.

Assess Cultural Relevance: Consider the cultural relevance of OER materials, ensuring that they resonate with the diverse backgrounds of students. Be mindful of cultural sensitivities to create an inclusive learning environment.

Train Students on OER Use: Provide guidance to predictive maintenance students on effectively using OER, including proper citation practices and an understanding

of licensing terms. This empowers students to responsibly engage with open educational content throughout their studies.

Be Cautious with Third-Party Platforms: When using third-party platforms for OER, be cautious about the platform's terms of service, data privacy policies, and long-term sustainability. Ensure alignment with institutional policies and standards.

Encourage Continuous Professional Development: Trainers should actively engage in continuous professional development to stay informed about changes in the OER landscape. This enables them to adapt to evolving challenges, incorporate new resources, and enhance the overall effectiveness of predictive maintenance courses.

Seek Community Support: Joining OER communities and networks allows trainers in predictive maintenance to share experiences, insights, and best practices with peers. Collaborative engagement provides valuable support in addressing common challenges and fostering a sense of community within the field.

By being vigilant about licensing, content quality, accessibility, and cultural relevance, and by promoting responsible use among students, trainers can navigate potential pitfalls and maximize the benefits of OER integration. Keep these strategies and common pitfalls in mind when completing the webquest of this module.

J. List of OER Repositories

The following collection of OER Repositories is designed to provide an academic and research-oriented exploration of freely accessible educational materials. In the context of predictive maintenance's rapidly evolving technological landscape, these repositories serve as repositories of rigorously vetted resources, encompassing textbooks, analytical modules, and empirical case studies. Within these repositories, educators can discern a wealth of materials aligned with the principles of open access, scholarly collaboration, and the imperative for perpetual learning.

Mason OER Metafinder (MOM):

<https://oer.deepwebaccess.com/oer/desktop/en/search.html>

MERLOT: <https://www.merlot.org/merlot/index.htm>

OER Repositories & Platforms List: <https://oer-obp.pubpub.org/pub/wac0y6kx/release/12>

OER Commons: <https://oercommons.org/>

Open Education Consortium: <https://www.oeconsortium.org/courses/>

OpenStax: <https://openstax.org/>

SkillsCommons: <https://www.skillscommons.org/handle/taaccct/1058>

K. Video resources

For further information, find related videos to the topic:

Open Educational Resources (OER) by UNESCO:

[Open Educational Resources \(OER\) \(youtube.com\)](#)

Open Educational Resources (OER) and innovation: Why OER?

[Open Educational Resources \(OER\) and innovation: Why OER? \(youtube.com\)](#)

EdTech Chats December: Open Education Resources by Open LMS

[EdTech Chats December: Open Education Resources \(youtube.com\)](#)

OER Ted Talk by Katie Gosa

[OER | Katie Gosa | TEDxUTA - YouTube](#)

Open Educational Resources (OER) and Adult Education

[Open Educational Resources \(OER\) and Adult Education \(youtube.com\)](#)

Webinar: Creating and Sharing Open Educational Resources (OER) by National Forum T&L

[Webinar: Creating and Sharing Open Educational Resources \(OER\)](#)

[\(youtube.com\)](#)

A Review of the Effectiveness & Perceptions of Open Educational Resources as compared to textbooks by Research Shorts

[A Review of the Effectiveness & Perceptions of Open Educational Resources As Compared to Textbooks \(youtube.com\)](#)

Open Educational Resources: What and Why by UAlberta Library

[Open Educational Resources: What and Why \(youtube.com\)](#)

Open Educational Resources by University of Groningen:

[Open Educational Resources \(youtube.com\)](#)

Finding and Remixing OER: A Practical Introduction by Open Education
Conference

[Finding And Remixing OER: A Practical Introduction \(youtube.com\)](#)

L. Conclusion

In summary, it is evident that the fusion of educational innovation and technological evolution is imperative for meeting the demands of the dynamic field of predictive maintenance. The journey through the facets of OERs – from their historical roots to current challenges and future prospects – reveals a reservoir of possibilities for transformative education in predictive maintenance.

As predictive maintenance trainers engage with the contents of this guide, the profound impact of OERs on the educational landscape becomes apparent. The inherent adaptability and accessibility of OERs provide an opportunity to enhance training programs, engage learners, and foster collaboration within the predictive maintenance community. The advantages, challenges, and future trends outlined in this guide serve not only as analytical insights but as strategic signposts for trainers navigating this intersection of technology and education.

With an expansive list of repositories and demonstrative videos, this booklet equips trainers with the tools and knowledge needed to embark on this transformative journey. The repositories offer a wealth of vetted resources, ensuring trainers have access to high-quality materials that resonate with the dynamic nature of predictive maintenance.

In the spirit of continuous improvement, the booklet concludes with a set of practical recommendations. These recommendations, spanning from needs assessment to fostering collaboration and leveraging technology, serve as a roadmap for trainers to seamlessly incorporate OERs into their predictive maintenance courses. By following these recommendations, trainers can not only navigate potential pitfalls but also contribute to the broader culture of open education within their field.

In essence, this guide stands not just as an informational resource but as a companion for Predictive Maintenance Trainers embarking on a journey where OERs are not just supplementary tools but integral catalysts for educational excellence. The transformative potential of OERs lies not merely in their adaptability but in their capacity to democratise knowledge, foster innovation, and create a collaborative ecosystem. As the landscape of predictive maintenance continues to evolve, trainers armed with the insights from this guide are poised to lead the way, ensuring that education remains at the forefront of technological advancement. Together, OERs and predictive maintenance trainers forge a path towards a future where knowledge is not confined but freely accessible, adaptable, and ever-evolving.

M. References

- Atkinson, S.P., & Fields, A. (2023). The continued importance of open educational resources (OER). *Journal of Open, Flexible and Distance Learning*, 27(1), 1-4.
- Bain, L. (2023). Open Education resources: Why were they developed and what are the future implications. <https://pressbooks.pub/techcurr2023/chapter/oer/>
- Blees, I., Deimann, M., Seipel, H., Hirschmann, D. & Muuß-Merholz, J. (2015). Whitepaper Open Educational Resources (OER) in Weiterbildung/Erwachsenenbildung
- Bliss, T.J., & Smith, M. (2017). A Brief History of Open Educational Resources. In: Jhangiani, R.S., & Biswas-Diener, R. (eds.) *Open: The Philosophy and Practices that are Revolutionizing Education and Science*. Pp. 9-27.
- Boston Consulting Group. (2013). *The Open Education Resources ecosystem. An evaluation of the OER Movement's current state and its progress toward mainstream adoption.*
- Cape Town Open Education Declaration. Cape Town Declaration. 2007.
- Hylan, J. (2006). Open Educational Resources: Opportunities and Challenges. *Proceedings of Open Education*. 49-63.
- OECD. (2007). *Giving Knowledge for Free: The Emergence of Open educational Resources*. Center for Educational Research and Innovation, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD).
- Southern Alberta institute of Technology. (2022). *Introduction to Open Educational Resources*. <https://openeducationalberta.ca/saitoer/chapter/introduction/>
- Roncevic, M. (2021). *Open Educational Resources: The Story of Change and Evolving Perceptions*. <https://openresearch.community/posts/open-educational-resources-the-story-of-change-and-evolving-perceptions>
- UNESCO/IIEP. (2008). *Open Educational Resources: A Way Forward*. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000157987>
- UNESCO/COL. (2015). *A Basic Guide to Open Educational Resources (OER)*. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000215804>
- Veletsianos, G. (2020). Open educational resources: expanding equity or reflecting and furthering inequities? *Education tech Research Dev* (2021) 69:407-410.

Wiley, D. (2018). Defining OER-Enabled Pedagogy. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*. 19 (4).

Wiley, D. (n.d.). Defining the “Open” in Open Content and Open Educational Resources. <https://opencontent.org/definition>

PreMETS

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training.

Module TN6: Ethical learner analytics [Booklet]

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A. Introduction

In the realm of predictive maintenance, the convergence of advanced technologies and data analytics has transformed the landscape of asset management. As organizations embrace the power of data-driven decision-making, the ethical implications of learner analytics in preventive maintenance have gained substantial significance. This booklet aims to provide comprehensive Ethical Learner Analytics Guidelines tailored specifically for the predictive maintenance field. It navigates the intricate intersection of data analytics, ethical considerations, and the preventive maintenance domain, offering a roadmap for practitioners, professionals, and decision-makers alike.

The implementation of learner analytics for predictive maintenance purposes necessitates a delicate balance between deriving valuable insights from data and upholding ethical principles. Leveraging analytics and machine learning to predict equipment failures, anticipate maintenance needs, and optimize schedules requires a cautious approach to data usage, privacy, and fairness. This booklet is designed to equip professionals in the field with the necessary guidance to navigate this ethical terrain, ensuring that while harnessing the potential of data, they also uphold integrity, transparency, and respect for individuals' rights.

Each section of this booklet delves into critical ethical considerations in learner analytics applied to preventive maintenance. It explores ethical frameworks, data privacy, consent, transparency, and accountability, shedding light on best practices and guidelines crucial for implementing and utilizing learner analytics responsibly in the context of predictive maintenance. By adhering to these ethical principles, organizations can harness the full potential of data analytics while fostering trust, ensuring ethical conduct, and ultimately optimizing the efficiency and effectiveness of preventive maintenance practices.

This booklet serves as a valuable resource, fostering a deeper understanding of the ethical dimensions inherent in utilizing learner analytics for predictive maintenance. It is designed not only to inform but also to inspire thoughtful reflection, ethical decision-making, and the establishment of a responsible and ethical framework for leveraging data in the pursuit of maintenance excellence." At its core, this booklet is designed to navigate the intricate ethical considerations intertwined with data analytics in the context of preventive maintenance. Its goal is to offer a comprehensive roadmap, delving into critical facets such as data collection, learning systems, ethical considerations, bias and fairness, transparency and accountability, regulatory compliance, continuous improvement, and analytic indicators.

Data Collection is a foundational pillar within ethical learner analytics. It encapsulates the judicious handling of data scope, ensuring its quality, relevance,

and accuracy, while also prioritizing consent and privacy in accordance with established ethical norms. Additionally, stringent measures for data security are imperative to fortify against unauthorized access or breaches.

Learning Systems, particularly the integration and deployment of machine learning algorithms, stand as a key focus. The booklet navigates the ethical intricacies surrounding algorithm selection, bias mitigation, and the pivotal aspect of model interpretability for fostering transparency and ensuring accountable decision-making.

Ethical considerations underscore the need for a solid ethical framework. This booklet aims to expound upon various Ethical Considerations, examining established frameworks and principles that guide the ethical use of learner analytics in preventive maintenance. It empowers practitioners to navigate ethical dilemmas and make informed decisions aligning with ethical norms.

Furthermore, addressing Bias and Fairness in analytics models is vital. Detecting and rectifying biases embedded in predictive models ensures fairness and accuracy in decision-making, thereby fostering trust and ethical credibility.

Transparency and Accountability stand as pillars of ethical learner analytics. The booklet advocates for the importance of transparent operations and accountable practices in deploying predictive maintenance strategies.

Moreover, Regulatory Compliance and adherence to industry standards are imperative to ensure ethical data usage and safeguard individuals' rights. The booklet delves into guidelines to navigate the complex regulatory landscape effectively.

Continuous improvement is central to ethical learner analytics. By constantly assessing and refining Analytic Indicators, organizations can drive improvements in maintenance practices while ensuring ethical conduct throughout.

B. Data collection

Ethical learner analytics in preventive maintenance embodies the conscientious sourcing of crucial data from diverse channels, harnessing information from equipment sensors, historical maintenance records, and user inputs. This approach integrates an ethical framework into the very foundation of data collection, acknowledging the significance of responsible data utilization in shaping predictive maintenance strategies.

Data collection is the cornerstone of predictive maintenance strategies. It involves a meticulous process of gathering, storing, and utilizing data pivotal for effective decision-making. The scope of data collection extends to identifying, procuring, and validating relevant information critical for forecasting maintenance requirements. Ethical dimensions are crucial in this process, demanding stringent adherence to principles of consent, privacy, and security. Obtaining explicit consent and protecting individual privacy rights are paramount ethical considerations. Equally essential is ensuring data security to safeguard against unauthorized access, breaches, or mishandling, thereby preserving the integrity and reliability of the collected data.

The primary objective of ethical learner analytics within preventive maintenance is multifaceted. Firstly, it seeks to acquire an in-depth understanding of equipment behaviour by assimilating data streams from various sensors and devices embedded within machinery. This amalgamation of sensor data allows for real-time monitoring of equipment performance, facilitating the identification of normal operating patterns and deviations that might signal potential issues. Moreover, by analysing this equipment behaviour data, predictive maintenance systems can proactively anticipate maintenance needs, enabling pre-emptive actions to prevent potential failures.

Secondly, ethical learner analytics focuses on detecting failure patterns inherent within the collected data. Historical maintenance records serve as invaluable repositories of past equipment failures and maintenance activities. Ethical analysis of this historical data unveils patterns, trends, and recurring issues, allowing practitioners to discern underlying causes contributing to equipment failures. This critical analysis aids in the development of predictive models capable of identifying precursors to failures, thereby enabling timely intervention and mitigating potential disruptions.

Lastly, ethical learner analytics aims to discern specific maintenance and upkeep requirements vital for sustaining equipment health. Through data synthesis and analysis, predictive maintenance systems can forecast specific maintenance needs tailored to each equipment unit. This personalized approach ensures that maintenance interventions are not only timely but also precisely targeted, optimizing resources and minimizing downtime.

The integration of ethical principles into the realm of learner analytics within preventive maintenance is pivotal. It not only enhances the accuracy and effectiveness of predictive maintenance strategies but also ensures responsible data utilization, fostering reliability, safety, and operational continuity.

C. Learning systems

The implementation of learning systems within the domain of preventive maintenance signifies the utilization of cutting-edge technologies like machine learning, artificial intelligence (AI), and analytics. These systems represent a culmination of technological advancements designed to elevate predictive maintenance practices to new heights.

These sophisticated systems are meticulously engineered to process the vast and diverse array of collected data. They serve as the analytical backbone, leveraging advanced algorithms and computational power to analyse, interpret, and derive actionable insights from this data deluge. Machine learning algorithms are the linchpin of predictive maintenance systems, revolutionizing decision-making through data-driven insights. However, their deployment raises significant ethical considerations. While these algorithms empower models to forecast maintenance needs, they may inadvertently inherit biases, affecting the accuracy and fairness of predictions. This section delves into the ethical complexities surrounding the selection, training, and deployment of machine learning algorithms. Their primary function lies in predictive capabilities. These learning systems harness the power of historical data, real-time information, and sensor data to forecast potential equipment failures. By scrutinizing patterns, anomalies, and deviations in equipment behaviour, they forecast the likelihood of failures, allowing for pre-emptive action to avoid unplanned downtime and prevent critical failures. Additionally, these systems offer valuable recommendations for maintenance schedules. By amalgamating historical maintenance records with real-time sensor data, they generate informed schedules, pinpointing optimal times for maintenance interventions. This proactive approach not only minimizes disruptions but also maximizes equipment uptime, optimizing operational efficiency.

Moreover, the learning systems go beyond mere predictions and schedules; they actively optimize maintenance procedures. Through continuous learning and adaptation, these systems refine their recommendations based on evolving data inputs. They facilitate the fine-tuning of maintenance procedures, ensuring that interventions are both timely and precisely targeted. This approach optimizes resource allocation, streamlines maintenance operations, and minimizes unnecessary overhauls, contributing to cost-efficiency and operational excellence.

In essence, the deployment of learning systems within preventive maintenance signifies a paradigm shift in asset management strategies. It emphasizes the criticality of detecting and mitigating biases within these algorithms, emphasizing the need for interpretability to enhance transparency and trust.

By harnessing the power of machine learning, AI, and analytics, these systems predict potential failures, offer tailored maintenance schedules, and optimize

maintenance procedures. This integration of advanced technologies not only enhances the efficiency and accuracy of maintenance strategies but also paves the way for a proactive and data-driven approach to equipment reliability and operational continuity.

D. Ethical considerations

Within the domain of ethical learner analytics, a central tenet revolves around safeguarding the privacy, security, and consent of individuals whose data contributes to the analytical process. This ethical framework underscores a commitment to respecting and preserving the rights and confidentiality of individuals involved in the data lifecycle.

Preserving privacy is foundational. It involves meticulous steps to anonymize personal data, ensuring that sensitive information is detached from identifiable details. Anonymization plays a pivotal role in protecting individuals' identities, shielding them from potential exposure or misuse of their personal information while still allowing for meaningful analysis.

Explicit consent for data usage is paramount. Ethical learner analytics prioritizes obtaining clear and informed consent from individuals before utilizing their data. This ensures that individuals are aware of and agree to how their data will be used, empowering them to make informed decisions about data sharing and usage.

Moreover, stringent security measures form a crucial pillar of ethical data utilization. Maintaining robust measures to safeguard sensitive information against unauthorized access or usage is non-negotiable. Ethical frameworks demand the implementation of state-of-the-art security protocols and encryption mechanisms to fortify data against breaches, ensuring the integrity and confidentiality of the data throughout its lifecycle.

This ethical approach towards learner analytics emphasizes the harmonization of technological advancements with ethical responsibilities. By anonymizing personal data, obtaining explicit consent for usage, and upholding stringent security measures, ethical learner analytics seeks to foster an environment of trust, transparency, and accountability. It ensures that while harnessing the potential of data-driven insights, the rights and privacy of individuals contributing to the data remain safeguarded, reinforcing ethical integrity in the realm of analytics and data utilization.

E. Bias and fairness

In the landscape of ethical learner analytics, a critical imperative is the implementation of robust measures to detect and mitigate biases inherent within algorithms and analytical processes. Biases, whether conscious or unconscious, possess the potential to significantly influence decision-making, thus requiring vigilant scrutiny and rectification.

One of the primary objectives is to conduct rigorous checks to identify biases embedded within algorithms and analytical frameworks. This involves a comprehensive audit and assessment process aimed at uncovering any biases that might skew the outcomes of predictive maintenance strategies. Mitigating these biases becomes pivotal to ensure fair and impartial treatment across various dimensions.

Equitable treatment across diverse equipment types, geographical locations, and user groups stands as a fundamental ethical principle. Preventive maintenance strategies must transcend biases related to specific equipment models, geographic regions, or user demographics. By prioritizing impartiality, the goal is to ensure that recommendations and decisions derived from analytics are universally applicable and not skewed towards or against any particular subset. Furthermore, a key focus lies in averting discriminatory practices that might compromise the integrity of analytical outcomes. This involves a conscientious effort to avoid biases that might result in discriminatory treatment or outcomes. Ethical learner analytics emphasizes the importance of fair and unbiased recommendations, steering clear of any prejudiced or discriminatory influences. Emphasis on identifying and mitigating biases within algorithms and processes underscores the commitment to ethical integrity in predictive maintenance. By ensuring impartial treatment across diverse equipment types, geographical locations, and user groups, the aim is to foster fair and equitable outcomes. Upholding these ethical principles safeguards against discriminatory practices, fortifying the integrity and credibility of analytical results in the realm of preventive maintenance strategies.

F. Transparency and accountability

Transparency emerges as a foundational pillar essential for fostering trust and accountability. Transparency pertains to the clear and comprehensive elucidation of the collection, utilization, and decision-making processes stemming from the data.

The cornerstone of this ethical principle lies in providing transparent explanations elucidating how data is collected, processed, and utilized within the analytics framework. This transparency empowers stakeholders to comprehend the lifecycle of data, from its inception to its utilization in deriving insights. Detailed explanations regarding data sources, methodologies, and analytical approaches

serve to demystify the complexities, enabling stakeholders to grasp the rationale behind the decisions made based on these insights.

The objective of this transparency is to engender trust among stakeholders. By providing clear and understandable explanations, ethical learner analytics aims to build a sense of trustworthiness and reliability in the data-driven decision-making process. Stakeholders, including users, management, and other involved parties, are more likely to trust and accept the outcomes when they are privy to the underlying processes and methodologies employed in the analytics.

Moreover, transparency also ensures accountability for the decisions derived from analytics. When the processes are transparently elucidated, accountability becomes inherent. Stakeholders can scrutinize the methodologies and decisions, holding accountable those responsible for the data collection, analysis, and the resultant actions or recommendations.

Overall, the provision of transparent explanations within ethical learner analytics is crucial. It not only fosters trust among stakeholders by offering insights into the data lifecycle and decision-making processes but also ensures accountability for the decisions derived from analytics. This commitment to transparency fortifies ethical integrity, laying the groundwork for responsible and credible data-driven decision-making within the realm of predictive maintenance.

G. Regulatory compliance

Adherence to pertinent laws and regulations governing data privacy, handling, and utilization forms an indispensable cornerstone of ethical learner analytics. It mandates strict compliance with a spectrum of legal frameworks, including industry standards, national legislations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in Europe, and other regional or global data privacy laws.

Compliance with industry standards is essential. It necessitates aligning data management practices with established norms within the industry. Ethical learner analytics mandates the adoption of best practices and guidelines prevalent in the field to ensure data is collected, processed, and utilized in accordance with industry-specific ethical and legal standards.

National legislations, like the GDPR in Europe, impose rigorous guidelines on data privacy and protection. Ethical learner analytics demands strict adherence to such regulations, ensuring that data management practices comply with the stipulated requirements. This involves obtaining explicit consent for data usage, ensuring data accuracy, and implementing robust security measures to safeguard personal information against breaches.

Implementing specific protocols and practices concerning data management is imperative within ethical learner analytics. This includes defining clear protocols for data collection, storage, processing, and sharing. Ethical data management practices entail establishing stringent protocols and adopting cutting-edge technologies to uphold legal and ethical standards. By adhering to these protocols, organizations can ensure that data handling processes are not only legally compliant but also ethically sound, prioritizing the protection of individual privacy rights and data integrity. Ultimately, the commitment to compliance with relevant laws and regulations forms a foundational element of ethical learner analytics, fostering responsible and lawful data utilization within the realm of predictive maintenance.

H. Continuous improvement

A commitment to continual improvement within the realm of preventive maintenance analytics is fundamental to ethical learner analytics. This commitment involves a proactive approach towards the ongoing enhancement of analytics models and systems, encompassing a spectrum of strategies aimed at refining algorithms, improving accuracy, boosting efficiency, and consistently elevating ethical considerations.

Regular assessments, audits, and feedback mechanisms serve as pivotal tools in this commitment. These processes facilitate the continual refinement of algorithms and analytics models. By subjecting the systems to regular evaluations, practitioners can identify areas for improvement, rectify shortcomings, and enhance the accuracy and efficacy of predictive maintenance strategies. Audits further ensure that ethical considerations remain paramount within the evolving analytics frameworks, emphasizing the importance of ethical integrity in decision-making processes.

Continuous feedback loops play a crucial role in this commitment to ongoing enhancement. Stakeholder feedback, insights derived from data analysis, and assessments of past performances feed into this iterative process of improvement. This iterative approach enables the identification of potential areas for enhancement, allowing for the fine-tuning of algorithms and models in response to evolving data landscapes and changing maintenance needs.

The ultimate goal of this commitment to ongoing enhancement is multifaceted. It aims to refine algorithms, ensuring their accuracy and reliability in predicting maintenance needs. Moreover, it strives to boost the efficiency of predictive maintenance strategies, enabling timely interventions and minimizing operational disruptions. Additionally, by consistently elevating ethical considerations, this commitment ensures that ethical integrity remains embedded within the fabric of

preventive maintenance analytics, guiding decision-making processes towards responsible and accountable actions.

In conclusion, the commitment to ongoing enhancement in preventive maintenance analytics signifies a dedication to continual improvement. Through regular assessments, audits, and feedback mechanisms, practitioners strive to refine algorithms, enhance accuracy, boost efficiency, and perpetually elevate ethical considerations. This commitment embodies a proactive approach aimed at optimizing predictive maintenance strategies while upholding ethical integrity within the realm of learner analytics.

I. Analytic indicators

Analytic indicators, the cornerstone of predictive maintenance, serve as invaluable tools providing comprehensive insights into equipment performance and maintenance needs. These indicators encompass a diverse array of metrics, from equipment health indices to performance benchmarks, offering a holistic view of machinery conditions and operational efficiency. Understanding and harnessing these analytic indicators are pivotal in driving enhancements within maintenance strategies. By comprehending the nuances of these indicators, practitioners gain the ability to discern subtle patterns, identify deviations from normal operations, and predict potential failures or maintenance requirements.

Moreover, the effective utilization of these indicators plays a transformative role in optimizing maintenance strategies. These indicators act as guideposts, directing attention to specific areas requiring immediate intervention or proactive maintenance. By leveraging insights gleaned from these indicators, practitioners can transition from reactive to proactive maintenance paradigms, thus minimizing downtime, optimizing resource allocation, and enhancing operational efficiency. Analytic indicators pave the way for data-driven decision-making within the realm of preventive maintenance. Their utilization empowers practitioners to make informed and strategic decisions, allowing for precise and targeted interventions tailored to equipment-specific needs. These indicators not only facilitate the identification of potential issues but also aid in devising tailored maintenance schedules and optimizing the allocation of resources.

In essence, analytic indicators represent a reservoir of actionable insights crucial for predictive maintenance. By comprehending their significance and utilizing them effectively, practitioners can drive substantial improvements in maintenance strategies, fostering reliability, operational continuity, and cost-effectiveness within industrial operations.

J. Conclusions

The culmination of ethical learner analytics within the realm of preventive maintenance encapsulates a profound evolution in data-driven strategies, fortified by ethical integrity and a commitment to excellence. This comprehensive booklet traverses the multifaceted landscape of ethical learner analytics, illuminating the core principles, methodologies, and imperatives crucial for shaping the future of predictive maintenance.

Throughout these pages, the booklet expounds upon the critical facets ingrained within ethical learner analytics. It underscores the pivotal role of data collection, learning systems, ethical considerations, bias mitigation, transparency, regulatory compliance, continuous improvement, and the significance of analytic indicators. Each section delves into the intricate tapestry of ethical analytics, elucidating its impact on maintenance strategies while balancing technological advancements with ethical responsibilities.

Ethical learner analytics isn't just about harnessing data; it's a commitment to preserving privacy, ensuring fairness, transparency, and compliance with laws and regulations. It's about proactively mitigating biases, fostering trust, and continually refining predictive maintenance models to drive efficiency, reliability, and operational continuity.

As industries navigate the complex intersections of technology, data, and ethical considerations, this booklet stands as a guiding compass, offering insights, principles, and actionable strategies. It echoes the ethos of ethical learner analytics—paving the way for responsible, informed, and data-driven decision-making that upholds ethical standards while optimizing preventive maintenance practices.

In essence, the booklet serves as a blueprint, advocating for an ethical paradigm shift in predictive maintenance. It calls upon practitioners, industry leaders, and stakeholders to embrace the transformative potential of ethical learner analytics, fostering a future where data-driven strategies merge seamlessly with ethical responsibilities, driving sustainable, efficient, and reliable maintenance practices.

K. References

- Keleko, Aurelien Teguede, et al. "Artificial intelligence and real-time predictive maintenance in industry 4.0: a bibliometric analysis." *AI and Ethics* 2.4 (2022): 553-577.
- Downes, Stephen. "Ethical codes and learning analytics." *European Distance and E-Learning Network (EDEN) Conference Proceedings*. No. 1. European Distance and E-Learning Network, 2020.
- Roberts, Lynne D., Vanessa Chang, and David Gibson. "Ethical considerations in adopting a university-and system-wide approach to data and learning analytics." *Big data and learning analytics in higher education: Current theory and practice* (2017): 89-108.
- Garay Gallastegui, Luis Miguel, and Ricardo Francisco Reier Forradellas. "Business methodology for the application in university environments of predictive machine learning models based on an ethical taxonomy of the student's digital twin." *Administrative Sciences* 11.4 (2021): 118.
- Prinsloo, Paul, and Sharon Slade. "An evaluation of policy frameworks for addressing ethical considerations in learning analytics." *Proceedings of the third international conference on learning analytics and knowledge*. 2013.
- Çınar, Zeki Murat, et al. "Machine learning in predictive maintenance towards sustainable smart manufacturing in industry 4.0." *Sustainability* 12.19 (2020): 8211.
- Slade, Sharon, and Alan Tait. "Global guidelines: Ethics in learning analytics." (2019): 2-16.
- Ifenthaler, Dirk, and Jane Yin-Kim Yau. "Higher education stakeholders' views on learning analytics policy recommendations for supporting study success." *International Journal of Learning Analytics and Artificial Intelligence for Education: iJAI* 1.1 (2019): 28-42.
- Leitner, Philipp, Markus Ebner, and Martin Ebner. "Learning analytics challenges to overcome in higher education institutions." *Utilizing learning analytics to support study success* (2019): 91-104.
- Lee, Sang M., DonHee Lee, and Youn Sung Kim. "The quality management ecosystem for predictive maintenance in the Industry 4.0 era." *International Journal of Quality Innovation* 5 (2019): 1-11.
- Lawrence, Joan, and Pavol Durana. "Artificial Intelligence-driven Big Data Analytics, Predictive Maintenance Systems, and Internet of Thingsbased

Real-Time Production Logistics in Sustainable Industry 4.0 Wireless Networks." *Journal of Self-Governance & Management Economics* 9.4 (2021).

Wellsandt, Stefan, et al. "Hybrid-augmented intelligence in predictive maintenance with digital intelligent assistants." *Annual Reviews in Control* 53 (2022): 382-390.

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PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training

Module TN7: Microcredential systems and skill certification
[Booklet]

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A. Introduction

In June 2022, the European Union's Council took a significant step by endorsing a Recommendation, proposed in May the same year, focused on establishing a unified European framework for micro-credentials, aimed at fostering lifelong learning and enhancing employability. This Recommendation is designed to facilitate the creation, implementation, and acknowledgment of micro-credentials across diverse institutions, businesses, sectors, and geographical boundaries.

The cultivation of a robust culture of lifelong learning is imperative for equipping individuals with the knowledge, skills, and competences necessary for personal and professional flourishing.

Micro-credentials play a pivotal role in certifying the outcomes of brief learning experiences, such as short courses or training sessions, providing a versatile and targeted means for individuals to acquire the knowledge and competences essential for their ongoing personal and professional advancement.

The rapid proliferation of shorter learning formats, like micro-credentials, is a global phenomenon, with Europe witnessing a surge in such opportunities. Offered by a diverse array of public and private providers in response to the growing demand for more adaptable and learner-centric educational and training approaches, these opportunities have the potential to extend education and training access to a broader spectrum of learners, including those from disadvantaged and vulnerable groups.

However, the realization of the full potential of micro-credentials hinges on the establishment of common standards ensuring their quality, transparency, cross-border comparability, recognition, and portability. Without such standards, the transformative impact of micro-credentials may be hindered.

B. Micro-credential Frameworks

European businesses and employers grapple with a shortage of relevant skills in the labor market, amplified by evolving work structures and changing skill requirements due to digital and green transitions. In line with Council Decision (EU) 2021/1868, Member States aim to develop a coordinated strategy, focusing on a skilled and adaptable workforce and future-oriented labor markets.

Continuous upskilling and reskilling are crucial for workers to navigate their current roles or transition to new opportunities, particularly in the green and digital sectors. The European Pillar of Social Rights emphasizes the right to quality education and timely assistance for improved employment prospects. Micro-credentials, highlighted in the European Pillar of Social Rights Action Plan, are recognized as innovative tools to facilitate flexible learning pathways and support workers.

Micro-credentials play a pivotal role in achieving EU's 2030 targets, aiming for 60% of adults participating in training annually and an employment rate of at least 78%. Aligned with the EASE Recommendation post-COVID-19, micro-credentials are part of a broader strategy for job-rich recovery. The European Skills Agenda introduces a European approach to micro-credentials, focusing on quality, transparency, and uptake across the EU.

Individual learning accounts, another initiative, leverage micro-credentials to bridge gaps in access to education and training. The Commission's commitment to a European approach aligns with the goal of expanding learning opportunities and reinforcing the role of higher education and vocational education and training (VET) institutions in lifelong learning.

Council recommendations and resolutions, such as the one on VET and the strategic framework for education and training, underscore the exploration of micro-credentials to enhance competitiveness, fairness, and resilience. The European Universities initiative recognizes the potential of micro-credentials to accommodate non-traditional learners, foster flexibility, and support access to higher education.

In the Rome Communiqué, Ministers for Education in the European Higher Education Area commit to diversifying learning offers, with a focus on smaller units of learning. This commitment acknowledges the value of micro-credentials in helping learners develop essential skills at different life stages. The ongoing cooperation under the Bologna Process explores the definition, development, and recognition of these smaller, flexible units, including micro-credentials, through common tools.

Micro-credentials stand as a valuable tool to support the professional development and mobility of workers, especially those engaged in non-standard forms of work like the platform economy. These workers, often facing barriers to training due to their employment status, can benefit from the accessibility offered by micro-credentials.

In the broader policy context, micro-credentials have the potential to actively contribute to EU initiatives driving digital and green transitions. Specifically, they align with the goals outlined in the Digital Education Action Plan 2021-2027, providing flexible learning opportunities for digital skills. Additionally, micro-credentials can play a crucial role in achieving the targets set by the '2030 Digital Compass' plan, aiming for a digitally skilled population and highly skilled digital professionals in Europe by 2030. Furthermore, micro-credentials can contribute to the objectives of the European Green Deal, supporting the transformation of Europe's economy and society towards sustainability.

The Council Recommendation on the European Qualifications Framework (EQF) emphasizes the EQF as a common reference framework for comparing different qualification systems and levels. Micro-credentials, when included in national qualifications frameworks, can become part of this reference framework, promoting transparency, portability, and comparability.

In alignment with the 2012 Council Recommendation on the validation of non-formal and informal learning, Member States were encouraged to establish arrangements for validating such learning by 2018. These arrangements facilitate the validation of acquired knowledge, skills, and competences, potentially leading to full or partial qualifications. The 2020 evaluation of this recommendation highlighted the need for further development of links between validation and micro-credentials.

Decision (EU) 2018/646 establishes a common framework for Europass, offering web-based tools for managing careers and lifelong learning. These tools, equipped with authentication services for credentials, enhance the portability of micro-credentials, providing individuals with a robust means of showcasing their skills and qualifications.

C. Objectives and Scope of European Standards for Micro-Credentials

Member States are encouraged to embrace a unified European approach to micro-credentials, driven by multifaceted objectives. Firstly, the aim is to empower individuals to acquire, update, and enhance their knowledge, skills, and competences, ensuring their readiness for the evolving labor market, societal changes, and just transitions to the green and digital economy. This approach seeks to enable individuals to navigate current and future challenges, promoting a socially fair recovery.

Secondly, they are urged to facilitate the preparedness of micro-credential providers, emphasizing the enhancement of quality, transparency, accessibility, and flexibility in learning offerings. This, in turn, enables individuals to shape personalized learning and career pathways, aligning with the dynamic requirements of the contemporary landscape.

Furthermore, the recommended European approach seeks to foster inclusiveness, access, and equal opportunities, contributing to the overarching goals of resilience, social fairness, and prosperity for all. In the face of demographic and societal changes and throughout economic cycles, micro-credentials are envisioned as a tool to promote a more equitable and accessible learning environment.

It is advised to judiciously incorporate micro-credentials into their educational landscape, leveraging them as a strategic tool to strengthen and complement existing learning opportunities. The goal is to increase overall participation in lifelong learning, aligning with the European Pillar of Social Rights Action Plan and the target of achieving 60% participation of all adults in training annually. This aligns with the aspirations outlined in the Council Resolution on a new European agenda for adult learning 2021-2030, as embraced by EU leaders.

Micro-credentials are recognized as a valuable complement to education, training, lifelong learning, and employability ecosystems. The measures outlined in the Recommendation⁶ are aimed at strengthening opportunities for learning and employability without disrupting initial, higher education, vocational education and training (VET) systems, and without undermining and replacing existing qualifications and degrees. The measures recommend the establishment of a common European approach to the ongoing and emerging provision of micro-credentials in the European Union. This approach sets out a definition and guidance for the design, issuance, and description of micro-credentials to improve their quality and transparency and facilitate their uptake. It is designed to enhance

⁶ <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-9237-2022-INIT/en/pdf>

the learning landscape without overshadowing existing structures but rather providing a complementary and enriching dimension.

D. Definition and Elements of European Standards for Micro-Credentials

In order to adopt the micro-credential system, the European Parliament has defined the micro-credential framework in the following ways:

The term '**Micro-credential**' represents a documented record of learning outcomes obtained by a learner through concise learning program. These outcomes undergo assessment based on transparent and precisely defined criteria. The learning process leading to attainment of micro-credentials are intentionally crafted to equip the learner with specific knowledge, skills, and competences addressing societal, personal, cultural, or labour market needs. Micro-credentials are shareable and portable, either as standalone credentials or integrated into larger qualifications. They adhere to quality assurance principles aligned with agreed-upon standards within the relevant sector or area of activity.

Providers of micro-credentials are educational and training institutions, workers and employers, employers and industry, civil society organizations, public employment services, regional and national authorities, and other entities involved in designing, delivering, and issuing micro-credentials for formal, non-formal, and informal learning.

Types of learning settings⁷:

Formal learning characterizes learning transpiring in an organized and structured environment exclusively dedicated to learning, leading to the attainment of a qualification, typically in the form of a certificate or diploma. This encompasses systems of general education, initial, continuing, and tertiary vocational education and training, as well as higher education.

On the other hand, **non-formal learning** describes learning transpiring outside formal education and training through planned activities with defined learning objectives and allocated learning time, with some form of learning support present.

Informal learning, therefore, denotes learning resulting from daily activities and experiences that lack organization or structure in terms of objectives, time, or

⁷ Regulation (EU) 2021/817 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2021 establishing Erasmus+: the Union Programme for education and training, youth and sport and repealing Regulation (EU) No 1288/2013, OJ L 189, 28.05.2021, p. 1.

learning support. While it does not automatically result in a micro-credential, it can be considered within validation arrangements that identify, document, assess, and/or certify individual learning outcomes.

The main characteristics of micro-credentials, defined by the European Parliament, are:

- **Portability** - signifies the ability of a credential-holder to store micro-credentials in a system of their choosing, share the credential with a designated party (whether national or transnational), and ensure all parties involved can comprehend the content and verify the authenticity of the credentials. This facilitates portability within and between education and training sectors, the labor market, and across countries.
- **Stackability** - refers to the potential to combine various micro-credentials in a logical progression. Decisions to 'stack' or combine credentials rest with the receiving organization (e.g., educational and training institutions, employers, etc.) in accordance with their practices, supporting the learner's goals and needs.
- **Assessment** - encompasses the processes or methods used to evaluate, measure, and eventually describe the learning outcomes acquired by individuals through formal, non-formal, or informal settings. Assessment is conducted by the provider or other recognized assessment entities.

However, elements used to describe micro-credentials consist of a few mandatory and optional elements described in the table as such:

Mandatory elements:	
Learner identification	Micro-credential Title
County/Region of the Issuer	Awarding bodies
Date of Issuing	Learning outcomes
Workload needed to achieve the outcome (ECTS)	Level of the learning process leading to a learning outcome (e.g., European Qualifications Framework, Qualifications Frameworks in the European Higher Education Area, etc) if applicable.
Assessment type	Form of participation
Type of QA used to support the micro-credential	
Optional Elements:	
Requirements for enrollment in the learning activity	Monitoring and verification of identity during assessment
Attained grade	Options for integration/stackability
Additional details	

E. Principles governing the design and issuance of micro-credentials in Europe

The following **10 principles** describe what micro-credentials are about and provide advice to Member States, public authorities, and providers on how to create and issue them, along with systems for managing micro-credentials. These principles emphasize the important aspects of the European approach to micro-credentials that contribute to building trust and maintaining quality. They are versatile and can be applied in any field or industry when suitable.

1. **Quality:** Micro-credentials undergo both internal and external quality assurance processes conducted by the system generating them, such as the educational, training, or labour market environment in which the micro-credential is conceived and offered. These quality assurance procedures must be tailored to the specific purpose, well-documented, accessible, and aligned with the needs and expectations of learners and stakeholders. External quality assurance primarily focuses on evaluating providers, rather than individual courses, and the efficacy of their internal quality assurance protocols.
2. **Transparency:** Micro-credentials are designed to be measurable, comparable, and comprehensible, providing clear information regarding learning outcomes, workload, content, level, and the learning offering as deemed relevant. Higher education institutions are encouraged to utilize the ECTS. This helps demonstrate the notional workload necessary to achieve the micro-credential's learning outcomes. Providers not using ECTS may employ alternative systems or types of information, ensuring compliance with the principles in Annex V to the EQF Recommendation.
3. **Relevance:** Micro-credentials are to be crafted and granted as specific, focused learning accomplishments, with corresponding learning opportunities subject to regular updates to address identified learning needs. Encouragement is given for collaboration among education and training organizations, employers, social partners, other providers, and users of micro-credentials to enhance the relevance of these credentials in the labour market.
4. **Valid Assessment:** The assessment of micro-credential learning outcomes is conducted based on clear and transparent criteria.
5. **Learning Pathways:** Micro-credentials are created and issued to facilitate flexible learning journeys, offering the opportunity to validate, recognize, and 'stack' micro-credentials obtained from different systems. It's important to note that stacking does not automatically grant entitlement to a qualification or degree. Such determinations are made by regional and

national authorities or institutions in accordance with their awarding processes. They can be earned either from a specific course leading to a micro-credential or through the evaluation of outcomes resulting from non-formal and informal learning.

6. **Recognition:** Micro-credentials possess a distinct signaling value by clearly indicating the learning outcomes for smaller learning modules. Recognition of these credentials opens the door to a broader array of such learning experiences in a standardized manner across the European Union. When formal education providers issue micro-credentials, they aim for recognition whenever possible, using standard procedures commonly used for acknowledging foreign qualifications and learning experiences abroad. It's important to note that this doesn't affect the right of authorities to set recognition processes or verify the authenticity of documents.
7. **Portable:** Micro-credentials belong to the credential-holder, which is the learner, and can be conveniently stored and shared by them. This sharing includes secure digital wallets like Europass, in accordance with the GDPR. The data storage infrastructure adheres to open standards and data models, ensuring interoperability and smooth data exchange, while also facilitating easy verification of data authenticity.
8. **Learner-centred:** Micro-credentials are crafted to cater to the specific needs of the intended group of learners. The involvement of learners in both internal and external quality assurance processes is actively encouraged, with their feedback considered a crucial component for the ongoing enhancement of the micro-credential.
9. **Authentic:** Micro-credentials provide ample information to verify the identity of the credential-holder (learner), the legal identity of the issuer, and the date and place of issuance of the micro-credential.
10. **Information and guidance:** Micro-credentials should be integrated into lifelong learning guidance services, ensuring its dissemination to a wide range of learners in an inclusive manner. This approach supports informed decision-making for education, training, and career choices across diverse learner groups.

F. Ecosystem Development for Micro-Credentials

All Member States are advised to actively promote the continuous growth and emergence of micro-credentials within formal learning environments. This includes encouraging higher education institutions to explore the role of micro-credentials in providing diverse learning opportunities, particularly by enhancing an attractive, accessible, inclusive, and learner-centered offering of lifelong learning activities. They are also encouraged to support vocational education and training institutions, as well as other VET providers, in exploring the role of micro-credentials in ongoing vocational education and training. This involves supporting initiatives such as the activities of VET Centres of Vocational Excellence, especially in the context of upskilling and reskilling adults.

In addition, considering the provision of public funding, based on national circumstances, for the development and delivery of small-scale education and training activities leading to micro-credentials across all levels of education and training is also one of the recommendations for the Member States. Recognizing institutional autonomy is crucial to allowing for diversity and creativity in this regard. Member States are also recommended, where suitable, to foster the development of micro-credentials within non-formal and informal learning settings. This involves:

1. Supporting the design and issuance of micro-credentials by providers such as companies, social partners, civil society organizations, local authorities, community centers, professional associations, research and innovation organizations, and private providers. Diverse funding sources should be promoted.
2. Encouraging the creation of micro-credentials designed and agreed upon through social dialogue between employers' and workers' representatives.
3. Considering adjustments to procedures for the recognition of prior learning and the validation of non-formal and informal learning to allow for the awarding of micro-credentials.

Member States are further encouraged, as appropriate, to bolster the quality and transparency of micro-credentials, including:

1. Applying, adapting, and developing quality assurance mechanisms for micro-credentials issued by various providers, utilizing existing mechanisms where feasible.
2. Supporting the use of 'skills-intelligence' systems to analyze labor market needs and demographic changes, identifying any requirements to develop or update micro-credentials.

3. Urging providers to publish catalogs of the micro-credentials they offer, including their policy on recognizing micro-credentials issued by other providers.
4. Integrating micro-credentials into national qualifications frameworks and systems. Decisions regarding the integration of micro-credentials into regional and national frameworks or systems are made by national authorities or institutions in accordance with national circumstances.

This collaborative approach, emphasizing experimentation, cooperation, governance, and partnerships, is essential for identifying micro-credential needs, co-developing them, and keeping them updated. It also plays a pivotal role in assessing the impact on upskilling, reskilling, lifelong learning, and career development.

In maximizing the impact of micro-credentials, Member States are encouraged to seamlessly integrate them into education and training systems, aligning with skills policies. This involves fostering inclusive and learner-centered offerings, supporting flexible learning pathways, and exploring their role in the digital and green transitions.

To achieve this integration, it is recommended to include micro-credential offerings in comprehensive catalogues of education and training opportunities. Furthermore, micro-credentials should be utilized to improve access to education for all learners, especially those from disadvantaged and vulnerable groups.

The application of micro-credentials as a complement or integration into degree programs is suggested, emphasizing their potential to enhance digital skills and contribute to sustainable development. Also advised is to promote the use of micro-credentials within their knowledge and innovation ecosystems to boost their positive impact on the local and regional economy.

Additionally, fostering an understanding of micro-credentials is crucial, urging continuous professional development for educators, trainers, guidance counsellors, and related staff. Their use can extend to challenging stereotypes and biases in educational practices, particularly within the European Education Area.

In parallel, they are also encouraged to seamlessly integrate micro-credentials into employment and labour market policies. This entails addressing skills mismatches, upskilling, and reskilling workers, especially in the context of digital and green transitions. Recognized training opportunities linked to individual learning accounts should include pathways leading to micro-credentials.

Moreover, micro-credentials can play a role in supporting self-employed and non-standard workers, including those engaged in platform work and SMEs. Targeted

initiatives are recommended to motivate disadvantaged and vulnerable groups to re-enter the labour market or continue employment.

Considering the evolving employment landscape post-COVID-19, Member States are encouraged to explore the role of micro-credentials in supporting effective active employment measures. Additionally, micro-credentials can be a valuable tool for professional development and meeting mandatory upskilling and reskilling requirements in various jobs and sectors.

G. Conclusion

In summary, the lack of a shared definition and standards for micro-credentials in Europe is currently hindering their widespread understanding and use. The European Union's Recommendation aims to build trust in micro-credentials across Europe, benefiting both providers and learners, as was also showcased in this booklet. Micro-credentials, targeting learning experiences, offer a way for individuals to acquire specific knowledge and skills to meet changing societal and job market needs.

It's important to note that they don't replace traditional qualifications but provide an additional way for individuals to address skill gaps. Micro-credentials can work alongside existing qualifications, without undermining the importance of full-degree programs in initial education and training. They can be offered by various providers in different learning settings, including formal, non-formal, and informal environments. This booklet aimed to provide a brief overview of its origins, framework, and objectives.

H. References

- Tamoliune G, Greenspon R, Tereseviciene M, Volungeviciene A, Trepule E and Dauksiene E (2023) Exploring the potential of micro-credentials: A systematic literature review. *Front. Educ.* 7:1006811. doi: 10.3389/feduc.2022.1006811
- Varadarajan, S., Koh, J.H.L. & Daniel, B.K. A systematic review of the opportunities and challenges of micro-credentials for multiple stakeholders: learners, employers, higher education institutions and government. *Int J Educ Technol High Educ* 20, 13 (2023).
- Orman, R., Şimşek, E. and Kozak Çakır, M.A. (2023), "Micro-credentials and reflections on higher education", *Higher Education Evaluation and Development*, Vol. 17 No. 2, pp. 96-112.
- Leesa Wheelahan & Gavin Moodie (2021) Analysing micro-credentials in higher education: a Bernsteinian analysis, *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 53:2, 212-228, DOI: 10.1080/00220272.2021.1887358
- Tamoliune, Giedre & Greenspon, Rasa & Tereseviciene, Margarita & Volungeviciene, Airina & Trepule, Elena & Dauksiene, Estela. (2023). Exploring the potential of micro-credentials: A systematic literature review. *Frontiers in Education*. 7. 10.3389/feduc.2022.1006811.
- Oliver, B. (2021). Micro-credentials: A learner value framework: Provocation. *Journal of Teaching and Learning for Graduate Employability*, 12(1), 48–51.
- Rory McGreal, Wayne Mackintosh, Glenda Cox, and Don Olcott, Jr., Bridging the Gap: Micro-credentials for Development UNESCO Chairs Policy Brief Form - Under the III World Higher Education Conference (WHEC 2021) Type: Collective X, *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning* Volume 23, Number 3, 2022
- Iniesto, Francisco & Ferguson, Rebecca & Weller, Martin & Farrow, Robert & Pitt, Rebecca. (2022). Introducing A Reflective Framework for the Assessment and Recognition of Microcredentials. *The Open/Technology in Education, Society, and Scholarship Association Journal*. 2. 1-24.
doi: [10.18357/otessaj.2022.2.2.37](https://doi.org/10.18357/otessaj.2022.2.2.37)
- A European approach to micro-credentials (2022). European Education Area. (n.d.). Education.ec.europa.eu. <https://education.ec.europa.eu/education-levels/higher-education/micro-credentials#:~:text=Micro%2Dcredentials%20certify%20the%20learning>

Wang, Libing, Micro-credentials: An important part of a bigger ecosystem. (2023). Unesco.org. https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/micro-credentials-important-part-bigger-ecosystem?TSPD_101_R0=080713870fab2000c3c10dc18800f37ee7694f45ae100b69de6d8d181560ccfd016aea3fcc9c2c08294f35d9143000110ff12cb83d25ce3204c1388a2f52e00d44d5d4f72d8385898d4ee439e2e35cf2d6684a42912cbc07f6b03d1dcdbb93

PreMETS

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training

**Module TN8: (Re)use existing infrastructures and learning
resources
[Booklet]**

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A. Introduction

In an era where sustainability and efficiency are paramount, harnessing the full potential of existing infrastructures and learning resources has become not only a necessity but also a pathway to innovation.

Technology can be a powerful tool for transforming learning. It can help affirm and advance relationships between educators, trainers, and learners, reinvent approaches of learning and collaboration, shrink long-standing equity and accessibility gaps, and adapt learning experiences to meet the needs of all learners. In this booklet the transformative power of repurposing is explored and leveraging existing infrastructures in order to create dynamic and resilient educational environments.

In the following chapters, various strategies, methodologies, and tools are analyzed aiming at maximizing the potential of existing infrastructures and learning resources. From the renowned CRAAP Test for evaluating sources to the transformative power of Open Educational Resources (OER), each section offers invaluable insights and practical tips for educators and learners.

B. Evaluating existing resources and materials – CRAAP TEST

The Internet offers a wealth of materials that can be reused and adapted to your needs. More information about open learning sources can be found below. However, we all know that the availability of materials does not determine their content value. Each source should be thoroughly evaluated before deciding to use it for one's own purposes.

There are several tools that can support such an evaluation. One of the most widespread is CRAAP test. CRAAP is an acronym for Currency, Relevance, Authority, Accuracy, and Purpose. By employing the test while evaluating sources, a researcher can reduce the likelihood of using unreliable information. The CRAAP test was developed by Sarah Blakeslee and her team of librarians at California State University, Chico (CSU Chico), and was primarily used by higher education librarians at universities. Blakeslee was frustrated that she could not remember the criteria for looking up different sources. After much thought, she came up with the acronym. She wanted to give students an easier way to determine what sources are credible. It is one of various approaches to source criticism. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/CRAAP_test)

The various elements of the test are explained below. (Blakeslee,2004)

C for currency

The first step in determining whether a source is reliable is to check its currency. Currency means that the information found is the most recent. Timeliness means that the information found is the most recent. These questions are important because they help point out the latest trends in information, and also show the constant changes in research that are spreading rapidly with the development of technology now and in the future. If the source is from a website, links to it must work. Sample questions to be asked when evaluation currency:

- When was the information published or posted? •
- Has the information been revised or updated? •
- Does your topic require current information, or will older sources work as well?
- Are the links functional?

R for Relevance

Looking at the sources, the relevance of the information will have an impact on a well-conducted study. There are a huge number of topics and increasing access to information. Therefore, relevance of information helps the audience know what they are looking for. It is also important to check that the data is at the right level of understanding, that is, the degree cannot be too elementary or advanced for the

needs. Because of the variety of sources, teachers can make every effort to keep an open mind about using sources. Moreover, they should decide whether they feel comfortable enough to cite a source.

The sample questions include:

- Does the information relate to your topic or answer your question?
- Who is the intended audience?
- Is the information at an appropriate level (i.e. not too elementary or advanced for your needs)?
- Have you looked at a variety of sources before determining this is one you will use?
- Would you be comfortable using this source for a research paper?

A for Authority

It is essential to check who the author, publisher or sponsor is before trusting the information. The author's level of education and connections are important because they can help readers know if the author is qualified to write about the topic. There should also be contact information for the publisher or author. The authority of the source helps to know that the information can be used and trusted in the right way. Authority in citing a source establishes a line of trust between the reader and the author of the work.

Questions to be asked could be as follows:

- Who is the author/publisher/source/sponsor?
- What are the author's credentials or organizational affiliations?
- Is the author qualified to write on the topic?
- Is there contact information, such as a publisher or email address?
- Does the URL reveal anything about the author or source?

A for Accuracy

Emphasizing the credibility of sources, the accuracy of the content in the source must be linked to the origin. Evidence must support the information presented to the audience. Evidence may include findings, observations or field notes. The report must be verified or refereed. It must be verifiable from another source or common knowledge. The language used in the source must be unbiased or free of emotion, due to its use for fact-finding. The content in the source should be free of spelling, grammatical or typographical errors.

Questions could be the following:

- Where does the information come from?
- Is the information supported by evidence?
- Has the information been reviewed or refereed?
- Can you verify any of the information in another source or from personal knowledge?

- Does the language or tone seem unbiased and free of emotion?
- Are there spelling, grammar or typographical errors?

P for Purpose

The purpose of sources helps readers figure out if the information they are looking for is relevant to their goals. Questions that arise when looking for a purpose include informing, teaching, selling, entertaining, researching and even your own goals. In addition, the author's intentions should be clear. Certain aspects should be considered, whether the information provided is fact, opinion or propaganda, as well as political, personal, religious or ideological biases.

Examples of questions:

- What is the purpose of the information? Is it to inform, teach, sell, entertain or persuade?
- Do the authors/sponsors make their intentions or purpose clear?
- Is the information fact, opinion or propaganda?
- Does the point of view appear objective and impartial?
- Are there political, ideological, cultural, religious, institutional or personal biases?

C. Assessing Existing Infrastructures

It is evident that the combination of incentives that promote reuse of existing infrastructure and reuse of them additionally with the provision of specialised education, skills and training would transform the way manufacturing sector currently operates and create opportunities for new business development.

There are multiple item scales developed and adapted from sources in the literature to measure investments in technology, infrastructure, and the performance of plants. Typically, relevant infrastructure Tests include software and hardware testing as also their dependencies required to run existing infrastructure and the running operations. Such testing applied in predictive maintenance may provide interesting challenges for any test manager. But unfortunately, there is no established methodology.

Thus, we propose some essential steps in order to ensure the trainees.

1. Ensure that trainees and trainers have broadband access to the existing infrastructure and resources, with a special focus on re-use of existing predictive maintenance tools.

Although connectivity to the infrastructure itself does not ensure the efficient use and reuse of technology to enable learning methodologies, the lack of it surely affects it negatively.

2. Ensure that every trainer and trainee has appropriate access to software and hardware resources.

Only when learners have the necessary tools to complete the learning activities are they able to realize the potential of education technologies fully. Educational personnel should make sure that all existing infrastructure is available to all trainees.

3. Support the development and use of openly licensed educational materials to promote innovative and creative opportunities for all learners and accelerate the development and adoption of new open technology-based learning tools and courses.

It is essential that trainees, trainers and relevant policymakers at all levels and in formal and informal spaces should consider the diversified learning paths through the use of openly licensed resources for educational purposes.

4. Create a comprehensive map and database of connectivity, infrastructure access, use of openly licensed educational resources, and their uses.

To understand the training goals and objectives better and progress toward bridging it, trainers should work in developing a map and database would allow for the easy access to infrastructure and open access learning material to empower them. In addition, the level of engagement with openly licensed learning materials should be made transparent as an indicator of progress toward equitable access and effective allocation of resources.

D. Potential of Open Learning Resources

OER, or Open Educational Resources, are free educational materials that are freely available to anyone and made available for further use under an open licence. They include textbooks, quizzes, videos and other educational resources that support learning.

The best-known definition of OER is the one from the 2012 UNESCO Paris Declaration, according to which open educational resources are:

"materials for teaching, learning and research, whether contained in any medium, whether digital or otherwise, in the public domain, or materials made available under open licenses enabling free access, use, adaptation and further dissemination of the material without any restrictions "Free licenses are based on the existing definition of intellectual property as set out in relevant international conventions; they recognize the author of the resource." (UNESCO Paris Declaration 2012)

The concept of Open Educational Resources was developed by David Wiley, who specified that they must meet the 5Rs principle:

1. Reuse - to reuse a resource in any way.
2. Revise - adapt, adjust and modify, e.g. translate a resource.
3. Remix - combining original content or its modifications with other OER to create a new quality (e.g. mashup).
4. Redistribute - distributing a copy of the original or modified, remixed content and sharing it (e.g. publishing a copy of a resource on the web for free download by others).
5. Retain - creating your own resource and making it present on the web.

(<https://pg.edu.pl/openscience/otwarta-komunikacja-naukowa/otwarte-zasoby-edukacyjne>)

Implementing OER requires careful planning, identification of resources, adaptation and development of guidelines. Using OER has advantages, such as cost savings, access to education and collaboration, as well as disadvantages, such as quality control, lack of support and copyright issues.

In recent years, the popularity of OER has increased due to several factors that can be counted among its advantages:

- **Cost savings** - the high cost of textbooks and other educational resources means that many people need help to afford the materials they need to study. OER is a

cost-effective alternative that allows access to high quality educational resources and materials at no extra cost.

- **Collaboration** - OERs encourage collaboration between (educators) teachers, trainers and other stakeholders by enabling them to create and share resources together. This leads to creativity, increased innovation and the sharing of best practice in education.

- **Quality and relevance** - the learning platform provided by OER is used to share its knowledge and expertise, thereby creating a high quality learning resource that others can use and improve upon. This ensures that the materials are relevant, up-to-date and engaging for learners.

- **Access to education** - OERs provide free access to educational resources, particularly in developing countries where access to educational materials may be limited.

- **Flexibility** - OERs are flexible, allowing teachers to adapt and modify resources to suit the curriculum and students' needs.

However, there are also some potential drawbacks to OER:

- **Lack of support**

The use of OER may require more work and support from faculty and staff to adapt and tailor materials to their curriculum.

- **Quality control**

The quality of OER can vary widely and a standardised system for assessing the quality of resources may need to be put in place.

- **Copyright issues**

OER is based on an open licensing framework, which can cause copyright and attribution issues. Before using OER, it is necessary to understand the terms and licensing requirements.

How do you convince sceptics that OER is the right choice?

- Start with something small

Start the implementation in a small area, such as a single topic or course. This will help demonstrate the benefits of OER and build support for their use.

- Highlight the savings

Highlighting the benefits they can provide to students will help convince sceptics who may resist change.

- Focus on quality

There are many high-quality resources available, so highlighting them and indicating their effectiveness can alleviate concerns about the quality of materials.

- Provide support and training

Sceptics may be more receptive to OER once they feel confident in their skills, use and adaptation of materials. Providing support and training to lecturers and staff will help build confidence and increase support for OER.

- Engaging with stakeholders

Engaging faculty, staff and students will help build support for OER implementation.

What is the future of OER?

As technology advances, OER will become even more prevalent in education. The development of online and blended learning will make it easier to access and distribute OER materials and this trend is likely to continue. In addition, many organisations are working to improve the accessibility and quality of materials, which will further increase their popularity in education.

Summary:

Open Educational Resources (OER) is a rapidly growing movement in education that can provide equal opportunities for students around the world. By offering cost savings for students, it encourages collaboration and innovation among educators and provides access to education where it might not otherwise exist. Implementing OER at your institution requires careful consideration and planning, but the benefits can be significant. Despite the potential drawbacks that exist, organisations are working to improve the quality and accessibility of OER, and its use is likely to continue to grow. When encountering resistance to implementing OER, focusing on cost savings, quality and the provision of training and support can help overcome sceptics. By adopting OER, institutions can contribute to a more accessible and equitable education system for all learners.

<https://elearningindustry.com/unleashing-the-potential-of-oer-the-advantages-and-challenges-of-open-learning-materials>

E. Repurposing existing e - learning materials

Over the past decade, researchers in the field of learning technology have introduced the concept of reusing educational materials and resources. It is expected that reuse, will bring an increase in the efficiency and quality of education in courses and training. Learning from a group of lecturers and other stakeholders working together on specific goals, e.g. through professional learning communities, project teams, multidisciplinary teams or data teams, leads to a shared sense of responsibility for professional development, commitment to common goals and learning. During the collaborative process, all stakeholders, share their best practices or examples, which are based on mistakes. It is important that in transformative learning, teams are made up of multidisciplinary people, i.e. not only lecturers, but also IT experts, subject matter experts and subject matter experts, so that participants can learn from each other.

Training facilitators, want to create and deliver engaging, effective and relevant learning experiences for participants. They don't have to, however, start from scratch every time. They can use existing resources and materials to improve the training content and delivery.

Here are some tips on how to repurpose existing learning resources and materials:

1. identify learning objectives and outcomes

Before you start looking at existing resources and materials, you need to have a clear idea of what you want participants to have learned and achieved by the end of the training. This will help you align the content and delivery with the learning objectives and outcomes. To define your objectives and learning outcomes, you can use the SMART (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound) criteria.

2. Review and evaluate existing resources and materials

Once the objectives and learning outcomes are defined, you can start searching for already existing learning materials and resources to support the training. These can range from books, articles, websites, videos or presentations, blogs, courses, webinars, case studies, reports, surveys, exercises, quizzes, games,, templates, checklists and other tools. A variety of sources can be used to find existing resources and materials, such as online databases, libraries, professional associations, colleagues, experts, mentors and learners. However, before using existing resources and materials, their quality, credibility, timeliness, relevance and accuracy should be checked and evaluated. The CRAAP test (Currency, Relevance, Authority, Accuracy, and Purpose) can be used to assess existing resources and materials.

3. Personalisation and customisation of existing resources and materials

Once you have selected existing resources and materials that can support your training, you need to personalise and adapt them to your objectives, audience and context. You can do this by updating, modifying, simplifying, extending or combining existing resources and materials to suit your needs and preferences. You can also add your own examples, insights, stories, questions, opinions or tips to enrich and personalise existing resources and materials. However, be sure to respect the copyright and intellectual property rights of the original sources and cite them appropriately.

4. Integrate existing resources and materials into the design and delivery of the training course

Finally, integrate existing resources and materials into the design and delivery of the training. This can be done by aligning them with the learning objectives and outcomes, choosing an appropriate delivery method and format, sequencing them in a logical and coherent way, balancing them with your own content and delivery, and creating transitions and connections between them. You can also use learner engagement such as discussions, reflections, interactive activities, feedback and assessments to improve outcomes and the learning experience. By using existing resources and materials, you can save time, money and effort and improve the quality, relevance and effectiveness of training content and delivery. However, care and selectivity should be exercised when selecting, evaluating, adapting and integrating existing resources and materials to ensure that they fit the learning objectives and outcomes, as well as the context and audience.

5. Here is what else to consider

Create a collaborative environment, encourage the involvement of trainees by sharing stories, examples or insights with each other that do not fit into any of the previous sections.

(Team, L. E., 2023)

To repurpose resources, you can use a variety of educational materials, examples of which are provided below:

Presentations - these are very popular for instructor-led training, but can also be used for self-training (for example, Powerpoint presentations can be easily shared).

Videos - these bring concepts to life by engaging students' multiple senses (using audio and visual media) and offering rich graphics and animations.

Written notes - comprehensive and clear notes help students by gathering information that can be easily transferred to different media (e.g. PDF documents, online notes or app-based notes).

Detailed training manuals - for more detailed or lengthy information (e.g. complex procedural or technical training), training manuals provide participants with a greater range of knowledge and reference material.

Infographics - virtually any resource can be turned into an infographic, especially if there is a flexible template that will fit any topic. Simply select the most important ideas/concepts and combine them with images. The focus should be on the 5 most important aspects of the topic that participants need to know to avoid cognitive overload. Relevant links where more information can be found and explored independently should also be included.

Checklists - offer learners quick and easy reference materials to help them remember critical steps, procedures and best practices.

Worksheets - offer guided instruction and allow learners to record their progress and answer questions.

(Zavvy, 2024)

Repurposing e-learning has many advantages. It saves time, money and at the same time ensures that the content offered is valuable and meaningful. Although it may seem simple, repurposing e-learning is not an easy task. It is more than just migrating content from one format to another. The process requires advance planning and strategy in a way that maintains learning effectiveness.

F. Reusing discussion forums as learning resources

Discussion forums are very popular and commonly used tools in web-based training (WBT) systems. Most commonly, discussion forums are sites where participants discuss topics related to the training material or the educational project they are working on.

These discussion forums have great pedagogical potential for education for future learners, as they contain questions and answers and entire discussions or examples created by previous learners.

Extracting useful information from discussion forums can be perceived as a rather strenuous task, and the results of such a process leave much to be desired. Below are described several ways to solve the problems associated with extracting information from discussion forums, and thus to reuse them as an educational resource.

One of the main reasons for the great success of discussion forums is the simple and self-explanatory nature of these solutions. Discussion forums have a very simple interface that is highly usable by a wide range of users with very different and probably non-technical skills. In this way, users simply read statements arranged in a tree or list and respond to them by activating a special reply button. Extracting knowledge from a discussion forum can be a difficult task mainly because of the organization of threads - in time sequence rather than by topic. This means that older threads are not easily accessible. Moreover, older threads are completely ignored and sometimes even completely deleted as they expire. Moreover, in each thread replies usually start with a simple "RE:" If we have more than one level of these replies usually start with as many abbreviations of "Reply" as many abbreviations as there are response levels. Therefore, extracting useful educational information from such discussion forums poses quite a serious problem.

Creating a conceptual schema from the concepts contained in the discussion forums can be a valuable resource of knowledge. The next step after creating the schema itself is to assign statements from the discussion forum to the concepts provided by the schema.

Essentially, a conceptual schema defines a series of concepts and the semantic relationships between them. The simplest conceptual schema can support only one type of semantic relations: Thus, such a conceptual schema arranges concepts into a simple tree of concepts and sub-concepts. (Helic D., Maurer H, Scerbakov N. 2004).

G. Conclusion

This booklet dives into the (re)use of existing infrastructures and learning resources. Throughout this booklet, are examined strategies for evaluating, assessing, and repurposing educational materials and infrastructural resources to optimize learning experiences.

The overarching aspiration of this report has been to bring together the current evidence on the effects of the (re)use of existing infrastructures and learning resources on educators, trainers, and learners. It is evident to be particularly strong on the impact of learning planning and on the learning progress. Thus, from the rigorous evaluation criteria of the CRAAP Test to the transformative impact of Open Educational Resources (OER), the power of leveraging existing resources to enhance education and training it is evident. What has also become clear in this report is the importance of connectivity, access, and collaboration in maximizing the benefits of existing infrastructures and materials, and the challenges and opportunities that arise in this dynamic landscape are highlighted.

The aim of the report is to define a starting point in helping educators, trainers, and learners on educational infrastructure investments to overcome the most common challenges and to reap all of the benefits that quality infrastructure can bring to teaching and learning achievement, educators and trainers retention, and community satisfaction.

H. References

Blakeslee, S. (2004). The CRAAP Test. DigitalCommons@EMU.

<https://commons.emich.edu/loexquarterly/vol31/iss3/4/>

Helic, D., & Scerbakov, N. (2003). Reusing discussion forums as learning resources in wbt systems. In IASTED International Conference Computers and Advanced Technology in Education, (Rhodes, Greece) (p. 223).

How do you leverage existing resources and materials to enhance your training content and delivery? (n.d.). Wwww.linkedin.com. Retrieved June 21, 2024, from <https://www.linkedin.com/advice/3/how-do-you-leverage-existing-resources-materialshttps://elearningindustry.com/unleashing-the-potential-of-oer-the-advantages-and-challenges-of-open-learning-materials>

Team, L. E. (2023, July 3). How to Leverage Instructional Design for Repurposed E-Learning. Learning Everest. <https://www.learningeverest.com/instructional-design-for-repurposed-e-learning/>

How to Create Training Materials That Will Engage, Motivate, and Transform Your People | Zavvy. (2024). Zavvy.io. <https://www.zavvy.io/pl/blog/tworzenie-materia%C5%82%C3%B3w-szkoleniowych>

Wikipedia Contributors. (2019, April 3). CRAAP test. Wikipedia; Wikimedia Foundation.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/CRAAP_test

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Train the Trainers Toolkit WebQuests for TN1-TN8

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**Module TN1: Learner happiness, motivation, engagement
and performance strategies**
[WebQuest]

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A. Introduction

The digital transformation of higher education was heavily accelerated by the COVID-19 crisis which posed the need for high quality and inclusive digital education. Such a challenge cannot be tackled in an isolated manner as it requires a true systemic and holistic approach to provide a suitable solution. There is a strong link between boosting the digital skills of three main actors (university lecturers, university administrators and students) and the improvement of EU's digital readiness towards inclusive and high-quality online education delivery (HBR, 2020, EC, 2020).

Whether isolated efforts of digitalization of higher education have been done recently, the outcomes of this approach have deemed to be inefficient leading to: frustrated academic staff unable to cope with technology, ineffectiveness of the taught content and delivery mode, limited engagement of students (lack of focus/attention/interest, limited connectionism and constructivism), lack of inclusiveness and personalized online teaching, rigidity of university administrators towards online teaching, and overall confusion and concern over the value of university services in such online format (EACEA, 2020).

B. Task

Your task is to assess learner motivation by first evaluating the current state of learners' motivation and empowerment by distributing evaluation forms/surveys. Next, explore online innovative and cutting-edge solutions to learner happiness and motivation and try to implement these solutions in a classroom setting. Finally, conduct a comparative assessment by doing the survey again to identify improvements in learner motivation. That being done, compile the information in a PPT presentation so that it can be shared with other colleagues working in education.

C. Process

Following these steps is recommended for the completion of the task:

1. Assess learner motivation

- Develop a survey or questionnaire to measure learners' motivation and perceived empowerment in the classroom.
- Administer the survey to the target group of learners.
- Collect and analyse the survey data to identify areas of improvement.

2. Research innovative/cutting edge solutions:

- Use online resources to explore innovative and cutting-edge solutions to enhance learner happiness and motivation.
- Consider solutions that align with the identified areas for improvement from the initial assessment.

3. Implement the chosen solution in a classroom setting.

4. Post-implementation assessment:

- Administer the same survey or questionnaire used in the initial assessment after implementing the innovative solutions.
- Collect and analyze the post-implementation data.
- Compare the data from the pre-implementation assessment with the post-implementation results.
- Identify and highlight areas of improvement in learner motivation and empowerment.

5. Create a PPT presentation:

- Summarize the assessment process, including the initial evaluation, solution research, implementation, and post-implementation assessment.
- Present the comparative analysis results, showcasing improvements in learner motivation.

D. Evaluation

Upon concluding this WebQuest, participants will achieve the following:

- Enhanced understanding of learner motivation
- Exploration and application of innovative solutions
- Data-driven decision-making skills

Evaluation criteria for participants:

- Clarity and relevance of survey questions
- Thorough data analysis and identification of key areas for improvement
- Selection of solutions aligned with identified areas for improvement
- Clear presentation of comparative data
- Organization, clarity, and visual appeal of the presentation
- Concise and impactful communication of the assessment process and results

E. Conclusion

Completing this Web Quest, participants have done a comprehensive exploration of learner motivation, delving into the assessment of current motivational levels of learners and actively seeking innovative solutions to enhance learner happiness. Throughout this task, participants have not only deepened their understanding of the learner motivation but have also translated this knowledge into actionable strategies for the classroom. These insights, documented and presented in a PPT presentation, would further serve as a valuable resource for colleagues in the education community.

F. References

- Brown KL. From teacher-centered to learner-centered curriculum: Improving learning in diverse classrooms. *Education*. 2003; 124:49-54
- Mickelson JJ, Kaplan WE, MacNeily AE. Active learning: A resident's reflection on the impact of a student centered curriculum. *Canadian Urological Association Journal*. 2009; 3(5):399-402
- Harris M, Cullen R. Learner-centered leadership: An agenda for action. *Innovation in Higher Education*. 2008; 33:21-28
- Misseyanni A, Papadopoulou P, Marouli C, Lytras MD. Active learning stories in higher education: Lessons learned and good practices in STEM education. In: Misseyanni A, Lytras MD, Papadopoulou P, Marouli C, editors. *Active Learning Strategies in Higher Education: Teaching for Leadership, Innovation, and Creativity*. Emerald Publishing Limited; 2018. pp. 75-105
- Freeman S, Eddy SL, McDonough M, Smith MK, Okoroafor N, Jordt H, et al. Active learning increases student performance in science, engineering, and mathematics. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*. 2014;111(23): 8410-8415

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**Module TN2: Reducing the percentage of drop-outs from
online education
[WebQuest]**

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A. Introduction

Welcome to the WebQuest on dropout rates in higher education and online learning! In this activity, you will explore the multifaceted reasons behind student dropouts, the impact on the educational ecosystem, and potential strategies for mitigating these challenges. Your mission is to understand the complexity of this issue and propose innovative solutions to improve student retention and success.

B. Task

Your task is divided into four main parts:

1. **Research:** Investigate the factors contributing to dropout rates in higher education and online learning environments.
2. **Analysis:** Compare and contrast the challenges faced by traditional and online learners.
3. **Solution Design** Propose a set of strategies aimed at improving student retention and success based on your research.
4. **Presentation:** Prepare a presentation or report summarizing your findings and recommendations.

C. Useful links and tools:

Concept map

Videos

How to curb the increasing dropout rate during pandemic

<https://m.facebook.com/punekarnews/videos/how-to-curb-the-increasing-dropout-rate-during-pandemic/435154694574521/>

5 ways to make online classes more interesting | Aravindhan Anbazhagan | TEDxCITBengaluru

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FJGsGxP6f9xs>

Tough Teacher Truths: How to improve online learning | Mark Russo | TEDxBasel
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=M2OShN_Aixs

Online education: Hello, goodbye? | Gino Camp | TEDxOpenUniversiteitHeerlen
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ddt3Vn_k-eQ

EMPOWER: Student Support, Student dropout, 28 September 2016
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zLIIOURPCec>

Rethinking online education | Megan Schaible | TEDxKassel
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0mxD7Ho7Jgg>

Online Classes - 10 Tips to improve your online learning experience
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kxANzDVkbqk>

Enhancing the user experience in online education through quality digital content delivery
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vmY0iAQXaWY>

Using Interactive Video to Improve Student Engagement Online | Teaching Online Masterclass
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5MMRdjNjyaA>

D. Process

1. **Research:**
 - Explore reputable educational websites, scholarly articles, and reports to gather information on dropout rates in higher education and online learning.
 - Focus on identifying learner-related, course-related, and instructor-related factors that influence dropout rates.
2. **Proceed to Analysis:**
 - Use the information gathered to compare the dropout challenges faced by students in traditional vs. online learning settings.
 - Highlight any unique factors or trends that emerge from your comparison.
3. **Move on to Solution Design:**
 - Brainstorm and develop a set of actionable strategies that institutions, instructors, and students themselves can implement to address the identified challenges.

- Consider innovative approaches that leverage technology, pedagogy, and support services.

4. Finalize with Presentation:

- Organize your findings and recommendations into a coherent presentation or report.
- Use visuals, charts, and bullet points to make your information accessible and engaging.

Resources

To get started, here are some resources that might help you in your research:

- [Educause Review, <https://er.educause.edu/>
- Journal of Online Learning and Teaching, <http://jolt.merlot.org/>
- The Chronicle of Higher Education, <https://www.chronicle.com/>
- Google Scholar for scholarly articles on dropout rates and persistence in higher education

Evaluation

Your project will be evaluated based on the following criteria:

- **Research Depth:** Quality and breadth of research on dropout rates and contributing factors.
- **Analysis:** Clarity and depth of your comparison between traditional and online learning dropout challenges.
- **Innovation in Solutions:** Creativity and feasibility of your proposed strategies for improving retention and success.
- **Presentation Quality:** Organization, clarity, and visual appeal of your final presentation or report.

E. Conclusion

By completing this WebQuest, you will gain a deeper understanding of the dropout rates in higher education and online learning, along with the challenges and potential solutions. This knowledge is crucial for educators, policymakers, and students as we work together to create more engaging and effective educational experiences.

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Module TN3: Inclusion of groups at risk and personalized education
[WebQuest]

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A. Introduction

Welcome to our WebQuest on the future of education in the field of predictive maintenance! As industries evolve with the advent of Industry 4.0, the demand for skilled professionals in predictive maintenance is growing. This WebQuest will guide you through the importance of adapting our educational approaches to meet these new challenges. You will explore how inclusive and personalized education strategies can prepare a diverse and adaptive workforce for the future.

B. Task

Your mission is to design a mini-curriculum for a course on predictive maintenance that incorporates principles of inclusive and personalized education. Your curriculum should:

1. Identify the key skills and knowledge areas required for predictive maintenance professionals in the era of Industry 4.0.
2. Propose innovative strategies to make the learning experience inclusive and personalized for students with diverse backgrounds and learning styles.
3. Suggest technological tools and platforms that could support online and flexible learning opportunities.

C. Process

1. **Research:** Start by exploring the concepts of predictive maintenance, inclusive education, and personalized learning. Use reputable sources to gather information on current trends and technologies in these areas.
2. **Analysis:** Reflect on the challenges and limitations of traditional education models in meeting the needs of today's learners, especially in technical fields like predictive maintenance.
3. **Design:** Based on your research, design a mini-curriculum for a predictive maintenance course. Include:
 - A brief overview of the course content, focusing on essential skills and knowledge.
 - Strategies for making the course inclusive and personalized.
 - Technological tools and platforms that will be used to deliver the course content.
4. **Collaboration:** Work in small groups (if possible) to discuss your ideas and refine your curriculum. Consider feedback from your peers to improve your design.

D.Evaluation

Your mini-curriculum will be evaluated based on the following criteria:

- **Relevance:** How well does the course content align with the needs of the predictive maintenance industry?
- **Inclusivity:** Are there clear strategies to accommodate diverse learning needs and backgrounds?
- **Innovation:** How creatively does the curriculum use technology to enhance learning?
- **Clarity:** Is the curriculum clearly articulated and easy to understand?

E. Conclusion

Reflect on your experience in creating this mini-curriculum. Consider the potential impact of inclusive and personalized education on the field of predictive maintenance. How might these approaches prepare students more effectively for the challenges and opportunities of Industry 4.0?

F. References

McKinsey & Company: "Demystifying Predictive Maintenance: How to Get Started" (2023) Link:

<https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/operations/our-insights/prediction-at-scale-how-industry-can-get-more-value-out-of-maintenance>

World Economic Forum: "Shaping the Future of Manufacturing: The Transformative Power of Predictive Maintenance" (2021) Link:

<https://www.weforum.org/agenda/>

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**Module TN4: Strategies for generating brain plasticity
and learning connections**
[Webquest]

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A. Introduction

The barriers associated with online learning correlate with some teachers' inability to build a personal relationship with their students and monitor their productivity during class. Providing the program content is only the first step, and probably not even the most important. Connecting with students should be an instructor's primary goal. Creating trust and convenient management of the virtual classroom for the user can be achieved by familiarizing oneself with the available technological tools.

Higher Education institutions have shifted towards online education in these past years due to the Corona pandemic. However, this presented a series of challenges for all parties involved, universities, teachers, and students. One of these challenges is related to finding the proper ways in which to support the students to become more efficient in their online learning. Different models and methods exist but there are still studies to be conducted in order to find the most appropriate way of doing things. Most likely there is not a single fit-all solution, and teachers and students alike need to experiment with several of these models and methods finding the one which best suits their needs.

B. Task

Your task consists of carefully analysing the AGES module and familiarizing yourself with behavioural/neuroscience teaching and learning methods. Here is a brief overview of the module:

To further help with the task, consult this website as well: <https://learningclusterdesign.com/2021/07/12/lcd-and-the-neuroscience-of-learning-ages/>

Please think and write down about how you can apply the AGES model to your learning/teaching program. First, reflect on your recent online classes and identify the moods associated with them. Following the AGES model, in each category (Attention, Generation, Emotion & Spacing) write down already existing strategies you recognize and the ones you would like to see implemented/improved. After this is done, create a PPT representing your research to motivate educators to improve their teaching practices.

C. Process

The following process should be followed:

- Create a spreadsheet with the main AGES modules and their brief descriptions;
- Rank your educators' performance by identifying the missing modules;
- Identify and rank at least 5 classes;
- Research solutions for the 5 classes you have identified needing improvement;
- Develop a PPT to suggest your recommendations.

D. Evaluation

Upon concluding this WebQuest, participants will achieve the following:

- Gain proficiency with the behavioural/neuroscience teaching strategies, AGES module.
- Comprehend the essential elements of utilizing the AGES module successfully.
- Propose enhancements based on the module.

Evaluation criteria for participants:

- Proficiency in analysing AGES Module.
- Capability to identify appropriate solutions for enhancing online education delivery.
- Competence in articulating key messages and recommendations through PPT format.

E. Conclusion

In conclusion, this webquest should serve as a valuable tool for users to assess the teaching methods and strategies of their educational institutions, offering a platform for users to discern and propose improvements in the area. The investigation into the implementation of AGES module by education providers culminates in the formulation of specific recommendations, and key improvements.

F. References

- J. A. Colliver, "Effectiveness of Problem-based Learning Curricula: Research and Theory," *Acad. Med.*, vol. 75, no. 3, pp. 259–266, 2000.
- Pitler, E. R. Hubbell, M. Kuhn, and K. Malenoski, *Using Technology with Classroom Instruction That Works*, vol. 22, no. 1. 2007.
- Owens, M.T. and Tanner, K.D., 2017. Teaching as brain changing: Exploring connections between neuroscience and innovative teaching. *CBE—Life Sciences Education*, 16(2), p.fe2.

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**Module TN5: Qualitative & effective open educational
resources (OERs)
[WebQuest]**

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A. Introduction

Welcome to the WebQuest designed for trainers in predictive maintenance. This quest aims to empower you to explore and integrate Open Educational Resources (OERs) into your training programs. As a trainer, harnessing the potential of OERs can enrich your teaching methodologies, engage learners effectively, and contribute to the collaborative advancement of predictive maintenance knowledge.

B. Task

Your task is to apply the knowledge gained through the booklet and slides on Open Educational Resources by searching the provided OER repositories for suitable materials for your teaching. Additionally, you are tasked with finding additional materials not listed in the booklet. Finally, you are asked to reflect on your current and future use of OERs in your teaching of predictive maintenance.

C. Process

Following these steps is recommended for the completion of the task:

OER Repository Exploration: Provide text documentation

- Visit the following OER repositories:
 - Mason OER Metafinder (MOM):
<https://oer.deepwebaccess.com/oer/desktop/en/search.html>
 - MERLOT: <https://www.merlot.org/merlot/index.htm>
 - OER Repositories & Platforms List: <https://oer-obp.pubpub.org/pub/wac0y6kx/release/12>
 - OER Commons: <https://oercommons.org/>
 - Open Education Consortium:
<https://www.oeconsortium.org/courses/>
 - OpenStax: <https://openstax.org/>
 - SkillsCommons: <https://www.skillscommons.org/handle/taaccct/1058>
- Explore the resources available for predictive maintenance training in each repository.
- Select two specific OERs from different repositories and provide a brief overview of their materials. You can use any word processor or websites like www.canva.com or www.genial.ly
- Identify one more source that offers valuable OERs not covered in the provided booklet and select one specific OER and provide a brief overview of the material in your document.
- Discuss how these three selected resources could be seamlessly integrated into your predictive maintenance training sessions.

Editing OERS: Provide link to OER

- Pick one OER that you want to integrate into your teaching.
- Modify the OER so it fits into your teaching.
- Make this OER available and provide a link to it. Make sure to properly identify where you got the original OER from and that you have modified it. You can use any word processor or websites like www.canva.com or www.genial.ly

Reflection: Provide text documentation

- Reflect on your training context and discuss how using OERs aligns with the unique demands and constraints of predictive maintenance training.
 - Are you already using OERs? Why/why not?
 - Would you effectively use OERs in the future? Why/why not?
- You can use any word processor or websites like www.canva.com or www.genial.ly

D.Evaluation

Upon concluding this WebQuest, participants will achieve the following:

- Enhanced proficiency in navigating and exploring OER repositories for predictive maintenance training resources
- Critical Analysis of the quality and relevance of OERs in predictive maintenance training
- Editing Skills of OERs in predictive maintenance training
- Considering future integration of OERs in predictive maintenance training

E. Conclusion

In conclusion, the completion of this task provides a comprehensive learning experience for predictive maintenance trainers. The exploration of OER repositories sharpens research skills, enabling trainers to identify and evaluate resources essential for enriching training programs. The subsequent analysis of specific OERs from varied sources fosters critical thinking, as trainers assess the applicability and quality of materials in the context of predictive maintenance. The editing of an OER further hones adaptation skills, emphasizing the importance of proper attribution and accessibility.

As trainers engage in the reflective component, they gain insights into the alignment of OERs with the unique demands of predictive maintenance training, considering both current practices and future integration. Overall, this task not only equips trainers with practical skills in navigating and modifying OERs but also encourages thoughtful consideration of their role in the evolving landscape of predictive maintenance education.

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PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

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Module TN6: Ethical learner analytics
[WebQuest]

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A. Introduction

In the predictive maintenance field, the integration of learner analytics can significantly enhance training programs' effectiveness and improve workforce performance. However, it's crucial to uphold ethical principles to ensure the responsible use of learner data. This WebQuest aims to explore and establish ethical guidelines for implementing learner analytics in the predictive maintenance field.

In the ever-evolving learning landscape, learner analytics is becoming increasingly important for improving teaching and learning experiences. However, it is essential to give priority to ethical aspects when collecting and using data on pupils, especially in the sensitive area of predictive maintenance. This WebQuest explores the ethical guidelines for analysing student data in the field of predictive maintenance, examining the challenges and opportunities it presents.

B. Task

You will learn about fundamental ethical principles, identify the ethical challenges specific to the field of predictive maintenance, and develop strategies to address these challenges.

This task involves a series of structured activities designed to bring the knowledge and skills needed to navigate the complexities of student data analysis in an ethical way.

Your task is to research and develop a set of ethical guidelines for utilizing learner analytics in predictive maintenance training programs. Consider various ethical considerations, including data privacy, transparency, fairness, and accountability.

Case studies and examples:

- The ethics of learning analytics in Australian higher education:
https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Deborah-West-5/publication/332263485_The_Ethics_of_Learning_Analytics_in_Australian_Higher_Education_DISCUSSION_PAPER_PREPARED_BY/links/5caab27e92851c64bd57b3f1/The-Ethics-of-Learning-Analytics-in-Australian-Higher-Education-DISCUSSION-PAPER-PREPARED-BY.pdf
- Ethical Challenges for Learning Analytics:
<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1237573.pdf>.
- Ethical Considerations for Using Learner Analytics in Preventive Maintenance Training:
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358973778_Early_Cerebellar_Development_in_Relation_to_the_Trigeminal_System.

C. Process

Activity 1: Fundamental ethical principles

Explore the fundamental ethical principles of student data analysis, such as:

- Informed Consent
- Transparency
- Equity
- Responsibility

Discuss the importance of these principles in the context of predictive maintenance.

Activity 2: Specific ethical challenges

Identify ethical challenges specific to the field of predictive maintenance, such as:

- Sensitive data (e.g. health, performance information)
- Use of algorithms and artificial intelligence
- Possible discrimination or bias

Analyse how these challenges can affect students and the learning process.

Activity 3: Strategies for addressing ethical challenges

Develop strategies to address identified ethical challenges, such as:

- Obtaining clear and concise informed consent
- Ensure transparency about how data is collected and used
- Implementing safeguards to prevent discrimination or bias

Consider the practical implications and feasibility of these strategies.

Activity 4: Implementation of ethical guidelines

Create a plan for implementing ethical guidelines in your own predictive maintenance context:

- Communicate the guideline to stakeholders
- Training staff on ethical issues
- Monitor and evaluate ethical compliance

Discuss the challenges and opportunities of implementing these guidelines.

D. Evaluation

Upon completion of this WebQuest, participants will the following:

- Gain competence in ethical guidelines for student data analysis in the field of predictive maintenance.
- Understand the ethical challenges specific to the field of predictive maintenance.
- Propose improvements based on the module.

Evaluation criteria for participants:

- Proficiency in the analysis of ethical guidelines.
- The ability to identify appropriate solutions to address ethical challenges in student data analysis.
- Competence in articulating key messages and recommendations in PPT format.

Formative evaluation: Participation in activities, discussions and reflections.

Summary evaluation: A written plan describing the ethical guidelines implemented and how they address the specific ethical challenges of predictive maintenance.

E. Conclusion

This WebQuest will serve as a valuable tool and provide a comprehensive exploration of the ethical guidelines for student data analysis in the field of predictive maintenance. By highlighting the importance of ethics in the collection and use of student data, this WebQuest aims to optimize learning experiences and improve teaching practices in the field of predictive maintenance.

This WebQuest will strengthen the knowledge and skills needed to navigate the complexities of student data analysis in an ethical way in the field of predictive maintenance. By understanding fundamental ethical principles, identifying specific ethical challenges and developing strategies to address them, you can contribute to creating an ethical and equitable learning environment for all students.

F. References

- L. Corrin, G. Kennedy, S. French, S. Buckingham Shum, K. Kitto, A. Pardo, D. West, N. Mirriahi, C. Colvin. (2019). The Ethics of Learning Analytics in Australian Higher Education. A Discussion Paper.
<https://melbourne-cshe.unimelb.edu.au/research/research-projects/edutech/the-ethical-use-of-learning-analytics>.
- S. Slade, P. Prinsloo. (2013). Learning Analytics: Ethical Issues and Dilemmas. American Behavioral Scientist, Special Issue Title: Learning Analytics, Volume 57 Issue 10
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0002764213479366>
- A. Alayan. (2019). Global Guidelines: Ethics in Learning Analytics. AACE Review.
<https://aace.org/review/global-guidelines-ethics-in-learning-analytics>.
- Niall Sclater. (2014). Code of practice for learning analytics. A literature review of the ethical and legal issues. Jisc, Commons Attribution 4.0,
<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>.
<https://solace.org.uk>.
- M. Rahimi-Balaei, H. Marzban, R. Hawkes. (2022). Early Cerebellar Development in Relation to the Trigeminal System. The Cerebellum, Volume 21, pages 784–790,
[DOI: 10.1007/s12311-022-01388-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12311-022-01388-2).
- M. Kazungu, E. Zhunusova, G. Kabwe, S. Günter. (2021). Correction: Kazungu et al. Household-Level Determinants of Participation in Forest Support Programmes in the Miombo Landscapes, Zambia. Sustainability 2021, 13(11), 5806,
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su13115806>.

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PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

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**Module TN7: Microcredential systems and skill
certification
[WebQuest]**

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A. Introduction

Micro-credentials play a pivotal role in certifying the outcomes of brief learning experiences, such as short courses or training sessions, providing a versatile and targeted means for individuals to acquire the knowledge and competences essential for their ongoing personal and professional advancement.

The rapid proliferation of shorter learning formats, like micro-credentials, is a global phenomenon, with Europe witnessing a surge in such opportunities. Offered by a diverse array of public and private providers in response to the growing demand for more adaptable and learner-centric educational and training approaches, these opportunities have the potential to extend education and training access to a broader spectrum of learners, including those from disadvantaged and vulnerable groups.

However, the realization of the full potential of micro-credentials hinges on the establishment of common standards ensuring their quality, transparency, cross-border comparability, recognition, and portability. Without such standards, the transformative impact of micro-credentials may be hindered.

B. Task

Your task consists of carefully analysing the micro-credential systems and skill certification module and familiarising yourself with definition, elements, and different aspects of micro-credentials. Here is the table that summarises elements that every micro-credential certification needs to have:

Mandatory elements:	
Learner identification	Micro-credential Title
County/Region of the Issuer	Awarding bodies
Date of Issuing	Learning outcomes
Workload needed to achieve the outcome (ECTS)	Level of the learning process leading to a learning outcome (e.g., European Qualifications Framework, Qualifications Frameworks in the European Higher Education Area, etc) if applicable.
Assessment type	Form of participation
Type of QA used to support the micro-credential	
Optional Elements:	
Requirements for enrollment in the learning activity	Monitoring and verification of identity during assessment
Attained grade	Options for integration/stackability
Additional details	

By referring to this table, as well as to the accompanying materials in this module, you would need to create your own mock-up micro-credential certificate by choosing the learning setting first (formal, non-formal or informal) and then follow all the principles and elements in order to produce a valid micro-credential certificate. You're free to choose the contents and overall look of the certificate.

Useful links and tools:

https://www.canva.com/en_gb/

<https://education.ec.europa.eu/education-levels/higher-education/micro-credentials>

<https://www.bcdiploma.com/en/blog/micro-credentials-platform-to-know-2021-05-28>

C. Process

The process will be as follows:

- Create a word file where you will explain the micro-credential certificate creation process.
- Pick a subject and create a certificate according to the materials provided.
- Insert the completed certificate into the same word file.

D. Evaluation

Content Relevance:

- The web quest effectively covered a wide range of topics related to micro-credentials, including their definition, principles, and recommendations for implementation.
- Learners were engaged through a mix of textual content, multimedia elements, and interactive activities.
- Participants will have gained insight and enhanced knowledge about creation of micro-credentials system, their definitions and elements needed to create them.

Evaluation criteria:

- Assessment of the participant's ability to apply micro-credential principles in a practical context through the creation of a mock-up certificate.
- Ability to reflect accurate application of micro-credential principles and elements.
- Capability in paying attention to design elements, ensuring a professional and aesthetically pleasing certificate.

E. Conclusion

In conclusion, this webquest sought to equip participants with the tools to navigate the micro-credential landscape with confidence and practical skill. By combining theoretical understanding with hands-on application, participants are better prepared to contribute to the dynamic and ever-expanding field of micro-credentials. It aimed not only to inform but to empower participants to apply their newfound knowledge.

The practical task of making a mock micro-credential certificate connected what participants learned with real-world application. It gave them a concrete way to express the principles and elements they studied.

F. References

Iniesto, Francisco & Ferguson, Rebecca & Weller, Martin & Farrow, Robert & Pitt, Rebecca. (2022). Introducing A Reflective Framework for the Assessment and Recognition of Microcredentials. *The Open/Technology in Education, Society, and Scholarship Association Journal*. 2. 1-24. [10.18357/otessaj.2022.2.2.37](https://doi.org/10.18357/otessaj.2022.2.2.37).

European Commission. 2022. *A European approach to micro-credentials*. Brussels: European Commission. <https://education.ec.europa.eu/education-levels/higher-education/micro-credentials#:~:text=Micro%2Dcredentials%20certify%20the%20learning,thei,r%20personal%20and%20professional%20development>

Wang, Libing, *Micro-credentials: An important part of a bigger ecosystem*, https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/micro-credentials-important-part-bigger-ecosystem?TSPD_101_R0=080713870fab2000c3c10dc18800f37ee7694f45ae100b69de6d8d181560ccfd016aea3fcc9c2c08294f35d9143000110ff12cb83d25ce3204c1388a2f52e00d44d5d4f72d8385898d4ee439e2e35cf2d6684a42912cbc07f6b03d1dcd93, UNESCO, 2023

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PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

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**Module TN8: (Re)use existing infrastructures and
learning resources
[WebQuest]**

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F. Introduction

In today's rapidly evolving educational landscape, the ability to leverage existing infrastructures and learning materials is paramount to fostering effective teaching and learning experiences. The positive benefits associated with creating an educated population are spelled out in the latest World Bank's World Development Report (WDR) entitled "Learning to Realize Education's Promise" (World Bank 2018). This WebQuest aims to explore the strategies and methodologies involved in evaluating, assessing, and repurposing educational resources to optimize learning outcomes. As educators, trainers, and learners, it's essential to recognize the wealth of resources available and harness their potential to enhance education and training initiatives. Throughout this WebQuest, it will delve into the significance of (Re)using Existing Infrastructures and Learning Resources, examining the challenges and opportunities it presents in both traditional and digital learning environments.

G.Task

Your task will engage you in a series of structured activities aimed at evaluating, assessing, and repurposing educational materials and infrastructural resources to optimize learning experiences.

Each task is meticulously designed to equip you with the necessary skills and knowledge to navigate the complexities of leveraging existing resources effectively. From mastering the CRAAP Test for source evaluation to harnessing the transformative potential of Open Educational Resources (OER), you will delve into various strategies and techniques tailored to enhance education and training outcomes. By actively participating in these tasks, you will not only deepen your understanding of the subject matter but also develop practical skills essential for promoting innovation and sustainability in educational practices.

Useful links and tools:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2WJN-U4j2_A

H. Process

The process will be as follows:

- Follow a structured approach to complete the task:
 - Begin by evaluating existing resources to determine their *suitability for reuse*.
 - Assess infrastructural needs by identifying gaps or areas for *improvement*.
 - *Repurpose learning materials and infrastructure* based on identified objectives and outcomes.

- Utilize the CRAAP Test for evaluating sources:
 - Assess the *Currency, Relevance, Authority, Accuracy, and Purpose* of each source.
 - Determine the *reliability and credibility* of information before incorporating it into learning materials.

- Implement strategies for repurposing e-learning materials:
 - *Identify learning objectives and outcomes* to guide the repurposing process.
 - *Customize existing resources* to align with specific audience needs and preferences.
 - *Integrate repurposed materials* into the design and delivery of training courses for maximum effectiveness.

- Provide guidance on using relevant tools and methodologies:
 - *Offer instructions* on how to apply the CRAAP Test effectively.
 - *Share strategies and best practices* for repurposing e-learning materials, such as personalization and customization techniques.
 - *Encourage learners to engage in hands-on activities and discussions to deepen their understanding* of the (re)use process.

I. Evaluation

Upon concluding this WebQuest, participants will achieve the following:

- Gain proficiency (Re)use existing infrastructures and learning resources strategies and CRAAP test.
- Comprehend the essential elements of utilizing the CRAAP test successfully.
- Propose enhancements based on the module.

Evaluation criteria for participants:

- Proficiency in analysing CRAAP test.
- Capability to identify appropriate solutions for reuse and use existing infrastructures and learning resources strategies.
- Competence in articulating key messages and recommendations through PPT format.

J. Conclusion

In conclusion, this WebQuest will serve as a valuable tool and provide a comprehensive exploration of the use and reuse of existing infrastructures, material and learning resources, offering valuable insights and practical guidance for educators, trainers, and learners. By emphasizing the importance of evaluating, assessing, and repurposing educational materials and infrastructural resources, this WebQuest aims to optimize learning experiences and enhance teaching practices.

K. References

World Bank. 2018. World Development Report 2018: Learning to Realize Education's Promise. Washington, DC: World Bank.
<https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/28340>

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**Interactive learner-persona based simulator as
assessment tool: Multiple choice questions for modules:
TN1-TN8**

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Module TN1: Learner happiness, motivation, engagement and performance strategies

Question n°	Question
1	What is emphasized as a crucial factor influencing student learning?
2	According to Clark et al. (2016), what is the impact of goal setting on student performance?
3	How can educators enhance learning outcomes using technology?
4	What is a key characteristic of constructivist learning environments, as noted by Jonassen (1994)?
5	According to Siemens (2005), what is a critical principle of connectivism?
6	How does connectivism differ from traditional views of learning, according to Anderson and Dron (2011)?
7	What is emphasizing regarding 21st-century skills?
8	According to the Foundation for Young Australians (2017), why are transferable skills important for young people?
9	What is emphasized as crucial for the effectiveness of technology in learning?
10	What is the primary focus of active learning?
11	What are some characteristics of active learning strategies?
12	How does the constructivist learning theory contribute to active learning, according to Hativa (2000)?
13	What does Mickelson et al. (2009) suggest about the role of students during active learning based on constructivist theory?
14	What is the primary goal of learner empowerment?
15	According to Kirk et al. (2016), what benefits are associated with highly empowered students?
16	What are the four dimensions of empowerment, according to Thomas and Velthos as cited in Frymier and Houser (1996)?
17	How can instructors improve students' involvement and higher-order thinking tasks?
18	What is the main purpose of formative assessment in the context of active learning?
19	How does peer assessment contribute to the empowerment of learners in the teaching and learning process?
20	What are the characteristics of effective feedback, according to Hattie and Timperley (2007)?
21	How could trainers achieve ongoing collaboration in an online and/or asynchronous mode, according to Yoon et al. (2020)?

Module TN2: Reducing the percentage of drop-outs from online education

Question n°	Question
1	What is dropout primarily defined as?
2	Which of the following terms is synonymous with dropout?
3	What does the term "retention" mean in the context of online education?
4	Why are dropout rates in higher education a significant concern?
5	Which challenge is NOT mentioned for online learners?
6	What significantly affects the persistence of online learners?
7	What is a student-focused definition of persistence?
8	How do dropout rates impact universities?
9	For students, what does dropping out entail?
10	Which is NOT a persistence factor related to online learners?
11	Which factor influences persistence related to online courses and course providers?
12	What role do online instructors play in reducing dropout rates?
13	How can dropout rates in online courses be reduced?
14	What is a proactive measure to address dropout rates?
15	What is important in the initial session of a course to set student expectations?
16	The use of learning analytics is suggested for:
17	Providing proactive academic advisory is aimed at:
18	Continuous quality assurance involves:
19	What is NOT a suggested action to reduce dropout rates in online courses?
20	Dropout rates can be mitigated by:

Module TN3: Inclusion of groups at risk and personalized education

Question n°	Question
1	What is a major limitation of traditional education models?
2	What gap is highlighted in traditional education regarding predictive maintenance?
3	Who are considered vulnerable in educational settings?
4	What challenge do at-risk groups face in predictive maintenance education?
5	What is a key advantage of fostering inclusion in education?
6	How does inclusion affect student success in predictive maintenance education?
7	What defines personalized education?
8	What is crucial for curriculum design in personalized education?
9	What role does technology play in personalized learning?
10	Which tool is essential for online delivery in education?
11	What does adaptive learning leverage for personalized education?
12	How does predictive maintenance data enhance education?
13	What is a strategy for implementing personalized education?
14	What recommendation is given for educators in predictive maintenance?
15	What is essential for engaging students in predictive maintenance education?
16	How can educators overcome the one-size-fits-all model?
17	What barrier does inclusive education aim to break down?
18	What is a benefit of using technology in predictive maintenance education?
19	Why is real-world relevance important in personalized education?
20	What outcome does fostering diversity and inclusion in education aim for?

Module TN4: Strategies for generating brain plasticity and learning connections

Question n°	Question
1	The AGES model, proposed by the Associate Professor of Psychology at New York University Lila Davachi, stands for:
2	According to the AGES model, is it possible to multi-task while learning something new?
3	Adults build on prior learning and take as much responsibility as they want for their ongoing learning (Illeris, 2010). As a result, self-directed learning methods are highly effective in adults.'
4	Including games in learning programs with relevant context increases learning outcomes.
5	When 'spacing' learning content, it is important to:
6	Of the factors that influence student learning, which one of the most potent?
7	People who are actively engaged, no matter the situation, are more productive.
8	Technology can aid motivation and engagement only when:
9	According to Sheninger and Murray, 2017, empowerment is improved through:
10	A pedagogical strategy that allows students to work collaboratively on meaningful tasks at their own level and pace (Prensky, 2001) through activities such as task-based learning is called:
11	Springer et al. (1999) investigated task-based learning further and found that the best results, in terms of positive effect size, were to be obtained through:
12	Neuroplasticity is:
13	Cortisol, released during stress, depresses synaptic plasticity.
14	Dopamine and ACh, released during states of motivation and attention, do NOT boost synaptic plasticity.
15	Behavioral learning and the formation of memories is associated with:
16	How many hours have the researchers estimated for young people being engaged on some form of Internet-connected device?
17	A connectivism learning theory:
18	As noted by Jonassen, 1994, there are how many main characteristics of constructivist learning environments?
19	Who is considered as the father of connectivist learning theory?
20	SMART Objectives stands for:

Module TN5: Qualitative & effective open educational resources (OERs)

Question n°	Question
1	What is the core principle behind Open Educational Resources?
2	When did the academic uptake and development of OERs take place?
3	How did the Covid-19 pandemic impact the uptake of Open Educational Resources?
4	Which organization coined the term "Open Educational Resources" during a 2002 conference?
5	According to the OECD, what does OER include, besides learning content?
6	What is the significance of the Cape Town Open Education Declaration, as mentioned in the text?
7	According to David Wiley, what are the 5R activities/permissions associated with OERs?
8	Why are materials accessed through library subscriptions not considered OERs?
9	What is one of the advantages of OERs for educational institutions based on the altruistic argument?
10	How do OERs contribute to financial savings for students and parents?
11	What is one challenge associated with OERs related to Quality Assurance?
12	How can trainers effectively integrate OERs into their teaching, according to the recommendations?
13	What should trainers emphasize when using OERs to avoid common pitfalls?
14	What is the potential drawback of the proliferation of OER initiatives in recent years, according to the text?
15	What future trend is associated with the digitization of media in the development of OERs?
16	What is one advantage of OERs for individual involvement highlighted in the text?
17	What is recommended to trainers to ensure the cultural relevance of OER materials?
18	What is a potential challenge associated with the establishment of central platforms for OERs?
19	According to the text, what should trainers emphasize when using OERs to avoid common pitfalls?
20	What is the primary driver in the implementation of OERs related to copyright issues, as mentioned in the text?

Module TN6: Ethical learner analytics

Question n°	Question
1	What does ethical learner analytics entail in the context of preventive maintenance?
2	Which is the least significant benefit of ethical learning analytics could offer?
3	Which cutting-edge technology assists in launching an effective learning system in predictive maintenance?
4	Based on what you know/learned, what is the impact of using emerging technologies such as AI & Machine Learning in predictive maintenance?
5	In what type of data does the advanced learning systems rely on?
6	What is emphasized as crucial for the effectiveness of technology in learning?
7	Why is it important to prioritize ethical considerations in the application of learner analytics?
8	How can data privacy and security be maintained when collecting and analyzing learner data for preventive maintenance purposes?
9	What steps can organizations take to ensure transparency in the use of learner analytics for preventive maintenance?
10	Discuss the potential risks of using learner analytics in preventive maintenance without proper ethical guidelines.
11	How can bias be mitigated in the development and implementation of learner analytics models for preventive maintenance?
12	What role does informed consent play in ethical learner analytics practices for preventive maintenance?
13	Explain the concept of fairness and equity in the context of using learner analytics for preventive maintenance decision-making.
14	How can organizations ensure accountability and governance in the use of learner analytics for preventive maintenance?
15	What measures can be taken to prevent the misuse of learner data?
16	How can organizations promote inclusivity and diversity in the development and application of learner analytics?
17	Explain the concept of algorithmic transparency and its importance in ethical learner analytics for preventive maintenance.
18	What strategies can be employed to ensure continuous reflection and improvement of ethical learner analytics practices in preventive maintenance?
19	How can organizations foster a culture of ethical awareness and responsibility among stakeholders involved in preventive maintenance analytics?
20	What role does data stewardship play in ensuring ethical learner analytics practices in preventive maintenance?
21	Reflect on a real-world scenario where ethical considerations were paramount in the application of learner analytics for preventive maintenance, and discuss the lessons learned.

Module TN7: Microcredential systems and skill certification

Question n°	Question
1	What is the primary aim of the European recommendation on micro-credentials?
2	What role do micro-credentials play in individuals' learning pathways?
3	What key challenge does the booklet address regarding micro-credentials in Europe?
4	How do micro-credentials contribute to addressing skill gaps?
5	European businesses and employers grapple with:
6	What is the European Pillar of Social Rights Action Plan's target regarding adult training participation?
7	How can micro-credentials be designed and issued?
8	What is the primary obstacle to the realization of the full potential of micro-credentials?
9	How do micro-credentials relate to the European Green Deal?
10	What is the overarching goal of the European Skills Agenda?
11	How does the European Qualifications Framework (EQF) contribute to the recognition of micro-credentials?
12	What role do micro-credentials play in supporting the goals of the Digital Education Action Plan 2021-2027?
13	What is the main focus on the validation of non-formal and informal learning?
14	What is the purpose of Europass?
15	How does the content suggest micro-credentials can contribute to a socially fair recovery?
16	What is a key characteristic of micro-credentials?
17	What are the three main characteristics of micro-credentials?
18	Which of the following is NOT listed as a mandatory element for describing micro-credentials?
19	What is an example of an optional element for describing micro-credentials?
20	How many principles describe micro-credentials?

Module TN8: (Re)use existing infrastructures and learning resources

Question n°	Question
1	What does CRAAP test serve for?
2	What does CRAAP acronym stand for?
3	Currency in CRAAP test evaluates:
4	OER stands for:
5	What principle do OER need to meet?
6	What is the 5r's principle?
7	Why is collaboration considered one of the biggest advantages of OER?
8	What are some potential drawbacks to OER?
9	What is the best way to identify learning objectives and outcomes when learning via OER?
10	What educational tools can you use to repurpose existing materials?
11	What are the advantages of repurposing existing materials?
12	Why do discussion forums have learning potential?
13	What is the future of OER?
14	Which stakeholders need to be taken into account when reusing OER?
15	In order to facilitate taking using discussion forums as learning source, it is essential to:
16	What criteria are recommended for evaluating existing resources and materials before repurposing them?
17	Why is it important to personalize and customize existing resources and materials during repurposing?
18	What is one of the main challenges associated with extracting useful information from discussion forums?
19	What is suggested as a solution for organizing information from discussion forums into a usable format?
20	What is the aim of the booklet on (Re)use of Existing Infrastructures and Learning Resources?

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[Collection of demonstrative videos for modules TN1- TN8](#)

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Module TN1: Learner happiness, motivation, engagement and performance strategies

Video n°	Video Title	Video Link
1	Student Motivation - 20 Ways Teachers can Motivate their Learners	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QBHSO-TBvJ4&ab_channel=EtacudeEnglishTeachers
2	Student Motivation: How to Motivate Students to Learn	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ydsCANTzVuY&ab_channel=TeachingsinEducation
3	Behaviorism, Cognitivism, Constructivism	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=svw3eyIPTvY&ab_channel=NajihaNajwa
4	The Science of Teaching, Effective Education, and Great Schools	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KVLTXkyxioA&ab_channel=Sprouts
5	The Active Learning Method	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xxVxgQJwV7w&ab_channel=Sprouts
6	The Project-Based Learning Method	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=V2Oa4OkkTtw&ab_channel=Sprouts
7	Active Learning Strategies Parts 1-2	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rq67bUJI8LA&ab_channel=UTSATeachingandLearningServices
		https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CI35poMORCg&ab_channel=UTSATeachingandLearningServices
8	The Shift from Engaging Students to Empowering Learners	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BYBJQ5rIFjA&ab_channel=JohnSpencer
9	10 Ways to Empower Students With Choice	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=L08wNizulOY&ab_channel=JohnSpencer
10	Community Skills 4: Asset-based Community Development	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ena4Rhe_IPo&ab_channel=NUSOfficeofStudentAffairs
11	The Meaning of Feedback in Assessment for Learning	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SVyNfgXFruA&ab_channel=CRIEDO-UAB
12	The 10 Do's and Don'ts of Feedback	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JzmD19_GW8g&ab_channel=CRIEDO-UAB

Module TN2: Reducing the percentage of drop-outs from online education

Video n°	Video Title	Video Link
1	How to curb the increasing dropout rate during pandemic	https://m.facebook.com/punekarnews/videos/how-to-curb-the-increasing-dropout-rate-during-pandemic/435154694574521/
2	5 ways to make online classes more interesting	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FJsGxP6f9xs
3	Tough Teacher Truths: How to improve online learning	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=M2OShN_Aixs
4	Online education: Hello, goodbye?	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ddt3Vn_k-eQ
5	EMPOWER: Student Support, Student dropout	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zLIIOURPCec
6	Rethinking online education	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0mxD7Ho7Jgg
7	Online Classes - 10 Tips to improve your online learning experience Enhancing the user experience in online education through quality digital content delivery	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kxANzDVkbgk
		https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vmY0iAQXaWY
8	Using Interactive Video to Improve Student Engagement Online	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5MMRdjNjyaA
9	How to curb the increasing dropout rate during pandemic	https://m.facebook.com/punekarnews/videos/how-to-curb-the-increasing-dropout-rate-during-pandemic/435154694574521/

Module TN3: Inclusion of groups at risk and personalized education

Video n°	Video Title	Video Link
1	Flexible Path & Pace in a Personalized Learning Classroom	http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1tn3H7dIXGg
2	Inclusive Education	http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Dq3sQCwqxv0
3	The Power of AI in Education: Personalized Learning, Intelligent Tutoring, and Beyond	http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Lxil-oEo-XU
4	Inclusive Education PLP Webinar	http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pr-3D15Xn_4
5	Personalized Learning: Three Ideas for Your Class	http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=USAHX56IWqE
6	Smart Choices for Digital Delivery: VILT, Asynchronous e-Learning & Beyond	http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QWCUQnPXVQ
7	Internal Communications – Engaging and Social News Delivery Strategies	http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xrIrrCfjOLM
8	Beyond content delivery: How to make online learning truly participatory?	http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dQ_xTfRiD2c
9	How to deliver eCommerce beyond limits - Mark Adams @eCommerceGrowthSummit	http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FX3NDT5N594
10	Webinar - Online learning beyond PDFs and Zoom	http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_BZ4i9tLV5k

Module TN4: Strategies for generating brain plasticity and learning connections

Video n°	Video Title	Video Link
1	Neuroplasticity and learning explained	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=88OL8NdkV-s
2	Brain Plasticity: A Mental Health Renaissance Hani Akasheh TEDxPSUT	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=u9YGGjAzOt0
3	If your attention span has been hijacked, here's how to take it back. Amishi Jha	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NYcbDtMdFm4
4	How Good Is Your Attention Span? (TEST)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vhaYnT08kLI
5	Can You Pass This Multitasking Test? Psychology of Attention	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=z-8JdsNWZiM
6	Understand & Improve Memory Using Science-Based Tools Huberman Lab Podcast #72 -	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=szqPAPKE5tQ
7	Tools to Enhance Working Memory & Attention -	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=COITmOFM4Qs
8	Science-Based Mental Training & Visualization for Improved Learning Huberman Lab	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ORYyQRQFgFk
9	Focus Toolkit: Tools to Improve Your Focus & Concentration Huberman Lab Podcast #88 -	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yb5zpo5WDG4
10	#1 Neuroscientist: Truth About Laziness, Discipline, Exercise, Stress & Journaling Andrew Huberman	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NKyyF9MOXn4
11	1. How to triple your memory by using this trick	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JsC9ZHi79jo
12	Test your might! • Shaolin Spirit Shi Heng Yi TEDxBaiaMare -	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lq0Y5QN8WQE

Module TN5: Qualitative & effective open educational resources (OERs)

Video n°	Video Title	Video Link
1	Open Educational Resources (OER) by UNESCO:	https://www.youtube.com/watch?app=desktop&v=rbJEARDuFag
2	Open Educational Resources (OER) and innovation: Why OER?	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=G7KFAE5SXgk
3	EdTech Chats December: Open Education Resources by Open LMS	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_hjm7Bs6RME
4	OER Ted Talk by Katie Gosa	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dUgqdSOD9bg
5	Open Educational Resources (OER) and Adult Education	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bgr0zsGQojA
6	Webinar: Creating and Sharing Open Educational Resources (OER) by National Forum T&L	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6JgoUbED4rM
7	A Review of the Effectiveness & Perceptions of Open Educational Resources as compared to textbooks by Research Shorts	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SX0K0hb_xKE
8	Open Educational Resources: What and Why by UAlberta Library	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=74mlgISSMdg
9	Open Educational Resources by University of Groningen:	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iRG8CsPAExg
10	Finding and Remixing OER: A Practical Introduction by Open Education Conference	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OVpVZzghiHE

Module TN6: Ethical learner analytics

Video n°	Video Title	Video Link
1	Learning analytics in a nutshell	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XscUJZ8dla-8&ab_channel=SocietyforLearningAnalyticsResearch
2	Learning Analytics and Ethics in MOOC	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2Bdu3X7IW0M&ab_channel=CommonwealthofLearning
3	Ethical Issues in Learning Analytics	https://ethics.mooc.ca/cgi-bin/page.cgi?module=7
4	Ethics and Learning Analytics	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bgMTxt9pRzw&ab_channel=AperreoFoundation
5	Technological Frameworks on Ethical and Trustworthy Learning Analytics	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tMroNHLyCsE&ab_channel=LearningAnalyticsLearningNetwork
6	Ethical AI: Addressing Bias & Algorithmic Fairness	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IO1Q320w6C8&ab_channel=RSAConference
7	Data Ethics 101: A Comprehensive Guide for Beginners	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ICNCRfDGvC8&ab_channel=TheDataGovernor
8	GDPR Employee Training	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lvC-WSDP7WQ&ab_channel=ComplyFox
9	GDPR Training by Aim	https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL3hXnyjyrT0eKiDHLukn4eVsyZJHmSLwQ
10	Identifying Analytic Condition Indicators Predictive Maintenance	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pcXr8l2QvHw&ab_channel=MATLAB
11	Asset Analytics and Predictive Maintenance with PlantSight	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SoXAz47hq8g&ab_channel=SiemensKnowledgeHub

Module TN7: Microcredential systems and skill certification

Video n°	Video Title	Video Link
1	Micro-credentialing Basics	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vrsqIaP3ilk
2	Micro-credential vs Certificate: The future of Education	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UK4nOAp7D6I
3	Are Micro-Credentials the Future of Education?	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ttsZ08qIawA
4	Competencies, Digital Credentials & Community Change	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dVdaEoCvBJ4
5	Making Skills Transparent Through A Unified Micro-Credential Framework	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pvPmL2wKK9s
6	Digital Credentials Roundtable: Models for Micro credentials in HED (April 17, 2023)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kn42ZnF5Kd4
7	Build Trust in Your Educational Software Ecosystem	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PID5mGVAeLw
8	Adaptive learning	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PEPGNaXZNSI
9	Digital Credentials Roundtable: All Digital Badges are Not Created Equal (24 October 2022)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3AASZuV9AK4
10	Webinar: European approach to Micro credentials	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YGVuCd92jug

Module TN8: (Re)use existing infrastructures and learning resources

Video n°	Video Title	Video Link
1	Open Educational Resources (OER) and innovation: Why OER?	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=G7KFAE5SXgk
2	The OERs - Open Educational Resources	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-xGRztrWv-k
3	Open Educational Resources	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3uRkheB0-CU
4	4 Design Tips for Building Better Learning Materials	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZSkPw-8vwbc
5	What Types of Learning Materials and Resources Could You Teach Your Course With?	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2IGcwCITTYE
6	Workshop Demo: Modifying & Creating Open Educational Resources	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gjtqLHGtM4
7	The e-Learning Advantage	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nzV1NmhC7ik
8	Advantages of e-Learning	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sxUQsKxcOYM
9	Evaluating Sources using CRAAP	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2WJN-U4j2_A
10	Evaluating Resources with CRAAP	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UST2zJjGQ4I
11	The C.R.A.A.P. Test	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=b5pP6vd99pl
12	Teaching with Online Discussion Forums	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=p3xo1RipS-c

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Annex I:

Additional learning material for modules TN1-TN8

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Presentation slides for modules: TN1-TN8

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Presentation slides containing educational material, outlining modules TN1-TN8, can be found in the project repository using the following link:

[https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1Wg9xm3LV_JOHozdTG_SGkHjfKJ4EXeZa?
usp=drive_link](https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1Wg9xm3LV_JOHozdTG_SGkHjfKJ4EXeZa?usp=drive_link)

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[Videos of presentation slides for modules: TN1-TN8](#)

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Videos of presentation slides containing educational material, outlining modules TN1- TN8, can be found in the project repository using the following link:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1Wg9xm3LV_JOHozdTG_SGkHjfKJ4EXeZa?usp=drive_link

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Storyboards for modules: TN1-TN8

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[Annex II: Train-the-trainers toolkit in multiple languages](#)

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The complete train-the-trainers toolkit with additional learning material can be accessed in multiple languages:

The complete train-the-trainers toolkit with additional learning material (**Romanian**), can be found in the project repository using the following link:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1EW7wLuZOtrdxySMYoXJtcPTFiAbaJjY?usp=drive_link

The complete train-the-trainers toolkit with additional learning material (**Greek**), can be found in the project repository using the following link:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1xrqsrWfBN2-PdKSOisDbmds-liYLALwH?usp=drive_link

The complete train-the-trainers toolkit with additional learning material (**German**), can be found in the project repository using the following link:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1CjWebi38wjW78h3E_zyEsQ3-qmOyiPUI?usp=drive_link

The complete train-the-trainers toolkit with additional learning material (**Italian**), can be found in the project repository using the following link:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1XVyU_HmRhSr8RMuQ5-stTJ6KGT06nxQT?usp=drive_link

The complete train-the-trainers toolkit with additional learning material (**Dutch**), can be found in the project repository using the following link:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1Jmh-qO28orjyAHkBdc05_pdFk3I6azl?usp=drive_link

The complete train-the-trainers toolkit with additional learning material (**Serbian**), can be found in the project repository using the following link:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1F5hKdhx-wBjLGoU8Uu5BnfcNYINwU9b9?usp=drive_link

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